

ARCS 8.0

ANNUAL RESEARCH ON CITIES SUMMIT 8.0

ABSTRACTS

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Future of Sustainable Urbanism in the Global South

8-10 February 2024

SCHOOL OF HUMAN SETTLEMENTS
XIM UNIVERSITY

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FUTURE OF SUSTAINABLE URBANISM
IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH**

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Book of Abstracts**Annual Research on Cities Summit (ARCS) 8.0****International Conference on Future of Sustainable Urbanism in the Global South**

8-10 February 2024

School of Human Settlements, XIM University, Bhubaneswar***Edited by:***

Arpan Paul, Annam Sai Kiran, Tiyali Bose and Jublee Mazumdar

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MESSAGE FROM THE VICE-CHANCELLOR'S DESK

On behalf of XIM University, I extend a warm welcome to all the delegates who have come from around the world to participate in the ARCS 8.0 the Eighth Annual Research on Cities Summit.

The theme of this year's summit, 'Future of Sustainable Urbanism in the Global South' could not be more timely or relevant.

As the world's population continues to urbanise at an unprecedented rate, it is crucial that we invest in education and research in the fields of urban management, governance, and planning. By working together, we can develop new and innovative solutions to the complex challenges facing our cities, from climate change and inequality to the need for affordable housing, access to clean water, sanitation, and sustainable transportation.

XIM University's identity is distinguished by its philosophy of 'Inspiring Futures' by not just walking the well-trodden path but striking out and exploring new paths. To address various developmental challenges

confronting our cities and regions, the School of Human Settlements at XIM University has pioneered innovative courses in the areas of Urban Management, Urban Governance, and Planning. By providing students with a comprehensive education in these areas, we equip them with the knowledge and skills necessary to address complex challenges and create sustainable, livable cities for all.

I believe that the insights and knowledge shared at this summit will be instrumental in helping us to create more sustainable, humane, and just cities for all. I urge you to engage in robust and productive discussions and to make the most of the opportunity to connect with your peers and colleagues from around the world.

Once again, welcome to XIM University, and I look forward to a successful summit.

Fr. Antony R. Uvari, S.J.
Vice Chancellor, XIM University

FOREWORD

The Annual Research on Cities (ARCS) Conferences was started by the Xavier Center for Urban Management and Governance (XUMG) in 2017, as a national platform for regular knowledge sharing and live discussion about urban planning and management across professional, academic, policy, and development spheres. It also marked the inception of a new professional field in India with the launch of the MBA-Urban Management and Governance programme at XIM University. This emerged from the conviction that sustainable urban development required not just spatial planning, but also managerial expertise for development and operation of urban systems. With the formation of the School of Human Settlements (SHS) at XIM University in 2019 and the launch of the Masters in Urban and Regional Planning Programme in the School, the ARCS has diversified further across fields and dimensions of urban development.

As numerous policy and programmatic initiatives to address urban issues in India are rolled out, a large variety of efforts, experiments, and innovations in urban planning, management, and development are implemented across cities by state, civil society, and private-sector actors. Absence of platforms for sharing of experience and impacts leaves valuable insights and learnings buried – and perhaps eventually lost, as they remain in individual and sometimes in organizational memories. An immense loss, for as the country rapidly urbanizes towards housing almost 30% of the global urban population in 2035, finding context-appropriate ways for delivering housing, basic services and infrastructure in climate resilient and sustainable ways is urgent and critical. In this context, the ARCS Conferences provides a learning opportunity for all, with sharing of experiences, discussion and reflection on urban development policy and interventions.

The ARCS Conferences continue to be a signal event in the domain for an annual sharing of academic, professional, and policy work across urban sectors and dimensions. To encourage research, case study, and documentation of urban initiatives, the Annual Urban Research Awards (AURA) have been instituted for best papers, research theses, and cases. From 2018 the Conference has become international, with the participation of researchers and key speakers from other developing countries. While multi-sectoral and multi-stakeholder knowledge sharing continues to be its hallmark format, every ARCS Conference focuses on a specific dimension of urban development.

The ARCS 8.0 draws attention to the question of urban sustainability and its implications for urban policy and practice in cities of the Global South, in the face of international policy and knowledge transfers which often shape initiatives in these cities. With increasing understanding of differences across cities in the global North and the South, how strategies and approaches in the former play out in cities of the South or are adapted to suit local contexts is important not only to make policy and practice more relevant but also to build appropriate capabilities for climate resilient, responsive, and inclusive urban development in developing countries.

Dr. Kajri Misra
Dean, School of Human Settlements
XIM University

XIM UNIVERSITY

XIM University, building on the long legacy of the high-quality development and management education of the Xavier Institute of Management Bhubaneswar (XIMB), was established under the Xavier University Odisha Act, 2013. The XIM Board of Governors comprises representatives of the Jesuit Society, the Government of India, the Government of Odisha, and eminent industrialists and educationists. Distinguished by its philosophy of ‘Inspiring Futures’- of students, organisations, and communities- by enabling them to explore beyond well-trodden paths and serve as active agents of change in society, XIM carries forward the hallmark education for the creation of social value provided by XIMB. The University has also carried forward and strengthened the three decades of knowledge support provided to government, business, and national and international organisations to design and implement business, social, and economic development initiatives. This is extended through consulting and advisory services for local, state, and national governments, businesses and civil society organisations, and high-quality management research towards the overall urban, rural, and industrial development of the state and the country.

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Xavier Institute of Management	School of Human Settlements
School of Human Resource Management	School of Economics
School of Rural Management	School of Computer Science & Engineering
School of Sustainability	Xavier Law School
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SCHOOL OF HUMAN SETTLEMENTS

The School of Human Settlements (SHS) houses all initiatives of XIM University for education, research, training and consulting in the fields of urban and regional development policy, planning, management and governance. SHS's mission is to create the expertise needed for sustainable, inclusive and just urban, rural, and regional development. Currently, the School of Human Settlements offers two 2-year full-time Postgraduate programmes- MBA in Urban Management and Governance (MBA UMG), and Masters in Urban and Regional Planning (MURP). Building on the long experience of management education at XIMB, the School's flagship MBA-Urban Management and Governance Programme extends the application of management expertise to human settlements at all scales with the understanding of spatiality, spatial transformations, and public systems in its programmes.

SHS also offers two Doctoral programmes, in Urban Management and Governance, and in Planning. In addition, it offers executive education and capacity building in public systems, in the areas of economic development, education, health, water and sanitation, affordable housing, mobility, habitat resilience, and other aspects crucial for sustainable development. Graduates work with Consultants, Government, SPVs, NGOs and Foundations, and industry.

PROGRAMMES OFFERED AT SHS

MBA in Urban Management and Governance (MBA UMG)
Ph.D. in Urban Management and Governance

Masters in Urban and Regional Planning (MURP)
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ANNUAL RESEARCH ON CITIES SUMMIT (ARCS)

Current understandings of the conditions of cities, towns, and peripheries and their functioning and development processes are minimal and partial, presenting a key challenge for effective intervention. The ARCS is an annual conference organised by the School of Human Settlements, XIM University, to share research and experience of researchers, academicians, and industry professionals in the planning and management of human settlements and urbanisation in India. It aims to stimulate creation and facilitate the exchange of knowledge to develop safe, sustainable, and just settlements.

ANNUAL URBAN RESEARCH AWARDS (AURA)

The Annual Urban Research Award (AURA) is presented at the ARCS annually for the best paper presentation. Submissions are invited at the time of the Conference announcement every year from academicians, researchers, students, professionals, and policymakers. ARCS 8.0 AURA awards for best paper presentation are selected based on- Overall delivery of the presentation, Research content, Communication skills, and Time management.

ARCS 8.0:

FUTURE OF SUSTAINABLE URBANISM IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH

The 8th Annual Research on Cities Summit (ARCS 8.0) focuses on experiences, initiatives, and insights into urban sustainability efforts in the cities of the Global South. SDG 11 - developing sustainable cities and communities – clearly flags the importance of greening cities in achieving global sustainability. Moreover, sustainability transitions are most urgent in cities of the global South, which are likely to take the brunt of the physical, economic, and social consequences of climate change. Over 60 percent of the areas projected to be urbanised by 2050 are in these parts of the world; 30 of the existing 40 megacities are in the South and more are set to emerge in the next decade. Urban areas in the Global South are thus pivotal in the efforts toward global sustainability; greening urbanism in the Global South will be crucial in addressing the broader sustainability challenge.

Policies, strategies, and technologies for sustainability transitions in the global South are frequently shaped by the experiences and expertise of the global North, mediated through vectors like consultants, development organisations, or knowledge networks. This one-way transfer overlooks the varied implications when these practices intersect with the distinctive realities of Southern urbanism. Global strategies for sustainability, such as compact cities, green spaces, renewable materials, green transportation, circular economies, or blue-green planning, may encounter unique challenges in Southern contexts, given the pressing issues like poverty eradication, affordable housing, access to basic amenities, and governance capacity.

On the other hand, local values, practices, and perspectives that shape the understanding and vision of sustainability in Southern contexts are frequently marginalised in global epistemic networks and policy discourses. These dynamics illuminate the need to focus on local ideas, perspectives, and initiatives in these contexts; to pay attention to the ways in which Southern cities respond to sustainability challenges. It also prompts inquiry into how global sustainability discourses are adapted or innovated locally and the kinds of outcomes which emerge. It is vital to acknowledge the unique challenges faced by these cities and the innovative solutions they develop in response, including a potential resurgence of traditional sustainable practices.

This School of Human Settlements (SHS), XIM University, therefore organised this international conference on ‘Future of Sustainable Urbanism in the Global South’ from 8-10 February 2024 seeking to elicit work which documents, explores, and critically examines sustainability efforts in Southern contexts. Papers, cases, reports and final year thesis on project and process experiences were invited from researchers, academicians, professionals, students, civic and policy actors on the questions of sustainable settlements in the global South for presentation. The conference also features the Annual Urban Research Awards (AURA) for the best paper.

Presentations from different perspectives and sectors were organised into five themes, and six tracks:

Themes	SDGs and Policies	Informality	Equity and Inclusion	Gender	Smart & Digital Applications
Tracks	Track- 1: Economy and Livelihood				
	Track- 2: Sustainable Infrastructure and Services				
	Track- 3: Environment and Ecosystem				
	Track- 4: Sustainable Settlement Planning and Development				
	Track- 5: Inclusive Urban Regeneration and Public Spaces				
	Track- 6: Governance, Capacity Building and Education				

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- Students of MBA in Urban Management and Governance (Batches 2022-24, and 2023-25)
- Students of Masters in Urban and Regional Planning (Batch 2022-24)

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TRACK-1: ECONOMY AND LIVELIHOOD

This track addresses the issues of economic development, growth, and creating equal, secure, and decent livelihood opportunities for all. It answers the questions of sustainable livelihood approaches and strategies. How does focusing on inclusive livelihood can lead to economic development? What are the various ways of achieving the same? What are the innovative techniques of income generation? What are the existing scenarios in the global south? The track is further divided into the following sub-themes:

- Economy of cities and its region
- Sustainable livelihood of the Global South: approaches, policies, case studies
- Economic growth and cities of the Global South

Female Migration And Fertility In Bhubaneswar City: Kaplan-Meier Survival Analysis

Sumita Bera¹, Dr. Sibabrata Das¹

¹Ravenshaw University, Cuttack

Urbanisation is strongly influenced by migration. While the role of rural to urban migration has been steadily rising, the contribution of natural increase in urban growth has decreased. In demographic study of urbanisation, the researchers have given more attention to the comparative fertility of migrant and non-migrant women in urban areas. But, in part, there is also a scope to study whether the migration process itself is associated with changes in fertility attitudes and behaviour and whether differentials between migrants and non-migrants reflect socialisation, selection, adaptation, or disruption with fertility associated with the process with movement. Bhubaneswar, the capital city of Odisha, is one of the planned cities and is home to a sizable migrant population from other regions. Significant social and economic changes have occurred in Bhubaneswar. Sakes investigates in Bhubaneswar, how family migration affects women's fertility patterns, which is unaddressed.

One of the most significant elements affecting Bhubaneswar's social and economic structure is the rapid increase in internal migration and urbanisation. Not only in the city of Bhubaneswar but also globally, there are very few studies on the reproductive behaviour of migrants. Also, majority of existing research focuses on the reproduction of immigrants in developed countries. Considering rural to urban migration, urban to urban migration, and urban natives, this study compares the fertility behaviour of migrants and non-migrants in Bhubaneswar. The study specifically looks at whether married women's reproductive behaviour changes when they migrate to Bhubaneswar with their families from different socio-spatial contexts.

The aim of the study is to examine fertility differentials between migrant and non-migrant women and to study the mechanism through which migration effects on fertility in Bhubaneswar. The study collected the data from a primary survey of 450 currently married women aged 15-49 years in 13 slum and non-slum areas of Bhubaneswar city. This study used Kaplan-Meier survival analysis technique.

Significant social and economic changes have occurred in Bhubaneswar. One of the most significant elements affecting Bhubaneswar's social and economic structure is the rapid increase in internal migration and urbanisation. The study cites four theories to explain fertility differences between different migrant groups and urban natives. The socialisation theory postulates that women/girls carry forward the social practices including fertility behaviour prevailing in their society from their childhood, and as a result, women who move to a new cultural environment cannot adopt new reproductive norms fully. Contrarily, the adaptation hypothesis places more emphasis on the significance of the present location than on the childhood residence. This theory is in favour of the idea that migrant couples modify their fertility in response to the expenses and possibilities they experience in their new surroundings. The main distinction between the socialisation and adaptation hypotheses is the time span over which both economic and social factors are assumed to operate. Contrary to the socialisation theory, which holds that adaptation to the fertility of the receiving community takes place over the course of a generation, the adaptation hypothesis claims that it takes place in less than 10 years (Eryurt and KOC, 2012). According to the selection hypothesis, migration has a tendency to be selective based on factors including age, education, occupation, and marital status. As per this hypothesis, migrants and natives in destination have almost similar attitudes and behaviour of reproduction. According to the disruption hypothesis, migration itself may affect fertility. So, fertility of the recent migrants is low (Sidney and Goldstein, 1987). This study intends to identify which of these four hypotheses is most appropriate to explain fertility differentials between migrants and non-migrants in the case of Bhubaneswar city by using a non-parametric explanatory survival analysis called 'Kaplan-Meier survival analysis'.

Fertility variation in migration status is conspicuous. The mean number of children ever born of women is the marginally lowest among non-migrants compared to the migrants in Bhubaneswar. This study demonstrates that even in-migrant women, the actual number of children of women are difference between non-slum areas and slum areas. The Kaplan Meier survival curves of second and subsequent births for urban native born, migrants in non-slum areas and women are almost similar. Rather than migrants in slum regions, the survival curves among women of migrants in non-slum areas resembled those of urban native born. Due to the presence of old migrants

in slum regions, the survival curves among migrant women diverge slightly from those of other groups of migration status. In this case, adaptation hypotheses come to mind. As is common knowledge, the socialisation hypothesis highlights the significance of the childhood environment, whereas the adaptation hypothesis highlights the significance of the new environment. Migrants' social and reproductive behaviours are shaped by the dominant values and conventions in their new surroundings. As a result, after some time, migrant women's fertility behaviour in the new environment begins to resemble that of natives. The findings imply that in Bhubaneswar, the adaptation hypothesis is more explicative than the socialisation hypothesis.

Keywords: Female migration, Actual number of children ever born, Kaplan-Meier survival estimates

Reshaping the Nature of Work: Digitalisation, Decent Work, and Online Food Delivery Workers in Delhi

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Work is an inevitable aspect of human existence. Historically, it has been limited to a specific geographic area, with a mutual connection between workers and employers. Nevertheless, as globalisation progresses and digitalisation becomes more prevalent, the nature and qualities of labour are rapidly evolving. In recent times, there has been a significant rise in both contractual and non-contractual employment arrangements, where the employer is not physically present and is referred to as a platform. These works are defined by payment being made in increments and are commonly referred to as the 'Gig Economy'. Due to its significant potential to reshape the labour market, it has been referred to as the "future of work." This is distributed over multiple sectors of the economy, encompassing a variety of employment activities for both males and females.

One activity that has thrived throughout the Covid-19 pandemic is online food delivery work. Currently, a significant number of educated young people and adults are involved in this activity both domestically and internationally. Moreover, this activity has the potential to alleviate the strain on the Indian economy, which is now grappling with the issue of "jobless growth." Given the current emphasis on sustainable development, Goal 8 of the Sustainable Development campaign aims to ensure that all individuals worldwide have access to decent work. This notion has also exacerbated the informal and contractual sector of the economy. In 2021, the International Labour Organisation (ILO) has expanded the scope of the "decent work" concept to include food delivery workers. Platform workers in India are also being acknowledged through the implementation of the Social Security Code of 2020 and the recently introduced Rajasthan Platform-Based Gig Workers (Registration and Welfare) Bill of 2023.

This research thoroughly examines various facets of online food delivery, including its socio-economic conditions, employment patterns, triangular relationships and associated risks, typologies, concepts, and policies pertaining to workers in different countries including the recently introduced 'Rajasthan Platform-Based Gig Workers (Registration and Welfare) Bill, 2023'. The research employed a mixed-method approach, drawing on both primary and secondary sources, including a survey of food delivery workers in Delhi. The study examines the working conditions of food delivery workers using the decent work paradigm. Furthermore, cross-tabulations have been performed and the 'Decent Work Index' has been computed in accordance with Standing (2002).

The study's findings indicate that there are ongoing disagreements regarding the classification of food delivery workers. Some researchers contend that these individuals should be classified as independent contractors, while others argue that they should be classified as employees. Equally important is the distinction between paid and unpaid labour. The food delivery work operates in a triangular relationship involving the restaurant, online platform, and delivery worker. This relationship is regulated by a contract that outlines the terms and conditions of the worker's involvement in the process. The contract grants the intermediary firm the authority to supervise, discipline, or terminate the worker, as well as restrict their use of the platform. The process of 'demutualisation' of risk, in which the primary risks of the firm are transferred to the worker, exacerbates the susceptibility and uncertainty experienced by food delivery workers.

Food delivery workers predominantly operate inside work-on-demand systems, which largely entail conventional, tangible, or ‘real world’ assignments and occupations rather than virtual duties. Many people now depend on these platforms for the majority of their wages; this is particularly relevant in India, where the economy is experiencing jobless growth leading to a dearth of inclusive growth, and these kinds of works have been warmly received because they have generated new jobs. Additionally, it has the potential to generate fresh prospects for individuals. Nevertheless, these platforms engender subpar working conditions by neglecting to offer benefits like employment security, and training or promotion opportunities. Employers provide ‘just-in-time’ supplies and ‘pay-as-you-go’ compensation to workers; in reality, they offer ‘human-as-a-service’.

The term ‘human-as-a-service’ accurately captures the concept of an intensified level of commodification of human beings. One would anticipate that they would operate with the same level of efficiency and effectiveness as a software or technology instrument. However, if any issues arise, they may receive more negative ratings or criticism compared to their counterparts in other sectors of the business. These factors together have turned them into ‘emotional labour,’ since it is likely to have an impact on how well one is rated for one’s work if one is kind and cheery with clients. The job is characterised by its uncertain nature and the absence of appropriate employment conditions. Controversies exist about food delivery workers, particularly around the extent of their flexibility and the impact of rating and ranking systems on their economic advancement. And whether the job of delivering meals constitutes a shift away from the traditional form of employment or an innovation in its own right.

The study also shed light on the Karl Marx’s idea of Precarisation of work and Neoclassicals arguments about labour market. It argues that the rise of the gig economy has proven Karl Marx’s prediction that technological progress would lead to a reduction in human labour and a subsequent rise in the unemployment rate. Establishing a “reserve army of the unemployed” would lead to a decline in wages and the wage share of income. At stake here are the presumptions of the so-called ‘Neoclassical theory of labour,’ which holds that employees are rational actors who make market-based decisions about where to put their time and effort based on factors like the opportunity cost of different possibilities and the relative merits of each activity. But in the instance of food delivery workers, this incentive system may entice people based on their risk appetites as well as their desire to induce more effort.

Delhi, being a metropolis, draws numerous migrants from northern India, primarily from Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. The city is a dynamic hub that embodies a fusion of diverse cultures and beliefs. Additionally, it boasts a substantial population of food delivery personnel. The study revealed that over 50% of food delivery workers were from Uttar Pradesh, with Bihar being the second most represented state. Additionally, about 40% of these workers were college graduates who worked full-time due to limited job prospects in India. The study’s findings indicate that the working conditions of food delivery workers are characterised by precariousness and a lack of decent work. The study also addresses policies issues and suggests policy measures.

Keywords: Food delivery work, Precarity, Decent Work, Digitalisation

Planning for Urban Heritage Tourism: A Tourism Development Plan for Chandernagore

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Urban cultural heritage is a powerful and often underutilised asset that has the potential to drive economic development and create job opportunities, particularly for the marginalised and informal sector workers in the cities of the Global South. The rich history, architecture, traditions, and artistic expressions embedded in urban spaces can be leveraged to foster sustainable economic growth while preserving the unique identity of these cities.

Case studies of prominent cultural heritage sites like Georgetown (Malaysia) and Pondicherry (India) suggests there are several ways in which this connection can be established: (i) Tourism and Hospitality: The preservation and promotion of urban cultural heritage can attract tourists, both domestic and international. This influx of visitors creates demand for various services, such as accommodation, transportation, restaurants, and guided tours, thereby generating employment for residents, especially those engaged in the informal sector. (ii) Cultural

Industries: Urban cultural heritage can serve as a source of inspiration for creative industries. Artisans, craftsmen, and artists can find opportunities to showcase their skills and products, contributing to the growth of cultural markets. This not only preserves traditional craftsmanship but also provides income-generating avenues for informal sector workers. (iii) Cultural Events and Festivals: Celebrating and promoting cultural heritage through events and festivals can attract a diverse audience. The organisation of such activities creates jobs in event management, hospitality, entertainment, and related sectors, offering opportunities for informal sector workers to participate in and benefit from these events.

However, cultural heritage-based economic development also poses several planning challenges. (i) Gentrification: The revitalisation of urban cultural heritage sites may lead to gentrification, where wealthier individuals and businesses move in, displacing the existing low-income communities. Striking a balance between development and social equity is crucial to ensure that economic benefits reach the informal sector workers rather than contributing to their marginalisation. (ii) Infrastructure and Services: Many cultural heritage sites in the Global South face challenges related to inadequate infrastructure and basic services. Ineffective urban planning can hinder accessibility, limiting the potential economic benefits for the local population. Investment in infrastructure development is essential to unlock the full economic potential of cultural heritage. (iii) Lack of Inclusive Policies: Urban planning initiatives often neglect the needs and interests of informal sector workers. Inclusive policies that actively involve and prioritise the informal sector are essential to ensure that economic development benefits all segments of the population, rather than exacerbating existing inequalities. (iv) Environmental Sustainability: Uncontrolled urban development can lead to environmental degradation, impacting the cultural and natural heritage of a city. Sustainable urban planning is crucial to strike a balance between economic development and the preservation of cultural and ecological assets.

Therefore, leveraging urban cultural heritage for economic development requires a holistic and inclusive approach to urban planning. By addressing the challenges and ensuring that the benefits are distributed equitably, cities in the Global South can harness their cultural richness to create a more prosperous and sustainable future for all residents, particularly those engaged in the informal sector.

This study focuses on Chandernagore a small town about 40 km north of Kolkata and part of the extended Kolkata Metropolitan Region. The town is a rich blend of Indo-French colonial architecture, religious festivals, and a prominent centre of the Indian nationalist movement. Urban Cultural Heritage tourism has the potential to boost sustainable development, foster economic growth, and provide social benefits. Major heritage aspects including the famous Jagaddhatri puja offer visitors an impressive glimpse and its cultural influences, enriching a unique destination for cultural exploration and historical discovery in Chandernagore.

The study addresses identification of potential tourist spots in the area through mapping, considering historical, architectural, and cultural value, and surveying existing attractions and infrastructure. Additionally, the research directs to understand indicators for the economic development of the urban poor (focusing on street vendors mainly), drawing insights from a comprehensive literature review encompassing concepts and HUL approach, as well as relevant case studies. The research involves a multifaceted approach, conducting interviews and surveys with stakeholders, municipal officials, and various institutional actors involved in heritage tourism. Structured questionnaire surveys are utilised to interact with different officials, gathering detailed insights. Random sampling surveys target stakeholders such as street vendors, drivers, retail businesses, and other miscellaneous contributors to assess their perspectives, the disparity in income levels among them. Through these interactions, the research looks after the impact of tourism on their lives and livelihoods. The study comprehensively examines the roles of different institutional actors in heritage tourism and evaluates the socio-economic conditions and development potential of the area. Additionally, site visits are conducted to Chandernagore to identify the intensity of the famous Jagaddhatri Puja and to discern the economic benefits. The research assesses the implementation of the Street Vendor Act in the study area, including the demarcation of vending zones and the incorporation of heritage zones in any development plan. It further investigates the status of existing plans, development proposals, and heritage-related regulations and policies. Also, an assessment of tourist flow in the region is conducted to provide a holistic understanding of the tourism dynamics.

It highlights the essence of a tourism development plan for Chandernagore that not only celebrates its rich heritage but also envisions a future where tourism has a potential for the improvement of livelihood opportunities of urban poor (focusing on street vendors) by including different planning interventions. By weaving together historical,

cultural, and economic dimensions, the tourism development plan endeavours to strike a delicate balance that nurtures both the city's legacy and the well-being of people. The journey towards realising this approach involves not just the preservation of heritage sites but the cultivation of a harmonious relationship between tourism, the local community, economic generation, and the overarching goals of inclusive, sustainable development in Chandernagore.

Keywords: Tourism Development Plan, Urban cultural heritage tourism, Livelihood opportunities

Revitalising Urban Finance: A Holistic Examination of Burdwan's Resource Dynamics

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As India experiences rapid urban growth, the imperative for substantial investments in infrastructure and services becomes evident. Ensuring the efficiency of these investments, however, extends beyond securing finances to guaranteeing their transformation into desired outputs and outcomes (Rao & Bird, 2010). This paper, centered on the city of Burdwan in West Bengal, India, endeavours to redefine urban finance discourse by transcending isolated vertical analyses and embracing a holistic perspective that recognises municipal areas as distinct entities.

The post-74th Constitutional Amendment Act landscape in 1992 marked a shift in India's local government fiscal structure, emphasising cities as pivotal growth engines and necessitating stronger revenue bases and mechanisms (Nallathiga, 2008). Despite the centrality of urban finance, literature predominantly confines its exploration to municipal finance, sidelining the complex interplay of resources from various sectors and programs within urban areas.

The realm of urban finance is a complex and multifaceted landscape, encompassing diverse monetary flows crucial for sustaining infrastructural services within municipal jurisdictions. The literature specifies numerous confusions with the term 'urban finance'. The term Urban Finance has been used interchangeably with 'urban public finance', 'local government finance', 'municipal finance', 'urban development finance', 'local finance', and 'local public finance'. But as far as this study and to my understanding, urban finance is conceptualised as all the money from different sources that gets spent and received in providing infrastructural services within a municipal jurisdiction/area, does not matter where it comes from or who spends it.

This study critically examines the sources of urban finance in India, challenging the prevailing perception of poor understanding compared to other urbanising nations. The issue is when we speak of urban finance, it is presumed same as that of municipal finance. The dichotomy between the conceptualisation of municipal finance and the actual diversity of urban finances poses a critical challenge, as the spatial unit of the municipal area is often overlooked in favour of sectoral or programmatic lenses. The literature specifies that in urban areas, municipal finance is probably the least and finances comes from all the other sources like inter-governmental transfers (IGT), official developmental assistances (ODA), etc. Utilising Slack's (2009) classification of urban finance into own-source revenues, inter-governmental transfers, and external assistance, this research identifies major avenues for external assistance within a municipal jurisdiction, including municipal bonds, public-private partnerships (PPP), and official development assistance (ODA). In fact, even the listing of all the urban financial sources from all programmes, grants, schemes, etc. are missing in the literature. Historically municipal finance began with Lord Rippon's Resolution of 18 May 1882 (UN Habitat, 2018), still it has been evolved and explored by various authors in the recent times. Encompassing municipal finance and all investments within an urban jurisdiction, urban finance, in this context, transcends conventional boundaries. (RBI, 2022).

A fundamental gap in the existing literature is the absence of a framework capable of assessing a city or municipal area as a cohesive unit. The prevalent practice of accounting by individual organisations in Burdwan (E.g.- Burdwan Municipality, Burdwan Development Authority), each with its own budget, obscures the true magnitude of urban finance. Though everyone is acting in the same space, still no one knows how much money is given by each of the organisation for development of the municipal area.

The study strategically focuses on the basic services in Burdwan, namely water supply, solid waste management, roads/public streets, and housing. Choosing to focus on the basic services is a strategic decision due to its fundamental importance, universal relevance, policy impact, utilisation of funds, public welfare focus, and state department and SPV involvement. By concentrating on these fundamental aspects, the research aims to address immediate gaps in understanding urban finance while laying the groundwork for future endeavours.

The study aims to explore- whether a comprehensive and consolidated picture of financial expenditures in Burdwan can be obtained by examining all entities spending money? The research is guided by the inquiry of whether it is possible to capture the totality of spending, even sector-wise, or region wise. This central question underscores the absence of an existing consolidated view of spending in Burdwan, prompting the need for a framework that can provide a holistic understanding of urban finance. The research outlines the devolution of powers to municipalities in India and specifically in West Bengal, detailing the functions, powers, and responsibilities conferred upon them. It further explores the departments in the government of West Bengal, providing insights into the budgetary priorities and demands for grants from various departments.

In conclusion, this paper contributes not only to academic discourse but serves as a catalyst for action among policymakers and practitioners. It advocates for a transparent and informed approach to urban development, emphasising the urgency of developing a comprehensive framework that captures the entirety of urban finances. This framework is crucial for fostering strategic planning, transparent fund allocation, and effective decision-making to ensure the sustainable development of cities. By systematically exploring Burdwan's financial landscape, this study lays the foundation for redefining urban finance on a broader and more inclusive scale.

Keywords: Urban finance, Governance structure in Burdwan, Sources of urban finances, Devolution to the municipalities, Basic services

Investigating the Economic Factors Shaping the Genesis of Informal Settlements in India: A Systematic Literature Review

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The rapid pace of urbanisation and internal migration defines the contemporary urban landscape, imposing significant pressure on housing infrastructure globally. As cities expand to accommodate a growing population pursuing economic opportunities, informal settlements become increasingly prevalent. This phenomenon is particularly pronounced in India, which is celebrated for its rich history and vibrant cultural tapestry. The resulting housing shortage, exacerbated by the influx of migrants seeking livelihoods, has propelled many individuals and households towards informal settlements like slums as an alternative dwelling solution.

Informal settlements pose a significant policy challenge for developing economies in the 21st century. In light of the varied physical, social, and economic factors contributing to the formation of these settlements, this study distinguishes itself by specifically delving into the intricate economic dimension. The decision to emphasise the economic dimension stems from a recognised gap in the existing literature. Previous studies have extensively explored the broader dynamics of informal settlements, acknowledging the influence of social factors such as community ties, cultural practices, and demographic shifts. Additionally, studies have delved into the physical factors, encompassing spatial patterns, infrastructure deficiencies, and environmental considerations. However, a thorough investigation into the economic factors that propel individuals towards informal settlements has noticeably been absent in the existing literature. This gap in the literature hinders the development of comprehensive strategies and policies to mitigate the challenges of informal settlements, particularly in India. Thus, the lack of an examination of economic factors in the context of informal settlements poses a significant constraint on developing housing policies and formulating sustainable solutions to address the socio-economic challenges associated with informal settlements. Therefore, bridging this gap in research is essential to enable policymakers to implement more effective strategies and initiatives that can meaningfully address the complexities of informal settlements and contribute to sustainable urban development.

A systematic literature review was conducted to bridge this gap, critically analysing academic sources encompassing peer-reviewed articles, books, and reports. Adopting a systematic approach facilitated a comprehensive examination of the existing body of literature, extracting relevant insights into the economic factors that contribute to the formation of informal settlements in India. The PRISMA Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) technique was employed to ensure a rigorous selection process of relevant research papers. The search strategy, implemented in two phases, involved the use of key terms such as 'informal housing', 'economic', and 'factor' in conjunction with context-specific terms such as 'India,' 'Sustainable Development', 'Sustainable Livelihoods', and 'slum'. The search was conducted on two widely used databases, Scopus and Science Direct. This systematic approach resulted in a comprehensive pool of 76 studies from various academic channels. In addition to peer-reviewed articles, this study systematically integrated the most frequently cited references through a backward snowballing approach.

Furthermore, research articles that were frequently referenced but did not surface in the initial search were also incorporated into the review. Thus, following a stringent inclusion criteria process, 54 research papers were deemed suitable for this comprehensive review, covering 2000 to 2021. The selected studies provided valuable insights into the economic factors influencing the formation of informal settlements in India. Each economic factor identified in the literature was assigned a normalisation score based on its frequency of appearance across the selected studies, enabling the identification of the most relevant determinants.

The research findings have highlighted a notable emphasis on the themes, patterns, and divergences within the informal settlements' literature. It intricately explores the multifaceted web of factors influencing the origin and perpetuation of these settlements, unveiling the pivotal roles of poverty, unemployment, and limited access to credit. At the core of this examination lie the pivotal roles played by poverty, unemployment, and limited access to credit, which collectively shape the economic foundations of informal settlements. As a persistent force, poverty propels individuals towards informal settlements, compounding housing challenges due to a dearth of economic resources. Simultaneously, unemployment exacerbates this predicament, prompting individuals to seek refuge in informal settlements owing to constrained financial means. The formidable barrier of inadequate access to credit further constrains residents' capacity to invest in formal housing solutions. This analysis goes beyond individual factors, providing a comprehensive perspective on the interconnected influences shaping informal settlements. It considers rapid urbanisation, dynamics within the land market, and governmental policies, all contributing collectively to the intricate economic landscape of informal settlements.

The consequential effect of rapid urbanisation, spurred by economic opportunities, places immense strain on housing infrastructure, consequently fostering the spontaneous emergence of informal settlements. The dynamics of land markets and governmental policies play pivotal roles in shaping the economic fabric of informal settlements. The intricate relationship between land markets and these settlements unveils a complex interplay where irregularities in the formal land market often prompt the emergence of informal settlements. Governmental policies, spanning from housing regulations to urban planning, exert substantial influence in shaping the economic landscape of these settlements. A nuanced understanding of these dynamics is imperative for crafting effective policies that directly address the economic foundations of informal settlements.

Thus, the outcomes of this systematic literature review establish a crucial groundwork for informed policymaking by shedding light on the economic factors that have been relatively understudied in the existing literature. The normalisation scores provide a quantitative measure of the importance of each economic factor, offering policymakers a valuable tool to prioritise interventions and formulate targeted strategies. These insights from the study contribute substantially to the ongoing discourse surrounding informal settlements, providing a better understanding of the economic challenges entwined with urbanisation and internal migration in India. Consequently, the study emphasises the imperative for a holistic approach integrating urban informal settlement research into the broader sustainable development agenda.

While this review contributes substantially to our comprehension of the economic drivers shaping informal settlements, it also has a few limitations. Though providing valuable insights, the focus on India may not fully capture the diversity of economic factors influencing informal settlements across different regions in the Global South. A people-centric design approach is recommended for future research, fostering a bottom-up perspective through methodologies like fuzzy Delphi to address this. This participatory method ensures the inclusion of diverse voices and experiences, shaping a more comprehensive understanding of economic factors in informal

settlements. This approach can provide valuable insights into the perspectives of individuals and communities directly impacted by these economic determinants, contributing to formulating inclusive and effective policies for sustainable urban development.

Keywords: Economic, Housing, Informal, Settlement, India

A Theoretical Review on Sustainable Livelihood Framework

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A livelihood is in the simplest terms, a way of gaining a living. A livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets and activities required for a means of living. The ability to cope with stress and shocks while continuing and improving is retained by a socially sustainable livelihood. The household's livelihood depends on five significant capitals: natural, human, financial, physical, and social. The natural capital is about the natural resources and stock available; human capital includes skill, knowledge, ability to labour and health, whereas financial capital is about the capital base of the household like savings, credit or debt and other economic assets; physical capital includes basic infrastructure and producer goods like housing, and social capital talk about networks and connectedness, membership of more formalised groups, relationships of trust, reciprocity, and exchanges. Social capital is intangible but vital in increasing, combining, and developing other capitals through their network and influence. Livelihoods are dynamic, and people adapt and change their livelihoods with internal and external stressors. People's livelihood is primarily determined by the changing environment (social, ecological, economic, and political) in which people exist. Seldom do households deal with just one stressor or shock at a time. Multiple stressors co-occur and, in sequence, uniquely mould livelihood due to inequalities and differential vulnerabilities between and within the households. Stressors include climatic challenges, socioeconomic and environmental factors, inequalities, and differential vulnerabilities that may become an opportunity or constraint for household livelihood opportunities and decision-making. Affluent households have various options to capitalise on their assets, whereas the poor are left with fewer options to cope with vulnerabilities and are forced to erode their capital. Livelihoods are universal. Poor and rich people both pursue livelihoods to make a living. Adverse outcomes may arise from a limited capacity for adaptation and specific coping mechanisms. These maladaptive behaviours jeopardise the sustainability of a livelihood over the long run, causing poverty traps and worsening inequality. The livelihood approach is grounded and multidimensional, providing a research framework to analyse the daily realities of the poor. With the neoliberal turn in the late 1980s, the livelihood approach became associated with a more individualistic development agenda, stressing various forms of capital. It acknowledges the limits and flexibility with which individuals build their lives and dynamically modify their means of living. This lens reveals factors that push people onto unwanted trajectories towards greater well-being by considering shocks, seasonality, trends, and the larger institutional, cultural, and policy context. The initial focus of livelihood research was on rural communities. The livelihood of the urban poor is primarily under the key aspects of social context, economic context, governance, environmental and health, and rural-urban linkages. Urban neighbourhoods are fluid in their structure because of the diversity of household types. Sometimes, this diversity is likely to create tension and require different approaches for coping strategies useful for survival, unlike their rural counterpart. Cities are represented as economic engines. The poor depend on cash income for their daily needs. In cities, people rely on a governance structure to deliver infrastructure and services through meso and macro levels. This linkage between poor and city governance is not unproblematic. Knowing the difference between rural and urban areas, C. Moser systematically analyses the strategies and expands livelihood research to the urban context through her asset/vulnerability framework. Later, the Department of International Development (DFID) expanded the use of the Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF) in urban contexts. The framework for sustainable livelihoods outlines the primary determinants of people's livelihoods and their usual interactions. This people-centric framework focuses on the numerous relationships between the determinants affecting their livelihood and the strategies that may lead to a critical threshold beyond which specific livelihoods are no longer sustainable. However, it does not attempt to present a realistic model. The SLF has been criticised for its analytical limitations, such as

measuring capital, especially social capital, and needing to sufficiently explain more comprehensive structural processes (e.g. policies) and ecological impacts of livelihood decisions. The SLF ignores the shifting dynamics and interplay among various forms of capital, the power dynamics, and the position of households in class, race and other dimensions of equality. The study aims to look at the development and use of the SLF, emphasising how the field of sustainable development gradually adopted it. The paper reviews the extant literature contributing to a sustainable livelihood knowledge base. The study examines the development of existing theories over time, how theories relate to one another, and how much research has been conducted on existing theories. The findings are helpful to fill the knowledge gap in the theories and will build the path for future research. Ultimately, a successful livelihood transfers capital into income, well-being, lessening vulnerability, food security, dignity, and sustainable use of natural resources to improve living conditions and well-being as a prerequisite for poverty alleviation. Enhanced technology and infrastructure and diversity of resources, pursuits, and social support systems can improve lifestyles by minimising risk and expanding opportunity.

Keywords: Livelihood, Sustainable livelihood, Urban area, Sustainable Livelihood Framework

Exploring the Factors Impacting Affordable Housing Accessibility in India

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According to Census 2011, urban areas accounted for 31% of the total population, or approximately 377 million people. Within these city areas, there were 7,933 locations. One million or more people lived in 53 of them, and three of them were quite large: Delhi, Mumbai, and Kolkata (Indian Census 2011). India is now the world's second most populous country, owing to its rapid population growth. Currently, cities house more than 31.3% of the global population, and by 2030, that figure is expected to rise to more than 39.8% (Viswanathan, 2014). As per India Census 2011, substantial growth in India's population, expected to reach between 1600 and 1800 million by 2050. Government forecasts reveal an inadequate supply of over 18.78 million houses in urban areas in 2012, primarily falling under the LIG and EWS categories. The Metropolitan Affairs Ministry projects a housing shortage of 19 million by 2022, reaching 38 million by 2030 due to population growth and urbanisation. This scarcity has led people to reside in slums and informal settlements. Traditionally, the government managed affordable housing, but the private sector is increasingly involved due to the government's inability to meet housing infrastructure demands. The Indian government has introduced various policies, with the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY) being prominent. The research aims to assess the effectiveness of government policies, especially PMAY, in promoting affordable housing. It seeks to analyse the impact of these policies on housing affordability and accessibility across Indian cities.

The research objectives include examining factors influencing the demand and supply of affordable housing across Indian cities and investigating the effectiveness of government policies in this regard. Ultimately, the research strives to enhance the feasibility of affordable housing practices in Indian construction projects, addressing the nation's demand for cost-effective housing solutions.

A report on the state of the affordable housing sector provides insights into the housing gap prevalent among LIG and EWS households. In 2019, rural India faced a gap of over 5.95 million homes, while urban areas experienced a shortfall of 1.05 million homes. Looking ahead to 2030, the new households to be added further exacerbate the housing shortage, particularly in urban India, where over 2.58 million homes are needed for EWS and LIG. (Anon. et al, 2012). Another study emphasises the severe housing shortage in India's cities, specifically for the LIG and EWS categories. The top eight cities require approximately 0.6 million homes annually, but only about 0.2 million units are constructed each year. Despite a strong demand of around 340,000 for EWS and LIG dwellings, only 44,000 homes are available in this category (Sarkar et al., 2019).

Understanding housing preferences is crucial for home buyers, especially those entering the market for the first time. The housing demand function, represented as $Q = Q(P, Y, Z)$, links housing quantity demanded (Q) with

household income (Y), unit price of housing (P), and demographic features (Z). Various factors, including income, credit limits, wealth, location, and household characteristics, influence home preferences. Housing affordability, as highlighted by (Kleshcheva, 2021), is directly impacted by factors such as population size, incomes, housing costs, loan interest rates, and economic development.

The research methodology employed in the investigation of affordable housing intricacies adopts a thorough mixed-method approach, seamlessly integrating both qualitative and quantitative research methods. In the pursuit of a comprehensive understanding of the subject, primary data is collected through surveys and expert interviews. Standardised questionnaires target households, developers, and government officials, extracting quantitative insights, while in-depth interviews with key stakeholders yield qualitative perspectives. The richness of primary data is complemented by secondary data derived from diverse sources such as housing market reports, government documents, research papers, journals, and databases. Descriptive statistics can be used to summarise demographic and housing related. Regression analysis can be used to find key factor influencing housing demand and supply. Correlation coefficients can be used to explore relationships between variables. make them assertive sentence The sampling strategy involves a meticulous selection process: stratified random sampling for households, encompassing various income classes and geographic regions; a diverse representation of developers, ranging from larger companies to smaller entities; and a minimum number of government officials responsible for housing policies at different administrative levels. The subsequent data analysis employs both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Descriptive statistics summarise demographic and housing-related data, regression analysis identifies key factors influencing housing demand and supply, and correlation coefficients explore relationships between variables. On the qualitative front, theme analysis is employed to derive nuanced insights from interview transcripts, unraveling patterns and recurring themes within the qualitative data. The variables under investigation span both demand and supply factors. For demand, considerations include household income levels, demographic characteristics, housing preferences, and access to government support. On the supply side, factors encompass land acquisition, construction costs, regulatory frameworks, developer perspectives, and public-private partnerships. This research methodology aspires to contribute nuanced insights that can inform policies and practices in the realm of affordable housing. By adopting a multifaceted approach and exploring a diverse array of variables, the study aims to provide a holistic understanding of the complex dynamics surrounding affordable housing, potentially influencing positive changes in this critical domain.

Keywords: Demand, Supply, Affordable Housing, PMAY, Regression

TRACK-2: SUSTAINABLE INFRASTRUCTURE AND SERVICES

This track investigates the global south's sustainable urban infrastructure (social and physical), like housing, transportation, delivery of basic services, and its management. It focuses on WASH's approaches, policies, and practices in the southern cities and its region. It emphasises the questions of sustainable ways of transportation in terms of their social and environmental impact. How do accessibility, quality, and equity in WASH make cities clean, green, and healthy? How does a circular economy promote resource-efficient living? How is affordable housing contributing to the well-being of people?

- WASH in the global south
- Sustainable Transportation: towards green mobility
- Affordable housing and real estate in the southern cities: policies, impact, and practices
- Circular economy in promoting resource-efficient cities.
- Case studies

Comparative Environmental Impact Analysis of Electric, Hybrid, and Conventional Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles

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This research paper presents a comprehensive wringer of the environmental impact of electric cars, hybrid cars, and conventional internal combustion engine (ICE) cars, with a focus on challenging the conventional weighing that electric cars are inherently increasingly environmentally friendly. Drawing inspiration from a recent study conducted by Prof. Avinash Agarwal of IIT Kanpur, this research seeks to provide a unique perspective on the topic by considering various factors and providing fresh insights into the sustainability of these automotive technologies. The study employs a holistic life cycle assessment (LCA) approach, examining not only tailpipe emissions but moreover manufacturing, electricity generation, and end-of-life disposal impacts. The findings of the research indicate that environmental advantages of electric cars are context-dependent and may not unchangingly outweigh those of hybrid and conventional ICE cars.

The global automotive industry stands at a crossroads, facing the pressing need to reduce its environmental footprint while maintaining the convenience and mobility it provides. In this context, electric vehicles (EVs) have emerged as a promising solution, touted for their potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate air pollution. This growing interest in EVs stems from concerns well-nigh climate change, dwindling fossil fuel reserves, and the imperative to transition to cleaner transportation options.

However, the narrative that electric cars are unequivocally increasingly environmentally friendly than their counterparts, namely hybrid vehicles (HEVs) and conventional internal combustion engine (ICE) cars, has wilt a prevailing belief. This weighing has garnered substantial attention, with governments, industries, and consumers worldwide investing in and raising EVs as an untried alternative. It is crucial to evaluate and critically examine this widely wanted notion to unearth the true environmental impact of these automotive technologies.

The motivation for conducting this research is rooted in the need to offer a comprehensive and nuanced perspective on the sustainability of EVs compared to HEVs and ICE cars. While drawing inspiration from a recent study conducted by Prof. Avinash Agarwal of IIT Kanpur, this research aims to expand upon and rencontre existing perceptions through a holistic life cycle assessment (LCA) approach. By considering the unshortened life trundling of these vehicles, from manufacturing to operation to end-of-life disposal, this research aims to provide valuable insights that contribute to a increasingly informed and evidence-based discussion on the topic.

This research paper seeks to achieve the following objectives:

1. Conduct a thorough environmental impact analysis of electric cars, hybrid cars, and conventional internal combustion engine cars.
2. Challenge the conventional belief that electric cars are inherently more environmentally friendly by considering multiple dimensions of their environmental impact.
3. Employ a comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) framework to evaluate not only tailpipe emissions but also the impacts of manufacturing and end-of-life disposal.
4. Investigate the context-dependent nature of the environmental advantages of electric cars and explore scenarios where hybrid and conventional ICE cars might offer comparable or even superior sustainability outcomes.
5. Provide recommendations and policy implications for promoting sustainable transportation choices in light of the study's findings.

This research is designed to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the environmental implications associated with different automotive technologies, ultimately aiding policymakers, manufacturers, and consumers in making informed decisions that align with the goal of reducing the automotive industry's environmental footprint.

Prof. Avinash Agarwal's groundbreaking study conducted at the Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur (IIT Kanpur) serves as a pivotal point of reference in this exploration of the environmental impact of electric, hybrid, and

conventional vehicles. In his research, Prof. Agarwal and his team conducted an in-depth wringer of the emissions and environmental consequences associated with electric and hybrid vehicles operating in an Indian context. Their study incorporated a rigorous towage of tailpipe emissions, taking into worth factors such as grid electricity sources, vehicle efficiency, and driving conditions specific to India. Prof. Agarwal's work highlighted several key findings, including the potential for significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions from electric vehicles when compared to conventional internal combustion engine vehicles. However, it moreover underscored the importance of considering regional variations, electricity generation sources, and the efficiency of electric vehicle components in assessing their environmental benefits accurately.

The literature surrounding the environmental impact of electric vehicles, hybrid vehicles, and conventional internal combustion engine vehicles is wide-stretching and multifaceted. Generally, there exists a wontedly held perception that electric vehicles are inherently increasingly environmentally friendly than their counterparts due to their sparsity of tailpipe emissions and the potential for cleaner energy sources. This perception has fuelled a global shift toward electric mobility, with governments and industries offering incentives to promote electric vehicle adoption. However, it is essential to recognise that this narrative may oversimplify the ramified environmental implications associated with variegated vehicle technologies. While electric vehicles indeed excel in reducing tailpipe emissions, their environmental performance hinges on various factors such as the source of electricity generation, shower production, and end-of-life disposal. Hybrid vehicles, on the other hand, tousle conventional and electric propulsion systems, potentially offering a increasingly well-turned tideway to emissions reduction. In light of these existing perceptions, this research aims to delve deeper into the environmental impact of these vehicle types, challenging conventional beliefs and providing a nuanced understanding of their sustainability wideness variegated contexts and scenarios. By doing so, this periodical seeks to contribute valuable insights to the ongoing spiel surrounding sustainable transportation choices and their potential global implications.

Keywords: Electric vehicles, Hybrid vehicles, Conventional Internal Combustion Engine Vehicles, Environmental Impact

Critical Analysis of Impediments to the Adoption of Sustainable Procurement Strategies in the Indian Built Environment Sector

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The construction industry is critical to economic progress, but it faces the difficult problem of balancing growth with environmental sustainability. The environmental impact is magnified in nations such as India, where rapid urbanisation is driving enormous expansion in the building sector. While construction is a big part of the economy, it also harms the environment (Mojumder et al., 2022), so strict rules are necessary to address this issue while still promoting economic and social progress (Gocontractor, 2021). According to a recent study from the construction blog Bimhow, traditional construction practices are responsible for causing 23% of air pollution, 40% of water pollution, and contributing to 50% of both climate change and landfill waste (Gocontractor, 2021). In different research, the United States Green Building Council (USGBC) has found that construction work uses 40% of the world's energy, and pollution from commercial buildings is projected to rise by 1.8% by 2030 (U.S. Green Building Council and Green Building Certification Inc, 2020; USGBC, 2020). In countries like India that are still growing and developing, construction work is using up a lot of their limited natural resources because there are so many people, cities are growing quickly, and industries are expanding (Mojumder and Singh, 2021). The procurement process for infrastructures project is being conducted in central, state and municipal level in India.

The purpose of this research is to look into the constraints that are impeding the adoption of green procurement methods in India's construction industry, with a particular emphasis on issues related to administrative support, management commitment, cost perceptions, and overall awareness. To gain thorough insights, the study adopts a mixed-methods approach, including questionnaire surveys and statistical analysis. A good trend has been observed within Indian government agencies, which are increasingly prioritising environmental and energy efficiency concerns in purchase decisions. National Building Construction Corporation (India) Limited is committed

to achieving its aims of legitimate and fair business operations through the incorporation of numerous ESG concerns into supply chain decision making, such as respect for human rights, business ethics, and environmental friendliness of products and services (NBCC's Sustainable Procurement Policy, 2023). As a concept in the area of supply chain management, the "green supply chain" tries to improve environmental sustainability by using eco-friendly methods. These include buying things in a way that doesn't harm the environment, using eco-friendly shipping and delivery methods, making things in a way that doesn't harm the environment, and managing products responsibly at the end of their useful lives (Mojumder et al., 2021).

Despite this, the survey uncovers significant barriers to green procurement adoption, such as a lack of administrative assistance and commitment from upper management, as well as a widespread assumption that sustainable techniques are intrinsically more expensive. The study goes into existing literature on green supply chain management and sustainable procurement in the construction industry to build a theoretical foundation. Supply chain management comprises the efficient supervision of a network of connections to ensure the optimal delivery of goods or services to the client. It enables organisations to collect data on how well each component of the supply chain performs in terms of social and environmental responsibility in the context of sustainability (Gosh et al., 2020). There is a higher emphasis on reducing carbon emissions in today's society. Each building material has its own carbon impact. Knowing carbon footprints and non-traditional green procurement tactics, according to the study, is crucial for both clients and governments. This background allows for a more refined understanding of the problems and possible benefits of adopting environmentally responsible procurement procedures. In order to provide a theoretical foundation for our research, we combined many organisational theories pertinent to green supply chain management. The Resource-Based View (RBV), Complexity Theory, Ecological Modernisation Theory (EMT), Institutional Theory, and Resource Dependency Theory (RDT) are among these theories. Institutional theory investigates the impact of external factors such as external motivators, facilitators, and barriers on organisational decisions and behaviours (Hirsch, 1975). According to complexity theory, as complexity increases, it becomes more difficult for firms to plan and foresee organisational behaviours such as the adoption of green supply chain management.

The study combines both quantitative and qualitative research approaches to address the multidimensional nature of the identified impediments. For hypothesis testing, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) is used, which provides statistical validation for the discovered barriers. A fuzzy best-worst method (FBWM) is also used to rank obstacles, providing a more sophisticated understanding of their relative importance. Recognising the importance of stakeholder viewpoints, the research consults with project managers and procurement professionals to gain insights from their experiences. This qualitative dimension adds to the study's richness by providing real-world perspectives that supplement the statistical findings. The report identifies and categorises main barriers to green procurement adoption, focusing on cost implications, a lack of knowledge, a lack of awareness, and the absence of defined regulatory frameworks and standards as primary challenges. The research attempts to unravel the interconnections between these constraints and provide a more nuanced understanding of their impact on sustainable procurement practices in the Indian construction industry by using a mixed-methods methodology. Lack of green product knowledge, inability to integrate green procurement policy into existing policy, lack of knowledge of the importance of green business strategy, poor knowledge of environmental management system certification and standards, lack of financial incentives for green procurement, green construction materials provide more operational incompatibility risks than other materials are some factors in the context of knowledge about sustainability practice. Furthermore, the research aims to propose practical answers for overcoming these obstacles. The study intends to guide construction companies, public entities, and other stakeholders toward the successful implementation of green procurement strategies by giving a prioritised list of issues and potential solutions. The findings of this study are expected to make a substantial contribution to the advancement of sustainable construction practices in India, providing vital direction for decision-makers negotiating the complexity of reconciling economic expansion with environmental responsibility. This study provides a thorough examination of the barriers to green procurement adoption in India's construction industry. The research gives a comprehensive insight of the difficulties faced by stakeholders by integrating quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The proposed solutions provide actionable information, paving the way for more sustainable and ecologically responsible procurement methods in India's dynamic construction sector.

Keywords: Sustainable Procurement, Green Supply Chain, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Fuzzy best-worst method (FBWM)

Hydraulic Heritage Case Study: A Comprehensive and Technical Study for Integrating Traditional Water Mills for Sustainable Development in the Hilly Regions of India

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In order to solve the problems that our world is currently and in the future experiencing, the idea of sustainability is essential. In order to be sustainable, current requirements must be met without sacrificing the capacity of future generations to meet their own needs. The necessity of sustainability is evident for many reasons. The realisation that our existing lifestyle and resource consumption are unsustainable over the long run gives birth to the necessity for sustainability. Achieving a harmonic balance among economic progress, social fairness, and environmental preservation requires embracing sustainable methods. In India, sustainability is essential to balancing social justice, economic development, and environmental health. India is confronted with increased resource demands and climatic vulnerability due to its growing population, diverse ecosystems, and urbanisation challenges. Adopting sustainability guarantees resilient cities, equitable development, and resource conservation. It tackles pollution, water scarcity, and the uptake of renewable energy. For present and future generations, sustainability becomes morally necessary in a nation where poverty and environmental deterioration coexist. India can pave the way for a sustainable future that promotes equilibrium and prosperity for both its people and the planet by implementing creative policies, including the community, and working with other countries.

Including strategies for sustainability based on renewable materials requires implementing actions that reduce environmental impact, increase resource efficiency, and promote long-term ecological balance. Making thoughtful decisions at every stage of the material life cycle, from sourcing and production to consumption and disposal, is part of this holistic approach. Organisations and community can mitigate the depletion of natural resources and contribute to the preservation of ecosystems by adopting circular design principles, minimising waste, and giving priority to materials derived from responsibly managed sources. Moreover, the employment of renewable energy sources in manufacturing processes, in conjunction with a steadfast commitment to transparency and adherence to accredited certifications, guarantees a thorough, moral, and environmentally responsible path towards sustainability.

The research study is based on reducing environmental impact, promoting resource efficiency, and supporting long-term ecological balance through adaptation and by implementing “water mill” strategy on renewable resources for sustainable development for services. A water mill, sometimes referred to as a water wheel or hydropower system, is a device that uses the force of falling or flowing water to power machinery. The fundamental idea is to transform the kinetic energy of flowing water into rotational mechanical energy, which can subsequently be utilised for various tasks like sawing wood and grinding grain. For centuries, water mills have been an indispensable tool in many cultures for processing grains into flour. Even though they were commonly used in the past, more contemporary technologies have largely replaced traditional water mills. Water mills, however, may still be in use for particular purposes or as historical and cultural landmarks in some areas, especially those with abundant water flow. Furthermore, hydropower is still a crucial renewable energy source. To produce electricity from flowing water, modern hydroelectric power plants employ sophisticated turbines and generators.

The focus of this research document is to promote this renewable technique for the hilly areas of India. Water mills are often found in hilly and mountainous regions of India, where the terrain allows for the natural flow of water. States like Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Jammu and Kashmir, and parts of Northeast India have a notable presence of water mills. Traditional water mills in India have historically been used for grinding grains, especially wheat and maize, to produce flour. The mechanical energy generated by the water wheel is transmitted to millstones for the milling process. In many cases, water mills are community-owned and operated. They serve as crucial communal resources, where multiple households can bring their grains for milling, promoting a shared and sustainable approach to resource use. Water mills exemplify a form of decentralised, renewable energy. They harness the power of flowing water without relying on external energy sources, making them environmentally friendly and well-suited for off-grid areas. In the context of sustainable development, there is renewed interest

in revitalising and upgrading traditional water mills to enhance efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and support local economies.

This research employs a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively investigate water mill techniques. Initially, a literature review will survey existing scholarly works on traditional water mills, focusing on historical significance, cultural contexts, and technological aspects. Field surveys will be conducted in relevant regions of India, incorporating qualitative interviews with local communities, mill operators, and experts. Quantitative data will be gathered through direct measurements of water mill efficiency, energy output, and environmental impact. The triangulation of qualitative and quantitative data aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the cultural, social, and environmental dimensions of water mill practices, contributing to a holistic research perspective.

The research work is concluded by promoting water mill techniques in India celebrates local heritage, fostering a sense of cultural pride and community ownership. These sustainable practices align with Southern Asian values, emphasising self-reliance, ecological harmony, and respect for indigenous knowledge. By showcasing the success of water mills, India shapes regional perspectives on sustainability, inspiring a vision rooted in adaptive, community-driven solutions. This approach not only preserves cultural identity but also influences policy discussions, contributing to a holistic understanding of sustainable development in the diverse and interconnected contexts of Southern Asia.

Keywords: Water Mill technique, Indigenous knowledge, Heritage conservation, Renewable energy, Sustainable services

Urban Water Pricing Policy in India – A Framework

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Every urban local body in India has been supplying potable water to urban households, charging for the water supply, and handling sewerage. However, there seem to be some major disparities among the states based on their policies. This paper explores the current policies among sampled states and identifies disparities. It proposes a possible framework to derive the pricing model to ensure consistency across the country. The paper explores the extent of such disparities. It identifies the reasons for the same. From this exploration, relevant parameters and variables are identified. Using these parameters, the paper proposes a framework that could help streamline the entire costing, pricing, and billing process. A multiple case study methodology has been adopted to help study each sampled state. The findings are analysed to identify disparities, parameters, and a common framework. The paper offers insights into an unexplored policy area with widespread relevance and consequences. One of the significant contributions is to shift the focus from the provision of water to a sustainable economic model so that the same could be understood using concepts beyond social and political considerations.

Being the basic needs of every citizen, drinking water and sanitation are of primary importance for leading a safe and sustainable life, and are critical to achieving SDG #3 Good Health & Well-being. While collection, cleaning, and supply are critical success factors, there are many other factors to be considered in the management of potable water sources to arrive at an appropriate mechanism to decide the charges to be levied on the consumers. A cursory review of the current billing policies and tariffs from a few sampled states of Odisha, Telangana, Kerala, Gujarat, and NCR showed significant differences in charges being levied on domestic consumers. The way citizens are being charged for sanitation services has similar disparities. These findings bring out the following research questions.

RQ1. What are the factors considered for arriving at urban water tariffs in the sampled states?

RQ2. What are the possible relevant factors not being considered for deriving the costs and pricing?

RQ3. What parameters should be considered for building a framework to ensure sustainable water supply?

The methodology used for this research is a multiple-case study approach. Each sampled state's policies were first studied independently. The common factors were identified and collated to arrive at the gaps. Finally, all relevant factors were collated to create a comprehensive framework. The research hypotheses explored are given below.

Hypo1. The disparities in pricing are not based on costs but based on political policies.

Hypo2. There are differences in parameters being considered for arriving at costing and pricing.

Hypo3. A comprehensive framework containing all the relevant parameters does not exist.

The objective of the research is to come up with a better understanding and possible common approach for levying urban domestic water charges. The research uses an innovative methodology of doing multiple case studies together to achieve the common research objective. While a few attempts have been made to develop such frameworks for water pricing, there have not been any significant attempts to arrive at such an approach in India.

Results

It is evident from the results that the current water tariffs across the sampled states are not comparable and are driven by political policies rather than a focus on cost recovery. The elements considered for cost calculation were also found to be varying. Most of the models did not consider the costs of environmental damage and environmental protection. The lack of transparency and non-availability of data also indicated a lack of a systematic approach to the whole process. Metering, or rather a lack of it, came out as one of the major issues causing effective cost recovery, making nearly 30% of water being used as unaccounted-for water. There is no clear policy for using groundwater except in a few states, making it a concern as it is being exploited for commercial purposes. All the three hypotheses were accepted.

Framework for arriving at costs

All water should be treated as public property and all usage is to be monitored, metered, and billed, including groundwater. The items suggested to be considered for arriving at costs are Sourcing costs that include capital expenditure of the dams, pipelines, pumping stations, and cleaning stations are treated as public investments, and a nominal rate of interest is to be considered towards ROI. The operations and maintenance costs should be calculated at the actuals. Costs of de-risking water resources, including cleanup, remediation, and restoration of water bodies, Groundwater monitoring, and conservation Program, including Rainwater harvesting costs, Environmental damage costs including costs of relocation and rehabilitation of people from submerged areas and the cost of the habitat lost for other species, Environmental protection costs, including forest conservation, river rejuvenation, and catchment area management, Access and provision costs that would include water treatment, cleaning, chemicals used, the last mile piping and metering from the main supply lines, operational costs, and power and pumping costs to the overhead tanks, Contracting and billing costs for meter reading, billing, and collection, including website/ portal costs, online payment costs, User relationship management costs that include call center management, complaint resolution, as per Service Level Agreements, outsourcing costs, Safety and emergency management costs like backup supply lines, reserve sources, plan for low flow conditions, etc., Water quantity and Quality monitoring program along with staff and lab costs, Wastewater and sewage treatment and handling costs. All these costs should be calculated and budgeted for. If different agencies are involved, the budget should be derived through consolidation.

For billing, a clear national policy should be formulated and regulated. Such policy should focus on building a value perception of water, rewarding conservation, self-regulation by water user committees, and conservation during low-flow conditions due to failed monsoons. The suggested types of users to be considered are Rural households, Domestic Urban poor households, Domestic Urban households, Institutions, MSME, Major Industries, Hydropower Utilities, Agriculture – small/ medium, and large farm holdings, and Navigation and tourism. Metering should be made mandatory so that the consumption can be monitored and tracked, irrespective of the policy about charges. An appropriate system with three slabs of volumetric consumption is suggested, for all types of users. All these elements should be considered and an appropriate model for cost recovery should be arrived at. If the same is to be subsidised, the same should be budgeted for, with clearly demarcated sources of funds.

Conclusion

The objective of the research was to come up with a better understanding and possible common approach for levying urban domestic water charges. The research used an innovative methodology of doing multiple case studies together to achieve the common research objective. While a few attempts have been made to develop

such frameworks for water pricing, there have not been any significant attempts to arrive at such an approach in India. The research findings have significant practical implications for sustainably formulating future urban water policies.

Keywords: Urban Water Pricing, Domestic consumption, Sustainable water supply, Pricing framework, Disparities

Development of Sustainable Ecosystem through Use of Industrial By-product for Development of Urban Infrastructure: Study of Industrial By-product Use by Firms in Indian Iron and Steel Industry

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Industrial Ecosystem is highly degenerative and during the production process, it generates a lot of by product and wastes, which includes both solid and gaseous substances. Industrial Ecosystem also contribute substantially to environmental pollution through contribution to Green House Gas emission. Management of Industrial by product and waste is a huge challenge. So effective Industrial by product and waste management is essential for sustainability of the Industrial Ecosystem. The developing countries are growing at a fast pace, due to which migration of population from hinterland to cities is taking place in an unprecedented rate. This is leading to growth of urbanisation at a rapid pace. In order to cater to that, there is a need to augment the infrastructure. So, can the Industrial by products be used to build the Urban Infrastructure which will help in achieving a sustainable growth for both Industry and Urban Infrastructure?

In this article, we have examined the case of by product generation by firms in Indian Iron and Steel Industry (IISI) and their use in building urban Infrastructure. Production of Iron and Steel is a complex process and during the entire production cycle, iron ore is processed through a number of intertwined and integrated steps to deliver the final output. Slag is one of the byproducts generated both during the production of Iron (Blast Furnace Slag) and Steel (LD Slag) in addition to other gaseous by products and flue dust. A lot of studies were conducted in different countries like USA, European countries, Japan, and China about the use of LD slag for development of urban infrastructure like land filling and road construction. Off late studies were also conducted about the use of LD slag as a substitute for fertilizer. It has been observed that countries like USA, European countries, Japan, China etc. effectively utilise the LD slag and Blast Furnace slag for land filling, road construction, production of cement and use as a substitute for aggregate and sand. Even some of the countries are effectively utilising the LD slag as a substitute for fertilizer. Use of LD slag not only helps in conserving the natural resources but also helps in reducing the carbon footprint thus creating a sustainable Ecosystem. But in the Indian context studies are scant about use of LD slag for land filling and road construction although few firms in Indian Iron and Steel Industry are working towards hundred percent solid waste utilisation by utilising the by products for Infrastructure development.

To address this gap, we have adopted a mixed-method approach, including surveys, interviews, and secondary sources to collect the data regarding use of LD slag for few firms in the Indian Iron and Steel Industry. India being a developing economy, needs to develop a lot of urban infrastructure to cater to the need of the future population that will migrate from the hinterland to the urban spaces. LD slag can be effectively utilised for building Urban Infrastructure especially land filling and road construction. LD slag contains lime, which makes it unstable and thus it becomes unsuitable for use in road construction. So, weathering of LD slag is required to increase the stability which can subsequently be used in the subbase of the road. Use of LD slag for road construction can eliminate the use of a lot of natural resources like sand and aggregate which will lead to its conservation and thus creation of a sustainable ecosystem.

From the literature, It has also been observed that LD slag use in Hot mix Asphalt (HMA) for road construction is being deployed on a trial basis in many countries especially in China. The result of use of LD slag in HMA is showing an encouraging result and, it's use is reducing the Green House Gas emission. But in India the use of LD slag in HMA is scarce. Similarly, use of LD slag as a substitute for fertilizer is being tried in other countries and the results

are encouraging. But in the Indian context the use of LD slag as a substitute for fertilizer is also limited. So, there is scope for future research in all these areas for use of Industrial by-product for creation of urban infrastructure. If found successful, then it will help in creating a sustainable ecosystem which will lead to regenerativeness.

Keywords: LD Slag, Indian Iron and Steel Industry (IISI), Hot-Mix Asphalt (HMA), Road Construction

Urban Infrastructure and Sustainable Development: A Study of Three Small Towns in West Bengal

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Infrastructure plays a critical role in all forms of development, and its deficiency often creates a major barrier in economic development, advancement of society, and environmental protection. In 1994, the World Development Report had listed the following four services under the infrastructure categories: (a) public utilities: contain solid waste collection and disposal, sanitation and sewerage, piped water delivery, power, telecommunications and piped gas supply. (b) public works: cover roads, large dams, irrigation systems, and drainage canals, (c) other transportation sectors: include airports, ports and waterways, urban and interurban railroads, and urban transportation. (d) social infrastructure: comprises of financial services, primary healthcare, and basic education. Generally, water supply, sanitation facilities and hygienic (WASH) practices are considered to be indispensable parts of urban infrastructure. Based on the World Cities Report (2022), currently 55% of the total population on Earth reside in urban areas, and by 2050, this percentage is predicted to be rising to around 68%. In order to meet the basic needs of the rising urban population, there is a dire need of these infrastructure amenities in the urban areas.

This study investigates adequate housing and the nature of three basic service provisions in Budge Budge, Diamond Harbour and Pujali small statutory towns in South 24 Parganas of West Bengal to achieve target 11.1 of sustainable development goal (SDG) 11. These infrastructure facilities include water supply service, sanitation facility and urban primary health care facility. To understand urban infrastructure sustainability, a total of 218 samples have been collected from the households through the stratified random sampling method. The structured and semi-structured questionnaires have been used to collect both qualitative and quantitative data from the field survey. Conducting interviews with municipal officials has been done with the aim of gathering information about the obstacles and challenges that are being faced by the towns in the path to achieve infrastructure sustainability.

Adequate housing is an important issue in India. In India, there are 0.9 million homeless urban people and about 65 million urban dwellers (17%) live in slums and suffer from housing problems (India's Housing Conundrum, 2020). To tackle the housing challenge, a number of policies were implemented in India after 1947. Currently, the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana Urban (PMAY-U), launched in 2015, has added a significant momentum to urban areas to reduce housing challenges. Based on the field survey report, overall, 85% of the urban dwellers have their own houses and about 74.52% of the households enjoy secure land tenure in these towns. A significant proportion of economically weaker section (EWS) and middle-income group (MIG) in Budge Budge (15%), Diamond Harbour (10.94%), and Pujali (17.19%) are enjoying the facilities of the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY), along with secure land tenure. On the other hand, the slum-dwellers in these towns are unable to avail the benefits of the PM Awas Yojana, because of the absence of secure land tenure. This study has found that Budge Budge, Diamond Harbour, and Pujali towns struggle greatly for access to adequate clean water supply. Regarding the municipal water supply system, Budge Budge, Diamond Harbour and Pujali differ from one another. When it comes to drinking water, the situation in Diamond Harbour and Pujali is more serious than that of Budge Budge. Household connection to municipal supply water service is highest (76.25%) in Budge Budge municipality, followed by Diamond Harbour (61.19%). In Pujali municipality, only 40.63% of the respondents are enjoying household access to the municipal supply of water. Considering the three municipalities, this study has found that none of the slum households are connected with the water supply service. The main reasons behind such deprivation are the insecure land tenant and insufficient income. Unfortunately, these residents have nothing to do but to wait in

long lines to get water from the community taps. A key component of sustainable development (SDG target 11.1) is access to adequate, safe water for all. Therefore, there is an urgent need to increase the supply of adequate, safe water at the household level. Additionally, a steady supply of sufficient, clean water is essential for maintaining both good health and quality of life.

Based on the 2018 National Sample Survey, 96.2% of the urban areas in India have access to household latrines, which shows a significant progress in the sanitation sector. More significantly, sanitation in urban India has greatly improved since the introduction of the Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM) in 2014. Through the effective work of the SBM, 98% of Indian cities (4,360) have become open defecation free (ODF), and 98.7% of men and 98.1% of women use latrines regularly in urban areas (MoSPI, 2018). According to the field survey data of these towns, about 93% of the total households have access to private toilets. In Budge Budge and Diamond Harbour, about 12% of the slum households rely on public toilets, and they have expressed dissatisfaction with the current state of sanitation. On the other hand, under the Mission Nirmal Bangla (U) or Swachh Bharat Mission (U), overall, only 20% of the poor and slum households have got individual latrines. There is no wastewater treatment system in any of the three municipalities. Here, wastewater flows directly into the Hooghly River through the internal canals and drains of these towns. Therefore, it is essential to treat all the wastewater through a Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) in order to prevent health-related and environmental risks. The municipal authorities have stated that due to financial crises they have not been able to install any STP in their towns. In case of drainage systems, overall 52% of the households in these towns are connected to the drainage system. Out of these three towns, the lowest percentage of households in Pujali (17.19%) have connections with the drainage system. The majority of the respondents (78%) are not satisfied with the drainage system. Due to inadequate drainage system, waterlogging is a common phenomenon in the low-lying places in Budge Budge (ward nos. 3, 4, 11, and 20), Diamond Harbour (ward nos. 8, 10, 14, and 16) and Pujali (ward nos. 1, 4, and 16). It has been also found that Budge Budge, Diamond Harbour and Pujali have been facing challenges to manage huge quantity of solid wastes produced by them. These three towns have taken important steps to implement the Mission Nirmal Bangla plan in accordance with the State Urban Development Agency (SUDA) guidelines for solid waste management. As per the field survey report, municipal authorities of these towns are not able to collect waste from all households of each ward.

In this study, about 80% of the households depend on private health care services. Respondents have stated that they prefer to go to private health services to avoid poor quality services and prolong waiting. Thus, this study provides insightful information on the need to ensure universal access to basic infrastructure facilities in selected small towns, particularly housing and WASH infrastructure to meet the SDG target 11.1.

Keywords: Adequate housing, Basic services, Small towns, Sustainable Development Goal 11

Jodhpur's Rising Tide: A Paradoxical Threat to a Scarce Resource

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Jodhpur, situated in the heart of the Thar Desert, grapples with a paradoxical water crisis like no other. On one hand, chronic water scarcity plagues the land, a constant reminder of the harsh desert environment. However, in a seemingly contradictory twist, at least 40% of the city experiences a peculiar phenomenon – rising groundwater levels. Though it seems like a promising solution, but the harsh reality is too far from it. This study delves deeper into the intricate threads weaving this complex paradox, unravelling its origins and exposing its far-reaching consequences. It urges the immediate adoption of sustainable water management strategies to navigate this unprecedented challenge and carve a path toward a water-secure future for Jodhpur.

The groundwater table has been continuously rising approximately 1.0 m per year in old walled city and adjoining areas. The multifaceted causes of Jodhpur's paradoxical water crisis include poor-yielding geological formations which are the layers of impervious rocks that act as a basin, trapping water beneath the surface that restrict the seepage of water to deeper levels, resulting in very low transmissivity of the water-bearing formations. Limited drainage options and low water transmissivity within these layers further restrict the natural outflow, leading

to a gradual accumulation. Additionally, inefficient canal irrigation systems like the Rajiv Gandhi Lift Canal contribute significantly to the rising groundwater table, posing challenges that require continuous pumping to prevent structural damage and flooding. Notably, the canal systems, intended to alleviate the desert's aridity, inadvertently contribute to the rise, at the cost of contamination with pollutants and salts. Hydrogeological data reveals a correlation between the elevated water level of Kailana Lake-Takht Sagar and the city's rising water table, accentuated by uneven distribution leading to waterlogging and persistent scarcity.

The consequences of this paradoxical rise are far-reaching and touch every facet of Jodhpur's life. Contaminated water, rendered unfit for consumption and irrigation, poses threats to both human health and agricultural productivity. Outbreaks of waterborne diseases become a constant concern, while crop yields dwindle. Rising water levels trigger structural damage, weakening buildings and compromising infrastructure. Delicate desert ecosystems face disruption, impacting habitats and biodiversity. Uneven distribution, with pockets of waterlogging amidst vast stretches of scarcity, further aggravates the situation, jeopardising economic activities and fostering social inequities.

Recognising the urgency, the city has adopted its Proposed Master Plan for 2031, a visionary roadmap for sustainable water management. This ambitious plan proposes a paradigm shift, reimagining how the city interacts with water. Imagine improved drainage networks channelling excess water away from vulnerable areas, nourishing thirsty aquifers through revitalised recharge ponds. Picture rooftops adorned with rainwater harvesting systems, collecting every precious drop from the desert sky. The plan prioritises decentralised solutions, empowering households and communities to become custodians of their water resources.

This proactive approach finds further support in recommendations from the Central Ground Water Board and the National Geophysical Research Institute. Their insights pave potential pathways for mitigating the crisis: improved drainage systems to redirect excess water, utilising underutilised surface water bodies like Kailana Lake-Takht Sagar, and even reviving historical groundwater structures like step-wells– a nod to the wisdom of the past. The Public Health Engineering Department's commendable effort of actively pumping from 89 groundwater sources showcases its commitment to providing immediate relief. However, drawing out such vast quantities underscores the need for long-term conservation strategies. Implementing smart meters, introducing tiered water pricing, and promoting water-efficient appliances can empower residents to conserve this precious resource. Additionally, innovative vertical drainage systems offer localised solutions to waterlogging. These systems, utilising clever underground channels, effectively divert excess water, protecting infrastructure and potentially contributing to soil moisture. While offering localised benefits, they serve as vital pieces of a broader drainage improvement plan necessary to combat the rising groundwater challenge effectively.

However, navigating this complex challenge requires a symphony of coordinated efforts. The government plays a crucial role, with state and district-level task forces working tirelessly alongside the Ground Water Department's constant monitoring. The construction of the Indira Gandhi Nahar Pariyojana Canal stands as a testament to this collective determination. Beyond government initiatives, building resilience through community engagement is equally vital. Imagine awareness campaigns educating residents about conservation practices and fostering a culture of responsible water use. Encouraging sustainable agricultural practices, adapted to the harsh desert environment, can further reduce pressure on precious water resources.

Jodhpur's water paradox is not just a local struggle; it presents a unique case study for arid regions and urban centers facing similar challenges. As the city navigates its path toward a water-secure future, its experiences offer valuable lessons for others. Continuous research, innovation, and adaptation will be the guiding stars on this journey. By embracing a holistic approach that prioritises long-term sustainability, Jodhpur can transform its paradoxical story into a compelling narrative of resilience and hope, becoming an inspiring precedent for tackling water challenges across the globe.

Keywords: Water crisis, Groundwater level, Water quality, Sustainable water management, Hydrogeology

Sawantwadi's Storied Drains: Managing Growth in a Heritage City

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Sawantwadi, a coastal town in India, has long been celebrated for its historically effective drainage management system. The town's network of interconnected open drains and natural water bodies has adeptly navigated seasonal fluctuations and monsoon rains for centuries. However, the rapid urban expansion and the surge in apartment complexes in recent years have placed unprecedented strain on this traditionally efficient system, presenting new and complex challenges to Sawantwadi's wastewater management.

Compounding the issue is the absence of a dedicated municipal sewerage system. Untreated greywater, comprised of soapy effluents and domestic waste, infiltrates drains and gutters, disrupting the natural ecological balance. This disruption leads to changes in the pH, hardness, and alkalinity of drain water, setting off a chain of environmental issues, including mosquito breeding. Poor maintenance of drains and improper solid waste disposal further exacerbate the problem, causing blockages and water stagnation.

A survey conducted by the Sawantwadi Municipal Council underscores the gravity of the challenges faced by the town. While traditional soak pits and septic tanks handle blackwater for individual houses, a significant 20% of households still release greywater directly into the drains. Despite commendable initiatives by the Municipal Council, such as mandating individual septic tanks or soak pits and mandating communal Sewage Treatment Plants (STPs) for apartment complexes, challenges persist. Non-compliance by some buildings and the absence of a comprehensive city-wide STP hinder the effectiveness of these efforts.

Despite a proposal in 2016 to strengthen the main drainage system, no tangible improvements have been implemented, emphasising the urgency of finding effective and sustainable solutions. In response to these challenges, this study explores potential remedies under the Swachh Bharat Mission 2.0 initiative. One promising option is the implementation of a centralised STP, ensuring efficient wastewater treatment and minimising environmental impact. Decentralised options, such as bioremediation techniques like anaerobic digesters and membrane bioreactors, are also considered viable, aligning with the local context and resource constraints. These solutions hold the potential to promote sustainability and resilience in Sawantwadi's wastewater management.

To delve deeper into potential solutions, Anaerobic digesters, for instance, are a type of bioremediation technology that utilises microorganisms to break down organic matter in the absence of oxygen. This process not only facilitates wastewater treatment but also produces biogas, which can be harnessed for energy generation. Moreover, the digestate produced during the process can be applied as fertilizer, contributing to agricultural sustainability. This technology proves to be a sustainable and cost-effective solution for wastewater treatment in Sawantwadi, especially in areas with limited access to centralised infrastructure.

Membrane bioreactors (MBRs) represent another decentralised bioremediation option. MBRs combine biological treatment processes with membrane filtration, providing a more efficient means of treating wastewater. This technology offers a smaller footprint compared to traditional treatment methods, making it suitable for densely populated urban areas. Moreover, the high-quality effluent produced by MBRs can be used for non-potable purposes, such as irrigation or industrial processes, contributing to water conservation efforts.

Incorporating relevant data and statistics further fortifies the arguments and supports the conclusions of the study. Sawantwadi, with its population and an average annual rainfall of 2,000 mm, generates a substantial amount of wastewater. The current drainage system, estimated to handle only about 60% of this wastewater effectively, poses severe environmental and public health concerns. Recognising these challenges, implementing a comprehensive wastewater treatment solution becomes crucial to ensure the long-term sustainability of the town.

To provide historical context, Sawantwadi's traditional drainage system, dating back to the 17th century, was a marvel of its time. The network of interconnected open drains and natural water bodies was designed to mimic natural hydrological processes and effectively manage stormwater and wastewater. However, the dynamics have shifted with rapid urbanisation and changing environmental conditions, necessitating the development of modern solutions.

A centralised Sewage Treatment Plant (STP) as a potential solution. A centralised STP serves as a critical component in addressing Sawantwadi's wastewater management challenges. Such a facility would consolidate the treatment process, efficiently handling a significant volume of wastewater from various sources.

The centralised STP would employ advanced treatment technologies, including biological treatment processes, chemical treatment, and filtration, to ensure thorough and effective purification of the wastewater. This would significantly reduce the environmental impact of untreated greywater entering the drains and gutters. The treated water, meeting stringent quality standards, could then be safely discharged or repurposed for non-potable uses, minimising the strain on natural water bodies.

Moreover, a centralised STP provides a platform for monitoring and regulating the quality of effluent released into the environment. Regular testing and analysis would ensure compliance with environmental standards, safeguarding the ecosystem and public health. The implementation of such a facility would also centralise maintenance efforts, reducing the likelihood of blockages and ensuring the longevity of the wastewater treatment infrastructure.

However, the success of a centralised STP depends on comprehensive planning, robust infrastructure, and community engagement. Stakeholder involvement, including residents, businesses, and local authorities, is crucial for the acceptance and sustainability of such a large-scale initiative. Public awareness campaigns and educational programs can foster a sense of responsibility among the community, encouraging proper waste disposal practices and reducing the burden on the wastewater treatment system.

While a centralised STP offers comprehensive wastewater treatment, its economic viability depends on various factors, including initial investment, operational costs, and potential revenue streams. The construction of a centralised STP involves significant upfront capital, including the cost of land, infrastructure, and advanced treatment technologies.

However, the economic feasibility improves when considering the long-term benefits, including reduced environmental impact, improved public health, and potential revenue from treated water reuse. The use of anaerobic digesters within the centralised STP can generate additional revenue through the production of biogas, which can be utilised for energy generation. This economic incentive enhances the overall sustainability of the wastewater treatment system.

In contrast, decentralised options like anaerobic digesters at the individual or community level provide a more localised and potentially cost-effective solution. While the initial investment for individual anaerobic digesters may be lower, the overall impact on the town's wastewater management depends on widespread adoption. Community-level anaerobic digesters can strike a balance between decentralisation and efficiency, catering to multiple households while maintaining centralised treatment benefits.

The economic feasibility of these solutions is intricately linked to government policies, incentives, and financing mechanisms. Subsidies for the installation of wastewater treatment systems, tax incentives for businesses adopting sustainable practices, and public-private partnerships can contribute to making these solutions financially viable.

In conclusion, the study critically examines Sawantwadi's drainage system in the face of contemporary challenges. By analysing existing infrastructure limitations and proposing potential solutions, it aims to contribute to the development of sustainable wastewater management strategies. By advocating for solutions that are ecologically sound, economically viable, and socially inclusive, we can ensure that Sawantwadi's storied drains continue to flow with the promise of a cleaner and healthier future.

Keywords: Wastewater management, Sewage treatment, Swachh Bharat Mission, Sustainability, Heritage city

Evaluating Level of Service for a Public Bus Transportation System- A Case Study of Mo Bus in Bhubaneswar, Odisha

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Public transportation plays a pivotal role in providing sustainable mobility. However, mere provision of a public transport system is not enough to shift passengers from private modes to sustainable mass transport modes. The need for quality mass transport modes that cater to the needs of both the captive and choice riders is the need of the hour, especially in countries of the Global south where not only are cities expanding at an exponential rate but also the income disparity between the rich and poor. Thus, evaluation of the performance of the existing transportation system is a requisite for retaining existing passengers and bringing about effective modal shift. The assessment becomes pivotal considering the volumes of investment made into development of public transport infrastructure in metropolitan cities, and especially those that have been identified as smart cities in India. Thus, the present study aims to evaluate the performance of the existing public bus transportation service of the city of Bhubaneswar.

An effective tool for measurement of the performance of an infrastructure is the Level of Service (LOS). LOS is a qualitative measurement tool that describes the operational conditions of an infrastructure by categorising it into four or more performance levels. There are multiple methodologies to compute Level of Services for public bus transportation systems based on user perception, observation of existing performance, expert opinion, etc. Since analysis based on perception can lead to biased results, the current study evaluates the LOS of public bus transportation system in Bhubaneswar based on service operation data, and observation-based surveys. Thus, the Service Level Benchmarking (SLB) developed by COE- CEPT University, in collaboration with the Ministry of Urban Development (MoUD), Government of India (GoI) for transportation systems in India has been used to evaluate the performance of the bus transportation system of the study area. The SLB has been a crucial tool for introducing accountability and aids Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) and other agencies in identifying performance gaps and implementing improvements through the sharing of information and best practices. The SLB identified a total of 14 indicators for measurement of the quality of a public transport facility in a city based on availability, efficiency, quality (attractiveness), and coverage of service. Performance of a PT is measured on a LOS scale of 1 to 4, where LOS 1 represents an excellent performance while LOS 4 represents worst performance. However, for the purpose of this study, the following twelve indicators have been selected- presence of organised public transport system in an urban area, extent of availability of public transport, service coverage of public transport in the study area, average waiting time for public transport users, level of comfort in public transport, percentage fleet size as per Urban Bus Specifications (UBS), percentage built-up area within 500m of public transport plying, total boarding per thousand population, affordability of public transport, percentage breakdown of public transport, and percentage vehicle utilisation.

The current study evaluates the performance of Mo Bus service operated by Capital Region Urban Transport (CRUT) in collaboration with the Government of Odisha within the Bhubaneswar Development Authority area. This includes the area under the Bhubaneswar Municipal Corporation, Jatani Municipality, Khordha Municipality, and Pipili Municipality. Bhubaneswar is the capital of the state of Odisha in India, and the largest city in the state. Additionally, with the status of being a smart city, Bhubaneswar is one of the most rapidly growing cities in the country. Estimated to be housing a population of 1,289,254 in 2024, the city has an intricate public bus transportation system. Mo bus has an operational network length of 97,761 km catered by 90 routes using a fleet size of 405 buses. However, as stated earlier, for the purpose of this study, the BDA area has been identified, and CRUT operates a network of 176 km within the BDA area through 66 bus routes. The daily average ridership within this region for the financial 2022-23 was 39,595.

The study observes that the performance of Mo bus services varies across various indicators. In context to indicators based on bus fleet, Mo bus services have LOS 1 service for indicators like presence of organised public transport system in an urban area, extent of availability of public transport, percentage fleet size as per Urban Bus Specifications. This is mainly attributed to the factor that all Mo Bus infrastructure including fleet is owned by CRUT. However, in context to maintenance, it has been observed that Mo bus experiences LOS 4 level of service

with 1543 breakdowns of buses during on-road operation during the year 2022-23. Mo Bus also performs poorly in context to indicators associated with comfort and service coverage. In spite of operating a network length of 176 km within the BDA area, the service frequency in some of the routes is as high as 60 minutes during off-peak hours.

This study contributes to the discourse on enhancing public transport performance through the city-level benchmarking approach. The proposed methodology provides a structured framework for evaluating existing services and making informed decisions before investing in a new public transportation system. The case study of Bhubaneswar City demonstrates the practical application of the methodology, and the focus on the level of service contribute to a holistic understanding of public transport quality, enabling cities to address challenges and improve overall urban mobility.

Keywords: Level of Service, Quality of Services, Public Transport, Bus System, Mo Bus

Urban Informality within the Context of Sustainability: A Study of Few Slums in Kolkata

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The urbanisation process is accelerating worldwide, and cities all over the world continue to gain greatly from it. High population increase in the global South—that is, parts of Africa, Asia, and South America — which were once referred to as developing economies — is now predicted to be the primary driver of the world’s rapid urbanisation. The governments of the global South’s fast urbanising cities however are struggling to keep up with and adjust to the growing population. Unrestrained urbanisation has brought about serious problems for sustainable development. One such pervasive problem in the urban landscape is urban informality in terms of illegal land occupation and informal housing. Urban informality is a major aspect of our times, impacting economies, personal livelihoods, and living arrangements. Because of its widespread popularity and potential, academics, city officials, and practitioners of urban planning are nevertheless interested in informality. As a result, informality is now central to the conversation around urban planning. Informal settlements or slums are the spatial expressions of urban informality resulting from lack of formal means of housing and illegal claim for space. The goal of the current study is to highlight the part slums play in the conversation about sustainable cities. The idea of sustainable cities is emphasised in the eleventh Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). Target 11.1 of the SDGs clearly specifies that by 2030, everyone must have access to sufficient, safe, and affordable housing as well as essential services and along with provisions of slum upgradation. Goal 11 of the SDGs aspires to make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable. In order to achieve this goal, a look into the current situation of slums is necessary to be able to decide on what measures to undertake to attain sustainable urban development. This paper therefore attempts to explore the socio-economic conditions of slum dwellers in a few selected slums of Kolkata in the context of sustainable urban development. Through an analysis of a few selected slums, this paper investigates the relationship between informality and sustainability in the city of Kolkata. The study highlights how urban informality in terms informal housing and illegal land occupation poses serious challenges to sustainable urban development in the city of Kolkata. Kolkata’s historical and geographical features makes it an ideal place to study in order to enlighten the relation between urbanisation and rising informalities in the metro city. Like other major cities in India, Kolkata is rapidly undergoing changes as the country’s population and economy booms. After a long period of stagnation post-independence, the city’s economy started to revive with the liberalisation of the Indian economy in 1991 and since then, it has been growing. However, with growth comes an insatiable appetite for land and development. Next to these modern and planned developments to cater to the demands of the growing economy are thousands of slums and squatter settlements where 31.35 % of Kolkata’s population resides, which is the second largest in any metro city in India, after Mumbai. Both the central and the state government have from time to time launched and implemented projects to improve and upgrade slums in Kolkata but have been unable to completely eradicate slums from the face of the city. The slums in the city of Kolkata are too diverse and the planning process too complex which makes it a challenging perspective within the scope of urban sustainability. The present work bases its findings on primary data through field survey in the slums of Kolkata. Eight slums were selected for the study - Belgachia model basti, Baghbazar Mayer Bari

basti, Ultadanga 76 pally basti, Ultadanga BSUP basti, Chetla thika basti, Jadavpur Jhoro basti, Behala Shanti Sangha basti, Taratala Sakaldev basti (these are the local names used for the respective slums). The slums chosen for the study were based on information gathered from Kolkata Municipal Corporation. Household survey was conducted through semi-structured questionnaire from November, 2022 to July, 2023 covering 105 research participants were chosen by random sampling method. The information is analysed using descriptive statistics. Responses have been collected on various socio-economic conditions and the marginal experiences faced by the research participants which are - main reason for settling in that particular slum, house ownership status, titles or documents possession with respect to land/house settled in, status of basic amenities received, type of pollution prevailing and the major problems faced by them, duration of their stay in the respective slums. The findings based on the mentioned parameters reveal that there is lack of security of tenure, limited access to basic amenities and urban infrastructure which stands in the way for sustainable urban development. To address the situation, few housing projects under Rajiv Awas Yojana, Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission and Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana have been taken up by the government in few selected slums in Kolkata; nevertheless, none of them are large enough to meet the issues of housing shortages and environmental quality in the city of Kolkata. A look into the situation after the projects are being implemented enables us to get a clearer picture and depict the reality. Urban informality, housing inequality, and social exclusion are significantly influenced by socio-economic level, which is why housing design, construction, and provision should be taken into account. The integrated socio-economic and environmental urban redevelopment approach should be focused while emphasising on renovation and renewal. A socio-economic support strategy should be undertaken that will encourage the overall slum environment to change. Four major urban stakeholders should be involved in this strategy: the public; the private and public-private sectors; the government (including relevant agencies); and non-governmental organisations that will combine socio-economic and environmental factors to enhance the quality of life in urban areas facing challenges. Sustainable initiatives not only initiate a long-term development process, but they also permanently improve living conditions. It is therefore in the hands of the planning process to deal with urban informality in terms of informal housing and illegal land occupation by making sure that the urban poor has access to formal housing, basic amenities and urban infrastructure. Planning is a collaborative, multidisciplinary effort. For urban planning in India, achieving rapid growth that is inclusive and sustainable poses enormous obstacles. In order to facilitate and accommodate growing urbanisation, new cities will need to be constructed, and existing cities and their peripheries will need to provide additional space. To effectively achieve sustainable urban development, inclusivity is essential. Promoting fairness and building inclusive cities where everyone may engage in their social, economic, and political dynamics should be the goals of achieving the sustainable vision. All housing—not only projects—must be completely integrated—physically, socially, and economically—into the surrounding neighbourhoods and the main city for it to be sustainable.

Keywords: Urbanisation, Urban Informality, Sustainability, Slums, Kolkata

Inclusive Slum Planning of Kolkata: A Case Study of Registered Slum and Unregistered Slum

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To shed light on the complicated process of establishing an inclusive planning strategy for a variety of slums, including those that are registered and those that are not registered, the purpose of this study is to provide information to shed light on the process. This study's objective is to shed light on the process. One of the goals of this study is to shed light on the particular procedure. To accomplish this objective, this inquiry is currently being carried out right at this exact time. To accomplish the objective of rehabilitation or relocation, it is required to use a wide variety of diverse ways. To achieve this level of comprehension, this must be carried out. Ensure that these groups are integrated into society in a way that is not easily obvious to persons who are not a part of it. The purpose of this strategy is to ensure that this integration takes place to accomplish the purpose of ensuring that these groups are integrated into society. The implementation of this approach is the primary purpose of this

strategy, as it is the only way to guarantee that this assimilation will take place. It was decided to use the method of stratified random sampling throughout the process to guarantee that the slums that were going to be researched were chosen appropriately. This was done to guarantee that the operation would be successful. It was necessary to take this action to ensure that the decision was taken. The classification of these slums was carried out in line with the legal rules that applied to every one of these particular instances. To ensure that the sample is representative of the total population, which was the aim behind this action, this was done to guarantee that the sample could be considered representative. This step was essential to ensure that the sample can be relied upon to produce an accurate representative of the entire. It was required to complete this step. The following section of the introduction is going to be devoted to providing a comprehensive study of the existing situation in the low-income settlements that are located in Kolkata. This section's objective is to provide a general overview of the issue currently being discussed. As a means of making the structure of this section easier, it has been divided into two distinct sections that are kept separate from one another. For the sake of the reader's attention, this analysis is presented to them in the section of the work that is devoted to the introduction. For this review, which has a particular emphasis on slums, some of the slums that have been discovered and taken into consideration are included. Additionally, the examination considers the slums that have been found at this time. To determine whether or not these communities are suitable in terms of providing housing that is not only safe but also affordable, as well as access to important urban services such as water, waste management, power, safety measures, and chances to generate money, the goal of this research is to investigate whether or not these particular communities are suitable. Ex-situ slum reservation and in-situ slum reservation are two distinct methods of planning that will be discussed in the next section. Both of these methods are referred to as "slum reservation." These two methods are not interchangeable with one another in any way whatsoever. In both their individual and collective forms, these two approaches are referred to as "slum reservation." In no manner, shape, or form are these two approaches compatible with one another. They are incompatible with one another. They cannot be converted into one another. After the conclusion of the next conversation, each of these tactics will be investigated in great detail, and the findings will be given to the audience. One of the most important aspects that must be considered is the classification of the slum, and both of these solutions consider this. The fact remains that this is the case regardless of the strategy that is utilised to address the condition. It has been suggested that this framework be built from the ground up to foster inclusion and spatial efficiency, which would ultimately lead to increased access to essential services. Developing a conceptual framework to achieve these goals would be how this would be accomplished. The creation of a conceptual framework, which would serve as how this objective would be achieved, would be how it would be completed. During the examination, it was determined that the growth of these informal settlements is subject to specific limitations. This was approved. In addition, it has been suggested that these flaws be addressed and repaired to effectively address and resolve them. In the meanwhile, while keeping in mind the end goal that we are working towards, the idea is to make these services more available to a greater number of people across the overall population. Based on the fact that rehabilitation or in-situ slum planning demonstrates a higher level of inclusion in comparison to the other design, it is possible to assert that both models have achieved a certain amount of success. Both of these models have shown that they are successful, which is the reason for this reason. With this information, one may conclude that it is reasonable to state that both models have achieved a certain amount of success within their respective markets. This is the conclusion that can be derived from this.

Keywords: Registered slum, Unregistered slum, In-situ slum planning, Ex-situ slum planning, Kolkata

Greening Tradition: A Technological Blueprint of Durga Puja Celebrations towards Sustainable Livelihoods in Global South

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Durga Puja, a grandiose South Asian holiday, transcends cultural boundaries, symbolising the triumph of good over evil. This article investigates the intersection of tradition and technology with the goal of transforming Durga

Puja into a sustainable paradigm that promotes economic growth and societal well-being. Our research navigates the interface between tradition and innovation, presenting a roadmap for sustainable celebrations using terms such as sustainability, technology, economy, and livelihoods. Understanding the socio-cultural relevance of Durga Puja, identifying areas for technological intervention, and developing a sustainable model are among our goals. We plan to investigate the economic and socio-cultural benefits that a sustainable Durga Puja model can provide, transcending its cultural context and making it relevant to a larger global audience. To construct a comprehensive digital model, the proposed workflow calls for a multidisciplinary approach that combines cultural studies, technology integration, and economic research.

Our research unfolds in three phases. First, we analyse the current scenario of Durga Puja celebrations, emphasising the need for sustainable practices in festivals globally. Second, we propose a technological framework, leveraging innovations like smart solutions for infrastructure, waste management, statutory approvals, collaborative action plans, capacity building and stakeholder integration through digital platforms to enhance the sustainability of this grand festival which has been recently inscribed under the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage list. Third, we analyse various intrinsic factors or parameters to establish the economic and socio-cultural impact of our proposed model, aiming to provide insights applicable to festivals beyond Durga Puja.

Festival sustainability is a pressing global issue. In this first paragraph, we underline the growing significance of sustainability in the context of festivals around the world. Festivals, which were traditionally thought to be ephemeral gatherings, are increasingly acknowledged for their long-term impact on the environment and society. The rising environmental impact of festivities necessitates a critical review of present methods as well as the need for innovative, sustainable solutions. Festivals, which were previously fleeting, now leave permanent imprints on the environment and society. This sentence reinforces the shift in attitude toward festivals. Festivals, once thought to be transient and transitory, are increasingly recognised for their long-term benefits on both the natural environment and human culture. The phrase emphasises the gravity of the problem, laying the groundwork for a more in-depth investigation of the environmental and societal ramifications of modern festival activities.

Our interest in Durga Puja stems from its universality as a festival, stressing the need for sustainable methods in celebrations. In this section, we explain why we chose Durga Puja as the topic of our research. Rather of focusing on the festival's cultural features, we emphasise its universality. This technique is critical in expressing that the study's findings are not limited to a single culture but are applicable to festivals worldwide. The phrase "sustainable models in festivities" implies a broader concept that goes beyond Durga Puja. Using Durga Puja as a case study, one can see how festivities can be rethought to be socially, economically, and environmentally responsible. In this statement, we set the stage for a closer look at Durga Puja as a case study. The title "case study" suggests an in-depth examination, and we highlight the three important characteristics we intend to investigate: environmental conscience, economic viability, and social inclusivity. We give a roadmap for the reader by utilising these terms, highlighting the aspects in which we want to examine and potentially modify festival celebrations. A sustained Durga Puja paradigm has considerable economic and socio-cultural benefits. This line establishes the importance of economic and socio-cultural issues in the framework of a sustainable Durga Puja model before transitioning to the paper's main themes. By using the word "significant," we mean the potential positive benefits that can be obtained by implementing sustainable practices during the festival. Festivals can serve as economic growth accelerators by creating job opportunities and supporting community development. In this section, we discuss the economic benefits of festivals, framing them as catalysts for greater good change. When addressed responsibly, festivals can contribute to economic progress by creating new job possibilities and supporting overall community development. This is consistent with the conference track's overarching theme of "Economy and Livelihood." Durga Puja is a festival that plays a crucial role in contributing towards specific SDGs such as SDG 1: No Poverty and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth. It helps in the socio-economic upliftment of communities by providing employment and income generation opportunities. This festival has a significant impact on poverty alleviation in marginalised communities and creates an environment that is conducive to economic growth. Moreover, Durga Puja also helps advance SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production. By promoting sustainable consumption patterns among visitors, Durga Puja encourages the idea of conscious consumerism.

In recent years, there has been a rising recognition of the importance of balancing economic progress with environmental conservation. This acknowledgment has raised the profile of sustainability as a fundamental idea, highlighting the critical need to handle present challenges without jeopardising future generations' ability to meet their own needs. Durga Puja, a festival celebrated in Kolkata, is significant in this context, necessitating

a thorough focus on sustainability throughout its celebration. This emphasis is critical for the preservation of cultural history, the growth of local businesses, and the preservation of environmental integrity. The celebration of Durga Puja provides a significant boost to the local economy in Kolkata. This impact manifests itself in a variety of ways, including the expansion of small-scale industries such as those pertaining to artisans, an increase in the tourism and hospitality sector catering to visitors, and increased employment opportunities for temporary contract workers—such as those involved in pandal construction—among other benefits. The festival acts as a unique venue for furthering and preserving Kolkata’s opulent cultural tradition. This is accomplished by promoting traditional handicraft and aligning with contemporary initiatives such as “Vocal for Local,” which creates market routes and protects centuries-old cultural heritage. In modern times, increased global awareness of environmental concerns has driven efforts to reduce waste output and promote recycling as essential components of sustainable Durga Puja celebrations. Environmentally concerned steps have been implemented by organisers, including the incorporation of eco-friendly idols and the strengthening of waste management infrastructure. Concurrently, energy saving has become a top priority, as indicated by the use of efficient lighting systems, the use of renewable energy sources in construction materials, and pandal campaigning for eco-friendly construction techniques. These efforts highlight the evolving commitment to sustainability within the context of festivities. Durga Puja holds immense cultural significance, fostering a deep emotional attachment among people. Beyond its ephemeral urbanism—a transient metamorphosis of urban spaces during festivities—this celebration becomes a canvas for collective emotions. Temporarily transforming the cityscape, Durga Puja becomes a shared narrative, blending tradition with contemporary urban dynamics, embodying a temporal fusion that resonates emotionally with the populace.

Keywords: Durga Puja, Technology-driven, Sustainable model, Socio-cultural, Digital solutions

A Study of the Needs and Challenges in Developing a Dashboard for Public Bus Transport Services: A Case Study of Mo Bus in Bhubaneswar, Odisha

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In this current era of fast paced development and rapid urbanisation, data plays a vital role in decision-making. Authorities globally are actively working to develop innovative solutions that take advantage of data available in different forms and sources. However, obtaining data to understand the mobility patterns of passengers and freight continues to be a challenge worldwide. Nonetheless, the increasing focus on ‘smart cities’ has made it imperative to generate data through various digital services, sensors, devices, etc. for effective planning and management. The incorporation of digital technologies like GPS in vehicles, usage of ETM machines for ticketing, or usage of RFID chips and cards in the operation of public transportation services have enabled public transportation operators to generate data on passenger mobility. However, generating and storing data is only a part of the process, and is a job half done. The collected data needs to be analysed and represented in a simple and lucid format that enables quick and informed decision- making.

An effective method to represent complex data in a simple, easy-to-understand form is the usage of dashboards. Cities across the world rely on dashboards that use complex analytics to illustrate volumes of information in a simplified visual format. The use of dashboards by the Smart City Mission to illustrate the performance of various smart cities across India is a prime example of the same. Public transit service operators across the world like Transport for London, Land Transport Authority in Singapore relies heavily on dashboards for effective daily functioning of public transport services, and measurement of the performance of the same. Transportation dashboards across the world are observed to be effective in optimising routes, managing traffic flow, and identify potential bottlenecks. These data analytic tools help in overall optimisation of resource allocation, boost operational efficiency, and improve service quality.

In case of cities like that in India and in the global south in general, it is often observed that the data though generated, often remains in its raw form, and is not effectively leveraged to improve and enhance the functionality and effectiveness of the transportation services. In spite of huge investment in development of intelligent public transportation systems, the projects fail to sustain themselves in the long run due to the lack of usage and understanding of the complex data. Transport operators continue to rely on traditional methods of service operation and fail to identify the growing complexity of urban mobility. Studies also reveal that numerous pilot efforts have been initiated by transit service operators through the help of expert agencies to develop dashboards and use the same for service provision and information dissemination. Yet, the usage of these dashboards is limited to a short duration, and termination of contracts with expert agencies ceases the usage of the technology. The current study thus aims to study the needs and challenges experienced in development of a dashboard for public bus transportation operators for the city of Bhubaneswar in Odisha, India.

Bhubaneswar is the capital of the state of Odisha in India, and the largest city in the state. Additionally, with the status of being a smart city, Bhubaneswar is one of the most rapidly growing cities in the country. Estimated to be housing a population of 1,289,254 in 2024, the city has an intricate public bus transportation system known as 'Mo Bus'. Operated by Capital Region Urban Transport (CRUT) Mo Bus was launched in 2018, and currently operates along 25 routes in Bhubaneswar, Puri and Cuttack region. Within the city of Bhubaneswar, Mo bus has an operational network length of 97,761 km catered by 90 routes using a fleet size of 405 buses. CRUT currently uses mobile application and social media platforms to disseminate transit service-related information to users. Most of this information is limited to service schedule of various routes, and overall ridership volume. The operators currently do not have a dashboard that depicts information related to fare collection system and depicts the sales and revenue collected. In spite of the usage of intelligent transportation technologies, and generation of huge volumes of data related to passenger mobility patterns, service performance, etc. the usage of data for decision-making is limited to revenue generation, and corresponding ridership volumes. No form of Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is utilised to track the progress of the service.

The current study included identification of the relevant KPIs, as well as the use of appropriate data visualisation tools and methodologies to ensure data accuracy applicable for Mo Bus service. The study also underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement and the need to collaborate with end users, and transport managers to obtain comprehensive insights and enhance the dashboard's overall design. A sample console has also been developed as part of this study using an open-source platform to include a user-friendly and interactive analytical dashboard that may provide real-time insights into critical aspects of public transport services for both users and operators. The usage of the dashboard is expected to improve operational efficiency, facilitate informed decision-making, and improve the quality of the public transportation system.

Keywords: Public transport, Bus services, Dashboard, Data analytics, Key Performance Indicators

TRACK-3: ENVIRONMENT AND ECOSYSTEM

This track answers questions related to attainment of climate-resilient cities. What are the approaches, policies, and innovative planning to reduce the impact of climate change? What are the challenges and solutions in making cities resilient to disaster? How can the differential impact of climate change and disaster be addressed? This theme is further divided into the following sub-themes to address the following questions:

- Climate-resilient sustainable cities- Adaptation strategies, present scenarios, and various approaches
- Disaster Risk Reduction: Practice and policies in the global south
- Case studies and best practices of inclusive resilient planning and management of cities and regions
- Nature-based solution for climate change and disaster mitigation

Assessment of Ambient Air and Sustainability Perception among Urbanites in Eastern India

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At present globally around 4.4 billion people i.e. 56 percent of the world population live in cities. This is expected to grow more in the future where almost 7 people in 10 will live in cities. The present urban growth and related development coupled with population growth is leading to the ever-increasing phenomenon of urban environment degradation. One of the many faces of this degradation is pollution. Particularly air pollution which can be defined as the presence of unwanted substances in the air changing the natural quality of it is one of the grave concerns for the world today and in cities this has emerged as an issue as it is affecting the people living there. Maintenance of urban ambient air quality and control of pollution for a sustainable urban environment and livelihood as mentioned in SDG 11 and India being a signatory to the sustainable development goals makes things much more serious. Being one of the most populous countries and developing in nature, the growing urban areas of India are experiencing a severe problem of air quality change. Due to continuous burning of fossil fuels and the growth of the vehicle population together with high population growth have been responsible for the degradation of the urban ambient air quality increasing respiratory health problems and related premature mortality among the vulnerable population. Sensitive groups including children and old age individuals are getting more affected by this. In most cities of India vehicular pollution is becoming one of the main factors of ambient air quality degradation. Apart from that demand for power and generation and consumption due to population growth is leading to the emission of different pollutants like oxides of NO₂, SO₂, O₃, and lead along with the most abundant particles like PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in the ambient air. Further, there are different secondary pollutants like PAN and ground-level ozone due to the reactions among the primary pollutants. The concentration of these in the ambient air of urban areas is making the air unbreathable. Further long exposure to these pollutants in the ambient air leads to an increase in cardiovascular diseases among the vulnerable groups. Urban areas of developing countries are facing this much more than the others due to somewhat lack of proper management and mitigation methods. In India, major urban centers like Kolkata, Delhi, and Mumbai are going through a phase of rapid development and have experienced degradation of ambient air quality in the last few years. Kolkata the capital of West Bengal is of the most prominent and rapidly growing urban centers in India. Today, Kolkata is also facing the issue of degradation of ambient air quality. Being the largest metropolis in eastern India it is burdened with rapid expansion of its limits due to population growth further resulting in vehicular growth and power consumption leading to the concentration of pollutants in the urban ambient air. In the last few years vehicular emission has been responsible for the concentration of particulate matter in the ambient air and oxides of Sulphur, nitrogen, and others are being emitted from the industries within and outside of the city's boundary. Thermal power plant both within and in the suburbs of Kolkata like Kasba and Cossipore is also responsible for sufficient concentration of pollutants. The present study focuses on the analysis of urban ambient air quality in Kolkata and its perception among the inhabitants of the city. For the analysis data collected by the regular monitoring of the primary pollutants by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) under the NAAQM (National Ambient Air Quality Monitoring) program has been used. Six monitoring station along the prime locations within the city limit has been chosen for ambient air quality assessment. the method of Exceedance Factor (EF) which categorises the concentration in four categories starting from Low to Critical based on the derived value has been applied for the assessment of ambient air quality based on four main pollutants as PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and SO₂ for the period of 2019-20 for the selected stations. Among the pollutants PM_{2.5} high level in all six stations with value above 1.0 in all six-station ranging from 1.0-1.4. critical concentration of 2.1 for PM₁₀ is seen in more than one stations whereas NO₂ and SO₂ concentration is fluctuating between moderate to low. Further trends of average concentration of each pollutant for the period 2016-22 has been analysed respect to the specific standard set by the CPCB. Lowest concentration has been found for oxides of Sulphur for the period The study also focused on the perception of the citizens about the urban ambient air quality to catch an overall perspective of awareness and coping strategies which was fulfilled by systematic questionnaire survey including specific questions based on the purposive random sampling method in the areas near the six monitoring stations. A total of 110 participants were surveyed. The overall basic perception varied from 40 percent to a maximum of 70 percent among the respondents from the selected areas. 75 percent

of respondents showed awareness regarding the primary pollutants. Around 65 percent of respondents lacked knowledge about particulate matter in a station in south Kolkata. The majority of the respondents considered particulate matter as a primary pollutant in urban ambient air apart from a few areas. Regarding taking precautions around 57 percent of respondents denied taking any precautions. As for coping mechanisms, around 80 percent of respondents preferred to use masks in general. Social media and government campaigning are preferred for raising awareness about urban ambient air quality among the masses.

Keywords: Air quality, Pollution, Particulate matters, Sustainability, Perception

Comparative Study on Water Quality of Major Rivers of Uttar Pradesh: ANOVA Analysis

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Water is an essential life-sustaining natural resource present on Earth. Planet Earth is blessed with an abundant amount of water on earth. Fresh water on Earth is present in rivers, ponds, lakes, springs, etc. India is particularly blessed with some of the most significant rivers in the world. Uttar Pradesh has been blessed with many important rivers. These rivers are the lifeline of the state. The water quality of the rivers has been deteriorating recently, and these rivers need to be preserved as they are the lifeline of the areas where they flow. Pollution levels in these rivers have been increasing as wastewater from industries and households directly flows into the river without treatment.

Rivers provide life to the areas where they flow. Cities and villages are all dependent on the water resources of that area. Cities are dynamic, multifaceted meta-systems where social and technological elements interact. Cities are vulnerable to various dangers, so it's critical to plan for resilience in the event of an urban disaster. We are only now starting to grasp the breadth and depth of the difficulties in building cities resistant to terrorist attacks and natural disasters.

In this proposed paper, we plan to analyse the water quality of four essential rivers of Uttar Pradesh - Ganga, Gomti, Saryu and Yamuna. The rivers considered in this study are critical for the state as Gomti is the lifeline of the state's capital city, Lucknow. Ganga is the largest river in India and flows through India's spiritual capital, Varanasi. Saryu and Yamuna are essential, as mentioned in the ancient texts, it also drains the ancient city of Ayodhya and helped to create the Ganges-Yamuna Doab in the Indo-Gangetic plain, respectively. These rivers are essential to maintaining a sustainable ecosystem.

As water resources are the lifeline of a place, we try to assess the water quality and analyse the precipitation in these areas in this paper. Urban floods have the potential to negatively impact people's quality of life, cause financial losses, and accelerate urban deterioration. However, restoring urban rivers is difficult and typically yields only modest benefits. While improving the city itself, it would be ideal to improve urban fluvial systems, reduce the risk of flooding, and boost city resilience.

This study is based on the secondary data to be collected from the website of Uttar Pradesh Pollution Control Board, Lucknow. This study considers the stretch of these rivers flowing in Uttar Pradesh. For analysis, we consider the data for the year 2022, from January to December. The water quality parameters considered for the study include pH, dissolved oxygen, biochemical oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, total coliform and faecal coliform. These parameters are very important to assess water quality in these rivers. These parameters help us determine the correct pollution scenario in these rivers. The data for all these parameters are available for many locations in Uttar Pradesh, such as 11 sites for Gomti, 22 sites for Ganga, 20 sites for Yamuna and 1 for Saryu.

Moving ahead with this conversation can be made possible by environmental concepts like biodiversity and nature conservation. A further justification stems from the need to improve urban quality of life, considering elements like leisure activities, landscape design, and the social aspects of the interaction between people, water, and cultural heritage. Last but not least, the socioeconomic dimension highlights the possibility that natural ecosystems can

offer a vital foundation for lucrative commercial pursuits like fishing and ecotourism, in addition to high-quality water that requires little treatment, among other opportunities. Well-maintained rivers that are closer to their natural state are likely to require less maintenance or none at all. The complicated relationship between urban land use and the depletion of natural resources is often made worse by this process. Urban water cycles and the reactions of river systems to the built environment are significantly altered by the process of urbanisation.

As biodiversity is decreasing, droughts have also increased. The increase in the earth's heat has increased the water evaporation rate from rivers, lakes, ponds, etc. This, in turn, reduces biodiversity. These environmental hazards have made difficult to maintain a balance between economic activities and environment.

To get a single value of each parameter for each month, we take the average of all the sites for a month. We have applied one-way ANOVA (analysis of variance) for each parameter on the data. One-way ANOVA is a statistical technique used to compare the means of three or more groups that are independent of each other. In the context of the comparative study on the water quality of major rivers of Uttar Pradesh, one-way ANOVA analysis was used to compare the water quality parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen, biochemical oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, total coliform, and fecal coliform for each of the four rivers - Ganga, Gomti, Saryu, and Yamuna. The analysis was conducted to test null hypotheses and predict the quality of water based on the obtained values. The analysis results helped in doing a comparative study between the rivers and assessing their water quality.

Further, these analyses are used to predict the quality based on the value obtained and compare the rivers. We have additionally considered the policies implemented by the government to conserve each river, and the data has helped us analyse the policies' effectiveness. Combining the two ideas of sustainable urban drainage and urban river restoration—can offer a dependable route towards a more long-term fix for urban flooding, along with other advantages. Urban river restoration has the potential to enhance the river's environmental quality and present chances for urban revitalisation. However, it is typically constrained by the significant alterations made to the urban watershed. Actions of the local government and various NGOs can be put together to maintain our ecosystem. The efforts made by various local governments can be replicated by different governments, which may have an overall impact on biodiversity. A combined effort by various agencies can only help us to maintain the ecosystem.

Keywords: Water, Pollution, ANOVA, Gomti

Strategies and Solutions to Promote Sustainable Urban Development in the Era of Urbanisation and Climate Change: A Review

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Global urbanisation is predicted by the United Nations to rise by 66% by 2050, making it extremely difficult for cities to strike a balance between growth and environmental responsibility. Greater economic prosperity and improved living conditions are promised by urbanisation. But growth also brings environmental challenges, such as higher energy consumption, increased transportation needs, higher waste production, impervious surfaces, falling subsurface water levels, reduced water permeability, etc. These elements contribute to climate change, worsen human-wildlife conflicts, degrade habitats, pollute the air and water more heavily, and modify landscapes.

The difficulties posed by urbanisation and climate change to sustainable urban development are significant and call for the development of creative solutions to reduce environmental degradation and improve urban resilience. This study aims to assess the environmental soundness and feasibility of Nature-based Solutions (NbS), such as Blue-Green Infrastructure (BGI). By embracing natural processes and ecosystem principles, NbS offers a route for significant, long-term catastrophic risk mitigation.

The present study delves into the significance of BGI in promoting sustainable urban development in the intricate relationship between urbanisation and climate change. Building resilient and sustainable cities as urban areas continue to grow worldwide is more important than ever.

The study starts by reviewing the leading causes and effects of urbanisation and climate change, highlighting the necessity of using transformational and adaptable urban design strategies. Rapid urbanisation exacerbates the impact of climate change by increasing heat islands, impervious surfaces, and susceptibility to extreme weather events. In light of this, BGI becomes apparent as a multidimensional approach that sustainably addresses urban difficulties by integrating constructed and natural aspects.

The fundamental ideas of BGI are discussed, including how to combine green areas, sustainable urban planning, and water management. Green roofs, Rain gardens, Permeable pavements, Vertical Greening Systems, and urban forests are just a few examples of the components of BGI that may be thoroughly analysed to show how they might improve stormwater management, reduce urban heat islands, and increase total biodiversity in urban areas.

Through a literature study, the review also showcases successful case studies from across the globe that demonstrate how BGI may be applied in various urban environments.

BGI has socio-economic benefits in addition to environmental ones. Creating recreational and artistic areas promotes community engagement, enhances mental and physical health, and may even raise property values. Examining the governance and policy frameworks that facilitate the incorporation of BGI into urban planning procedures is a critical component of this analysis. Adopting BGI and ensuring its long-term viability requires effective local, regional, and national policies. The assessment discusses public-private partnerships, financial incentives, and zoning laws as examples of policies supporting BGI.

Furthermore, the review delves into the possible obstacles and hindrances to the extensive implementation of BGI, including insufficient knowledge, financial limitations, and reluctance to modify. There is a discussion of how to get above these obstacles, focusing on the value of multi-stakeholder cooperation, capacity building, and education. The evaluation also emphasises how innovation and technology have advanced BGI, from data-driven decision-making tools to intelligent water management systems.

The success of the BGI project relies on public-private partnerships and community involvement. BGI reduces heat and pollutants, enhances urban resilience, and promotes social interaction. It also boosts public health by enhancing green spaces and encouraging social interaction. BGI can raise a city's reputation and property prices, offering sustainable urban water management solutions at reasonable costs. Successful implementation requires efficient stakeholder collaboration.

BGI dramatically contributes to the accomplishment of several SDGs. The development of green jobs contributes to reducing poverty (SDG 1) and improving food security (SDG 2) through sustainable land and water management. By ensuring access to clean water (SDG 6) and improving environmental conditions, BGI advances health and well-being (SDG 3). It promotes robust and creative urban infrastructure (SDG 9), Job possibilities increased by returns on investment and entrepreneurship (SDG 8), and the reduction of inequality (SDG 10) via equal access to natural resources. BGI is essential for achieving SDG 11's sustainable urban living, SDG 13's mitigating the effects of climate change, and SDG 14's and SDG 15's conservation of life on land and below water. Adopting BGI is essential for integrated, sustainable urban development in Indian cities, which would help achieve these SDGs.

The review also emphasises how crucial technical innovation and developments are to boost BGI's efficacy and efficiency. This covers the utilisation of smart sensor networks for real-time data collecting and administration, geographic information systems (GIS) for planning and monitoring, and cutting-edge materials for the development of green infrastructure.

With a particular emphasis on the function of BGI, this thorough analysis concludes by synthesising the state of knowledge about tactics and solutions to support sustainable urban development in the face of urbanisation and climate change. It promotes a paradigm change in urban planning and policymaking by highlighting the necessity of integrated, holistic methods that consider the social, economic, and environmental aspects. BGI is a flexible and comprehensive strategy that improves urban areas' overall resilience and liveability while addressing environmental issues. To promote and implement BGI and eventually help create resilient, sustainable, and liveable urban settings for future generations, the review urges for more awareness, research, and collaborative efforts among governments, businesses, academia, and communities. The assessment advocates for the broad adoption of BGI as a crucial component in the development of sustainable and climate-resilient cities for future generations, calling for a paradigm change in urban planning and policymaking.

Keywords: Urbanisation, Climate Change, Nature-based solution, Blue-Green infrastructure

Effect of Climate Change on Liveability: A Case of Delhi

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Cities are a living entity that evolves to represent the community it serves. The traits of the most well-known city change over time though the factors that influence it are slow and merely visible. The changes include the physical, social and environmental aspects that have an irreversible influence on the standard of living. For any region to become a city, a significant transformation from rural to urban changes the population and regional dynamics. As urbanisation spreads, it comes with a cost that eventually has an impact on people's lives in the form of social security, employment opportunities, living standards, and much more. Cities become the epicentre of growth and environmental degradation all at once.

It was rightly said by Jay Inslee "We are the first generation to feel the impact of climate change and the last generation that can do something about it." In this century, climate change and urbanisation are two major terminologies that are intensely interlinked to each other. Cities often behave as 'resource-hungry beasts' that gulp up the major share of energy, food, water, etc and the desire to acquire more seems to have no end. When this situation is complemented by other factors like urban heat islands, limited vegetation, traffic congestion, high population density, etc., climate change's effect scales up to an unimaginable level. Due to these factors, an imbalance occurs leading to an unpredictable set of disasters. This justifies that there is no such thing as 'natural disasters' and it is most often human-induced (e.g. there is nothing natural about the rise of greenhouse gas emissions). Major disasters that strike at a global and Indian level include floods, droughts, heat waves, earthquakes, air pollution, sea-level rise, etc.

Cities are not formed by accident. It's the people who add meaning to the spaces in a city. Liveable cities focus on providing a balance between recreation, work and a sustainable environment. The notion of liveability is very subjective and differs based on age, income, family size, and personal preferences, so it doesn't follow a one-size-fits-all approach. Liveability is all about having a city that benefits all by putting their needs first. The common factor that binds and affects everybody is quality of life.

The liveability of any city is highly dependent on the impact of climate change which eventually threatens the foundation of liveability. Climate change has various effects, the most prominent being extreme weather events. This is called the ripple effect where both don't seem to exist in isolation. In this paper, it is attempted to explore the relationship between liveability and climate change. In this process of exploration, various ill effects of climate change are identified. Among the concerns is rising temperatures leading to heat waves and urban heat islands that pose a threat to low-income communities, migrants, the elderly, people with ailments and street animals, which results in outdoor discomfort or even fatalities. The next problem that the cities encounter is urban flooding due to heavy rainfall, increased use of hardscapes and pavements and reduced green spaces leading to infrastructure damage, migration, loss of lives, and disrupted transportation system, each of these leaving a shadow on the basic lifestyle of the people. The third main issue is air pollution due to increased energy consumption, emissions from vehicles, and stubble burning resulting in increased greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) all eventually leading to respiratory problems and other health issues affecting the well-being of the city dwellers. The next issue is droughts which contribute to wildfires leading to loss of lives and biodiversity, reduced air quality and hazardous living conditions. The last concern is the sea-level rise which forces an existential threat on the coastal communities due to flooding, saltwater intrusion, and imbalance of the marine ecosystem all of which affect their lives and their livelihood.

It is observable that when a disaster strikes, it is often accompanied by allied events. The best example is Delhi's Earthquake along with the dip in air quality to the 'severe plus' category that occurred in November 2023. The irony was that people were evacuating from buildings due to tremors and returning indoors due to the extremely poor quality of air. Other examples in the Indian scenario include combinations like 'drought-urban flooding', 'drought-heat waves-wildfires', and 'urban flooding-landslides'. To reduce the influence of such a lethal combination of disasters, there is an immediate need to find the best solutions for mitigating the climate change impacts.

This study investigates several possibilities to mitigate the ill effects of climate change by realising the recent trends and their impact on the liveability of Delhi through a systematic literature review and various secondary sources. The methodology includes various stages like data collection on climate change and its impacts, identifying patterns in climate change impacts through literature case studies, understanding challenges and opportunities, and existing climate change mitigation and liveability enhancement efforts.

Keywords: Climate Change, Liveability, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Mitigation measures

Nature's Symphony: Crafting a Carbon-Neutral Tomorrow through Technological Ingenuity in the Nilgiris Biosphere Reserve

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“Climate change is the prolonged alteration of Earth’s average temperatures and weather patterns, primarily driven by human activities. This results in a range of impacts and disruptions to ecosystems, biodiversity, 1 and human health, as evidenced by intense extreme weather events and changes in global, regional, and local climates.” Similarly, “Carbon neutrality balances emitted greenhouse gases with removal or offset, achieving a net-zero carbon footprint through reduction, sequestration, and careful carbon balance.” Combining these concepts, “Climate change and carbon neutrality form a comprehensive strategy addressing human-induced climate challenges. While climate change underscores the impact, carbon neutrality provides a proactive solution with a net-zero carbon footprint, ensuring a sustainable and balanced future.”, derived on the basis of looking into various definitions from famous institutions.

The Western Ghats, a mountain range in India that plays a significant role, is well-known for the vast biodiversity and ecological value it possesses. The Nilgiris, which is among these ranges, play a significant part in determining India’s climate and in providing support for a wide variety of habitats. The fragile balance of the Nilgiris is currently at risk due to the combined impact of climate change and carbon emissions. This is despite the fact that the Nilgiris carry a significant ecological significance. The Nilgiris Biosphere Reserve, which was India’s first biosphere to be awarded the designation, is being confronted with issues brought about by climate change and rising carbon emissions. There is a deterioration in the deep interconnection of ecosystems, which brings about a disruption in the delicate equilibrium that has supported life in the region for several centuries. Taking into consideration the pressing need to comprehend and address these difficulties, this study was conducted.

The Nilgiris district, which constitutes the Nilgiris Biosphere Reserve, serves as a storehouse for the diverse array of life that can be found in India. As a result of changes in the environment, the region’s distinctive plant and animal species are confronted with considerable challenges, which threaten the delicate ecological balance that is characteristic of the region. The lush greenery and diversified ecosystems of the Nilgiris are being negatively impacted by environmental deterioration, which is being driven by shifting weather patterns and disruptions to the region’s biological equilibrium. Vulnerabilities are made worse by climate change, which results in altered patterns of precipitation, greater temperatures, and a decrease in the populations of native animals. Given the complex interplay between climate change and the sophisticated ecological balance that has evolved over thousands of years, the study emphasises the urgent necessity to fully tackle the challenges currently confronting the district.

This study provides a comprehensive examination of the difficulties faced by the district, with the goal of revealing the complex network of problems, including disturbances in weather patterns and risks to biodiversity. The main contribution of this proposal is to suggest a new strategy that cleverly integrates advanced technology, such as artificial intelligence, renewable energy systems, and smart infrastructure, into the process of achieving sustainable urban development. The core of this strategy is the ambitious objective of guiding the district towards a future marked by carbon neutrality, surpassing mere recognition of emissions to actively achieving a balance between emissions and their elimination or compensation. In addition to its specific geographical area of interest, the study considers the Nilgiris as a potential exemplar for worldwide sustainable development, capable of inspiring similar endeavours internationally. The paper’s statements are supported by a rigorous methodology, which includes

systematic literature reviews conducted at several levels. This approach ensures a comprehensive awareness of the current trends, difficulties, and possibilities. The results include a perceptive comprehension of current patterns, a subtle recognition of complex difficulties, and the expression of strategies to achieve sustainable development. This article not only analyses but also recommends a cutting-edge and visionary plan, establishing the Nilgiris as a model for international efforts to address climate change and promote environmental adaptability.

A comprehensive systematic literature analysis at the global, national, and local levels is included in the study process. The purpose of this review is to gain an understanding of the current trends, issues, and possibilities. One of the outputs is the formation of strategies for sustainable development, as well as insights into the current situation of the Nilgiris. Other outcomes include the identification of critical challenges. The research offers a sustainable basis for urban growth by incorporating cutting-edge technologies, community involvement, and environmental stewardship into the planning process. In order to ensure the long-term durability of technological solutions, it places an emphasis on the significance of community involvement in the planning and implementation of these solutions. In order to provide a thorough picture of the issues that the district is currently facing, the research investigates contemporary trends connected to climate change, carbon emissions, and sustainable development from a variety of perspectives. The study outlines a way forward for the Nilgiris, which involves combining technology breakthroughs and community cooperation in order to establish itself as a leader in sustainable development. This would be a substantial contribution to worldwide programs that are focused at minimising the effects of climate change.

By Recognising the intricate relationship that exists between climate change and ecological equilibrium, the Nilgiris have the ability to not only ameliorate the environmental problems that they are currently facing, but also to become a model for sustainable development on a global scale. The comprehensive approach integrates environmental stewardship, community empowerment, and technological advancements, guaranteeing a sustainable future and supporting global initiatives to safeguard the planet for future generations.

Keywords: Climate change mitigation, Carbon neutrality, Nilgiris Hill station, Sustainable development

An Integrated Framework for Assessment of Impact of Urban Flooding Considering Environmental and Urban Features

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Climate change accompanied by rapid growth of cities leading to developed catchments, increases the flood peaks and flood volumes. Along with meteorological and hydrological factors, human factors contribute significantly to urban flooding. Urban flooding is the inundation of land or property in a built environment, particularly in more densely populated areas, caused by rainfall overwhelming the capacity of drainage systems, such as storm sewers. Flooding disasters in cities with dense population and centres of economic activities are having devastating impacts on human life, mobility, and the collapse of urban infrastructure. Although sometimes triggered by events such as flash flooding or snowmelt, urban flooding is a condition, characterised by its repetitive and systemic impacts on communities, that can happen regardless of whether affected communities are located within designated floodplains or near any body of water. Aside from potential overflow of rivers and lakes, stormwater, or water released from damaged water mains may accumulate on property and in public rights-of-way, seep through building walls and floors, or back up into buildings through sewer pipes, toilets, and sinks.

Although the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) has made efforts to prepare the National Guidelines on Management of Urban Flooding, there is a need for cause analysis, appropriate risk assessment of flood, and mapping flood risk urban areas augmented with digital technology to devise specific plans and strategies. This involves large data and parametrisations, where conventional hydrological methods fall short in providing appropriate flood risk assessment to take effective action. Flood severity is analysed by considering the hydrological parameters like, the amount of received rainfall (precipitation), duration of rainfall, pervious/impervious surface, soil moisture, time to accumulate, and topological features of the river surroundings. Multicriteria decision-making

methods need to be integrated with automated digital systems and linked with Information Communication Technology (ICT) to develop a digital platform that will enable mitigation of urban flooding and rapidly respond to disaster incidents.

Disaster Management Support (DMS) Programme, comprehensively addresses various aspects of natural disasters in the country, using space-based inputs. Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) disseminates relevant information in the interactive geo-spatial domain through various geoportals like Bhuvan, National Database for Emergency Management, and MOSDAC for the administrators to better understand the impact and for improved decision support. ISRO provides satellite-based near real-time information support to Central Ministries / Departments and State Ministries / Departments, before, during, and after major natural disasters. In addition, ISRO also provides capacity building in the use of Space technology inputs in Disaster Management Support.

Flood modelling is often conducted in a very localised fashion, with hydrological models created for individual municipalities and incorporating details about buildings, infrastructure, vegetation, land use, and drainage systems. An integration of localised hydrological modelling with larger-scale climate modelling allows the benefits of both forms of modelling to be realised simultaneously and creates the potential for modelling flooding due to climate change in a way that allows planners to design specific strategies to mitigate it at the local level. From understanding flood hazard and flood impacts there are known and tested measures for urban flood risk management, typically classified as structural or engineered measures, and non-structural, management techniques. A combination of measures to form an integrated management approach is most likely to be successful in reducing flood risk. Climate uncertainty and budgetary, institutional, and practical constraints are likely to lead to a combining of structural and non-structural measures for urban flood risk management.

This paper discusses the concepts, causes, impacts, and assessment methods for evaluating urban flooding scenarios. Further, the paper highlights the factors that are influential in causing flood vulnerability conditions in urban areas. The flood risk indicators are categorised under Geo-environmental and urban factors that can systematically evaluate urban flooding scenarios. The land use segmentation of Satellite images is the first step in any Flood Modelling using GIS techniques. Runoff conditions vary considerably among different land use and land cover patterns. Analysing DEM helps to delineate the watersheds to map water flows and possible flood patterns. Hydrological modelling based on multiple data inputs combined with multiple layers of Geo-Spatial data of Urban landscape can lead to accurate modelling and prediction of flash floods in Urban areas and associated damage. Geo-environmental indicators: slope aspect, elevation, slope angle, soil, rainfall, curve number, and urban feature indicators: Land use/land cover, distance to urban drainage, urban drainage density, and road conditions form the structural construct of the model to predict urban flooding scenarios. The paper presents a framework for creating a Digital platform for ingesting and aggregating data on flood risk indicators from various connected systems, which can be analysed to enable an effective response to Urban flooding and disaster management along with simulating flash flood scenarios and climate impact for future growth of urban areas and development of urban infrastructures. With a combined analysis of hydrology and transportation infrastructure, the proposed methods could further help to reduce traffic congestion during flood seasons, facilitate early warning, and assist users in making informed travel decisions.

Keywords: Urban flooding, Climate Change, Rainfall, Land use, Land cover

Evaluation of the Resilience Index of Cities in the Global South: A Case Study of Bhubaneswar in Odisha, India

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The impacts of climate change are currently being experienced worldwide, including extreme weather events, rising temperatures, and disruptions to ecosystems that affect millions globally. The disruption and loss are in acute in urban environments, where the interplay of rapid urbanisation, and climate change exerts additional strain on urban infrastructure and services, laying bare existing vulnerabilities.

Numerous studies project that by 2030, 40% of India's population will be residing in its cities. Yet, India ranks fifth in terms of vulnerability in the Global Climate Risk Index. The rapid population growth outsmarts the corresponding pace of development of infrastructure, especially in the case of the non-Tier-I cities. The relentless pace of urbanisation in smaller metropolitans coupled with the increasing frequency and intensity of climate-related shocks, enhances their susceptibility to disasters such as floods, earthquakes, and heatwaves. Thus, strategic urban planning to ensure sustainable development and resilience in the face of these multifaceted challenges. The Global Climate Risk Index highlights the need for instant action to protect cities from future calamities and the need to create resilient urban environments that can withstand and bounce back from unforeseen catastrophes. This sense of urgency results from the need to strategically shape urban environments to ensure the long-term safety and well-being of urban people, in addition to responding to current risks.

A crucial tool for assessing a city's capacity to deal with and adjust to unforeseen catastrophes is the Resilience Index. It is essential for urban development since it integrates several elements to provide a thorough picture of a city's capacity to withstand disruptions. It is a valuable resource for communities, local authorities, and legislators, allowing individuals to identify gaps, organise focused initiatives, and promote sustainable development. The index assesses the Absorptive Capacity, the Adaptive Capacity, and the Transformative Capacity of cities to determine a city's level of resilience. Absorptive Capacity assesses a city's ability to withstand shocks. It examines immediate response mechanisms and recovery strategies to demonstrate their effectiveness during an occurrence of any kind of unforeseen circumstances. Adaptive capacity examines a city's receptiveness. It focuses on a city's ability to dynamically respond to evolving circumstances, fostering a culture of continuous learning and adaptability. The Transformative Capacity emphasises a city's ability to make significant adjustments to address issues and guarantee long-term sustainability. Thus, the current study develops a Resilience Index for the city of Bhubaneswar in Odisha, India to systematically assess its capacity to withstand, adapt to, and recover from various shocks and stresses associated with natural disasters.

Bhubaneswar is the capital of the state of Odisha in India, and the largest city in the state. Estimated to be housing a population of 1,289,254 in 2024, Bhubaneswar is one of the most rapidly growing cities in the country. Additionally, with the status of being a smart city, the population migration into the city heaves immense pressure on the urban infrastructure. The state of Odisha as a whole, and Bhubaneswar is susceptible to cyclonic risks. In the last two decades, 10 of the deadliest cyclones in the country have hit Odisha, and the damage to life and property has been immense. A resilience index framework for Bhubaneswar is thus being developed as part of this study to evaluate the city's readiness for cyclonic disasters as well as its ability to recover from these events. The major aim of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of urban services, identify areas of weakness, and gauge the adaptiveness of the local communities. A detailed study on risk assessment has also been conducted to understand the effects of the natural disaster on the city's economy, infrastructure, and social structure. The findings of this evaluation may serve as a basis for focused initiatives meant to increase the city's resistance to cyclonic disasters. In conclusion, the study highlights the critical need to enhance Bhubaneswar's mitigation and recovery strategies for strengthening resilience against the impacts of cyclonic hazards, and thus fostering sustainable development.

Keywords: Resilience Index, Risk Assessment, Cyclone, Vulnerability

Assessing the Spatio-temporal Variability in Land Use and its Impact on Land Surface Temperature Using Geospatial Techniques

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Urbanisation, a defining characteristic of the modern era, has ushered in profound changes in land use patterns, catalysing a global concern—the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. This study seeks to address the urgency of the situation, examining the intricate relationship between land use changes, UHI intensification, and the broader implications of rapid urbanisation on environmental dynamics.

At the heart of this exploration is the utilisation of Geographic Information System (GIS) as a pivotal tool. GIS emerges as an indispensable mechanism for comprehensively assessing the UHI effect, offering a systematic approach to understanding the spatio-temporal variations in land use. In doing so, it unveils a holistic perspective on the dynamics of UHI and its interplay with urban growth. Remote Sensing Indices, namely the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI), and Normalised Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), stand as cornerstones in this geospatial analysis.

As urban landscapes transform and natural elements give way to concrete jungles, the urgency to understand the consequences on urban climates becomes paramount. This study embarks on a multidimensional approach, incorporating additional parameters such as Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) changes, surface heat dynamics, and Landsat imagery. These elements collectively contribute to a comprehensive exploration of the intricate relationships between land use changes and their direct impact on land surface temperature.

The primary aim of the project is to evaluate the relationship between UHI and land use changes, specifically induced by urban expansion. This objective aligns with the broader motivation of the study, emanating from the pivotal role urban planners play in shaping the trajectory of urban development. The negative consequences of rapid urbanisation, characterised by the loss of natural vegetation, disappearance of water bodies, and the expansion of built-up areas, demand urgent attention.

In selecting Visakhapatnam as the case study, the research strategically addresses the impact of rapid urbanisation on UHI dynamics. Visakhapatnam, experiencing significant population growth and conversion of natural lands into urbanised landscapes, serves as a representative model for understanding the challenges posed by urban growth. The study seeks to provide actionable insights for urban planners and policymakers in Visakhapatnam, fostering informed decision-making for sustainable urban development.

In the process of selecting Visakhapatnam as the study area, a rigorous and systematic approach was undertaken, leveraging various surveys and data collection methods. Four distinct zones within the city municipality area were identified, characterised by exceptionally high land temperatures. These zones were not only marked by elevated temperatures but also had a consistent presence of heat hotspots over the past five years. To gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of these temperature variations on residents and their perspectives, household surveys were conducted in these identified zones.

The household surveys were instrumental in elucidating the thoughts and experiences of the residents regarding the increasing land temperatures. The surveys delved into the ways in which residents perceived the temperature changes, how it affected their daily lives, and their overall concerns regarding the escalating urban heat conditions. This qualitative data proved to be invaluable in capturing the nuanced human dimension of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect.

Simultaneously, extensive data collection efforts were directed towards municipal offices, where a wealth of information on urban heat islands was gathered. The municipal office served as a repository of insights into the existing conditions of UHI in Visakhapatnam and the strategies that the Urban Local Body (ULB) had in place or planned to implement in order to address this environmental challenge.

As the research delves into the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect, the study aims to provide insights that empower urban planners to develop strategies mitigating the adverse effects of unplanned urban growth. UHI, a complex phenomenon rooted in the alteration of surface temperature dynamics due to urbanisation, manifests as elevated land surface temperatures in urban cores. These changes not only impact surface energy balance but also induce changes in local climate dynamics.

Geospatial techniques, anchored by GIS, form the backbone of this study. Remote Sensing Indices serve as a lens into the density of green on land, offering insights into the health of urban vegetation. The Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) highlights water features, while the Normalised Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) maps built-up areas. These components collectively contribute to unravelling the evolving urban landscape.

In conclusion, the study underscores the critical need for proactive measures in mitigating the adverse effects of UHI associated with urbanisation. By employing GIS and assessing various components, the research aims to equip stakeholders with valuable information to formulate effective strategies for sustainable urban planning. The findings of this study, particularly in the context of Visakhapatnam, are poised to contribute significantly to

the broader discourse on balancing urban development with environmental well-being. As cities grapple with the challenges of unchecked growth, informed decision-making and strategic planning become imperative for creating urban spaces that are both vibrant and sustainable.

Keywords: Land surface temperature, NDWI, NDBI, NDVI

Tourism Surge and Vulnerable Infrastructure: A Comprehensive Study of Manali, Himachal Pradesh

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The impact of tourism on a city is a subject of growing significance in contemporary urban studies. As global travel trends continue to surge, cities worldwide grapple with tourism's complex ramifications on their socioeconomic fabric, environment, and cultural identity. The influx of visitors can catalyse economic growth, offering business opportunities and job creation, yet it also poses challenges such as congestion, resource strain, and cultural commodification. This research delves into the multifaceted impact of tourism on a city, seeking to unravel the intricate relationships between economic development, environmental sustainability, and the well-being of local communities. By understanding these dynamics, the study aims to contribute valuable insights to urban planning and policy-making, fostering a balanced and sustainable approach to managing the effects of tourism on the urban landscape.

Tourism plays a crucial role in the economy; however, a rise in visitor numbers can pose challenges if the city fails to manage crowds effectively. While we possess sufficient evidence to demonstrate the positive effects of increased foot traffic, there are also negative impacts that necessitate further study. The economic effects of the growing tourism in Manali are readily apparent, yet the city has frequently experienced disorderly situations due to mismanagement, particularly in traffic, accommodation, and overcrowding. This paper aims to explore the consequences of the surge in foot traffic, considering both the positive and negative aspects. Utilising a case study method, the research thoroughly investigates the economic, environmental, and socio-cultural dimensions linked to the upswing in tourism.

When examining the economic ramifications, the research explores the impact of increased tourist numbers on the local economy, influencing businesses, employment prospects, and income distribution. At the same time, it examines the environmental impact of heightened tourism, closely analysing challenges like resource strain, waste management, and ecological sustainability.

The objective is to highlight the importance of taking proactive measures to reduce risks linked with Construction in these regions. This includes ensuring the safety of residents and tourists and preserving the natural environment. The study goes beyond merely identifying issues; it provides practical insights and recommendations for sustainable tourism practices. The overarching aim is to achieve a harmonious balance between economic growth, environmental preservation, and social responsibility within the changing tourism scenario of Manali.

Manali stands out as an exemplary case study, particularly due to its significant impact from tourism post-COVID. Its proximity to Delhi consistently fuels an increase in tourism activities. Endowed with stunning landscapes adorned with snow-capped mountains and lush greenery, Manali has evolved into a prime tourist destination, drawing a diverse range of visitors. Nevertheless, the upswing in tourism, contributing to economic prosperity, concurrently introduces challenges, including strain on infrastructure and apprehensions regarding hotel construction in areas vulnerable near the riverbank.

A critical aspect of the research is the scrutiny of structures proliferating in areas near the riverbank, which poses significant risks during disasters. This issue brings attention to the urgent need for safety and planning considerations in the context of tourism-related developments in Manali. The primary objective of the research is to dissect the dynamics of increased tourism and the subsequent development of lodging facilities in locations

susceptible to natural disasters. While acknowledging the economic importance of tourism in the region, the study critically evaluates the potential risks and consequences associated with expanding accommodation infrastructure in vulnerable zones.

The examination investigates safety and security issues associated with building hotels in disaster-prone regions, evaluating the readiness of both residents and visiting tourists when confronted with natural disasters. By untangling the complex interplay between tourism development, the Construction of accommodations, and the resilience of the local community, the study aims to offer a thorough comprehension of the challenges and opportunities in the evolving tourism landscape of Manali.

The study provides significant insights for urban planning, policy development, and decision-making. It supports a comprehensive development strategy that places emphasis on the safety and well-being of both residents and visitors in Manali. This approach aims to find a harmonious equilibrium between economic growth fuelled by tourism and the region's cultural and environmental sustainability. The primary objective is to present practical recommendations for sustainable tourism practices, underscoring the significance of proactive measures to mitigate risks linked to Construction in vulnerable areas.

This research can give us a fair idea about the comprehensive understanding of tourism's multifaceted effects on the city. Anticipated outcomes include insights into the economic repercussions, environmental implications, and socio-cultural dynamics associated with increased tourism. The research aims to provide valuable data and analysis to inform urban planning, policy formulation, and decision-making processes. Additionally, the project seeks to offer practical recommendations for sustainable tourism practices, promoting a balanced approach that ensures both economic growth and the well-being of the city's residents and the preservation of its natural and cultural assets. Ultimately, the expected outcome is to contribute meaningful information that can guide responsible and resilient urban development in the face of growing tourism.

Keywords: Tourism impact, Ecological sustainability, Disaster-prone areas, Resilience, Responsible urban development

Breath of the City: Unmasking the Air - A Dive into the Microcosm of Bhubaneswar's Vulnerable Zones

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The proliferation of industrialization, globalization, and transportation, concomitant with the pollution-induced developmental exploitation of non-renewable resources such as coal, petroleum, and natural gas, has precipitated the degradation of our natural environment, thereby imparting significant implications on both the physical and mental well-being of individuals, while concurrently disrupting the climatic equilibrium. The surge in population has engendered the over-exploitation of resources, giving rise to substantial negative externalities that are frequently overlooked by administrative authorities. The escalating costs associated with pollution are increasingly burdensome, causing adverse repercussions on human well-being. This research endeavours to systematically investigate air quality, focusing on the concentrations of PM 2.5/10, NO₂, SO₂, CO₂, among other pollutants, across various vulnerable locations in Bhubaneswar. The objective is to elucidate their impacts on both human populations and the environment. Subsequently, the study aims to propose point-source induced mitigation measures with the goal of fostering climate-resilient and sustainable urban development, thereby promoting public health and welfare. Site selection is conducted based on criteria encompassing population density, industrial activities, traffic patterns, and socio-economic factors. Air quality is systematically monitored through the deployment of air quality monitors, meteorological stations, and comprehensive surveys. Rigorous adherence to established air quality parameters and permissible concentration levels is maintained throughout the formulation of pollutant presence in the atmosphere. The assessment of air samples employs both continuous and periodic sampling methodologies, accompanied by meticulous quality control measures. These measures include instrument calibration, the implementation of standard operating procedures, and regular scrutiny to ensure the precision and accuracy of measurements. The data analysis encompasses a rigorous application of

descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and spatial analysis, employing Geographic Information Systems (GIS) alongside other pertinent analytical tools. Ethical considerations integral to the study include the meticulous acquisition of informed consent from participants, the safeguarding of privacy, and a steadfast commitment to ensuring the welfare of individuals within the designated study area. The ensuing data analysis and interpretation of diverse trends in air quality across disparate locations serve as the foundation for formulating comprehensive recommendations within the scope of this scholarly paper. In enhancing the paper's utility and facilitating a comprehensive survey on air quality, a meticulously crafted questionnaire has been devised. This instrument systematically addresses pertinent aspects, including participants' perceptions of air quality, the discernible health impacts, levels of awareness and knowledge, considerations of mitigation measures, and potential behavioural changes. Notably, this scholarly inquiry distinguishes itself from antecedent research endeavours on air quality in Bhubaneswar by extending its focus beyond the overall Air Quality Index (AQI). Emphasis is placed on the critical aspects of point-source apportionment and the identification of potentially vulnerable communities, with particular attention directed towards children and women. Considerable emphasis was directed towards quantifying the influence on air quality in close proximity to street vendors in Bhubaneswar, with a particular focus on comprehending the challenges they encounter due to prolonged exposure to air pollution resulting from cooking activities. Employing GPS technology and air-quality monitoring instruments, a continuous assessment of the dynamic fluctuations in air quality was meticulously conducted while traversing along the array of street food stalls. Observations indicate a prevailing trend among individuals partaking in street food consumption to stand in proximity to the food vendors, prompting an assessment of the resultant impact on their health through a comprehensive review of relevant literature. In the course of this research endeavour, collaborative assistance was sought from the State Pollution Control Board to precisely ascertain pollution sources. The timing of the research, conducted during the winter season, is pivotal, as results indicate an elevation in air pollution levels during this period, attributed to factors such as heightened pollutant entrapment in cold air masses, temperature inversion phenomena, increased emissions, and the prevalence of dry air conditions. The paper introduces several nature-based strategies aimed at mitigating air quality concerns in diverse locations, underscoring key concepts such as Urban Greening, the establishment of green roofs and walls to effectively filter harmful gases and capture particulate matter, the restoration of ecosystems encompassing soil and urban water bodies, the advocacy for active mobility, the delineation of low emission zones, and the application of photocatalytic coatings on roads and buildings to facilitate the breakdown of specific airborne pollutants. Additionally, it underscores the pivotal role of efficient waste management in influencing the air quality of a given locale. Recognizing the intrinsic interconnectedness of Air Quality Index (AQI) dynamics, the paper posits that its impact transcends individuality, exerting profound implications on a state's tourism rates and the frequency of recreational outdoor activities. A heightened AQI is demonstrated to potentially trigger diverse regulatory interventions, including advisories, restrictions on specific activities, or the implementation of pollution control measures. This, in turn, disrupts the societal fabric, impeding normalcy and stalling the trajectory of growth and development, as observed prominently in urban centres such as Delhi and other states in India. Individually, mitigation of Air Quality Index (AQI) can be achieved through conscientious practices, including the utilization of public transportation and adopting fuel-efficient driving habits to mitigate vehicular emissions. Additionally, energy conservation is advocated through the use of energy-efficient appliances and the judicious powering down of electronic devices. Strategies to reduce indoor pollution encompass proper ventilation measures and the limitation of indoor burning activities. Implementing effective waste management practices to curtail the release of pollutants from waste sites is crucial. Furthermore, endorsing eco-friendly initiatives, such as tree planting, vegetation maintenance, and the preservation of green spaces in urban areas, serves as a natural filtration mechanism for air quality improvement. Individuals are encouraged to cultivate an awareness of and advocacy for change by actively monitoring local air quality. Embracing sustainable energy consumption practices, particularly through the incorporation of solar and wind power, coupled with the upgrading of home installations and appliances to minimize energy consumption and emissions, represents a pivotal avenue for fostering positive environmental impact. Moreover, a shift towards electric and hybrid vehicles is advocated, underpinned by the dissemination of awareness through word-of-mouth communication and community initiatives.

Keywords: AQI, Sampling, Environment, GIS, Mitigation, SPCB

TRACK- 4: SUSTAINABLE SETTLEMENT PLANNING AND DEVELOPMENT

This track answers the urban, peri-urban, and rural landscape questions and their dynamics. What is the role of migration in shaping cities? What are the dynamics of the city region? What are the challenges in sustainable settlement planning and approaches? It explores the rural-urban linkages and livelihood perspective. This track is further divided into the following sub-themes:

- Dynamics of urban, peri-urban, and rural landscapes
- Rural-Urban migration: Impact and management
- Settlement planning and sustainable land use
- Rural-urban linkages and its dynamics in development

Framing Settlement Plan and Sustainable Land Use Policies for Cities in Mountain Terrain

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Cities and towns have become ubiquitous units of settlement. The transition areas between urban areas and countryside have become wide. Rural depopulation, increasing threshold to maintain services and provisioning of amenities have acted as push factors. Growing aspirations, visible changes in urban infrastructure, increasing additions of urban amenities and functions, progress in smart city initiatives, better and diverse occupational choices, etc. have acted as pull factor for the growth of cities in rugged and mountainous terrain areas.

Itanagar was established in 1974 as an administrative town. In 1978 the offices were shifted to Itanagar from Naharlagun and started functioning as State Capital. It was then had only Government office buildings and Government quarters for the staffs and personnel. By 1990s some business establishments, few private residential units were built. Transport and communication were big hurdles for mobility. However, there was no defined boundary of Itanagar town as there was no municipality jurisdiction till 2007. Subsequent to notification of Arunachal Pradesh Municipality Act in 2009, the rule forward delimitation in Arunachal Pradesh was notified 2010. Arunachal Pradesh Reservation of Urban Land for Housing of Urban Poor Rules was notified in 2011. In 2018, The Arunachal Pradesh (Land Settlement and Records) (Amendment) Bill, was introduced that allowed lease of land to non-natives for a period of 30 years which is renewable for another 30 years.

Focus to develop the township municipality has increased, ensuing with inclusion of Itanagar in the list of smart-cities, has resulted in boosting the growth of cityscape, both horizontally and vertically. This continued trend of expansion due to influx of people to reside in the city not only generated huge demand of land but also induced skyrocketing land prices, occupying vulnerable and disaster-prone areas in the mountain terrain. The Directorate of Town Planning, Government of Arunachal Pradesh, has prepared a Final Draft for Arunachal Pradesh Building Byelaws covering many facets for : i) Development code pertaining to residential and non-residential premises; ii) General building requirements; iii) Conservation of heritage sites including heritage buildings, heritage precincts and natural feature areas; iv) Additional provisions in development control regulations for safety in natural hazard prone areas; v) Additional provisions in building byelaws for structural safety in natural hazard-prone areas; vi) Integrated township; vii) Multi-story buildings and group housing schemes'/apartments' additional requirements. This is a good plan on paper but remained un-implemented due to various reasons.

As the city is located on the Siwaliks, heavy dissection of land has left only few and narrow water divides as best and most suitable areas for habitation. Current scenario has surpassed the capacity to accommodate new houses. Topographic parameters like altitude and its deviation from regional trend, slope, aspect, curvature, distance from stream, topographic wetness index and topographic position when studied as guiding natural factors have been found to be crucial and critical in understanding vulnerability associated with buildings in the municipality area. Soil in the Siwalik region of the Himalayas is uniformly formed out of unconsolidated aggregates with high permeability pose threat to sinking and landslide. In many cases, the setbacks of buildings have been prominently absent, or being destroyed by earth cutting by owners in the down-slope areas.

The topographic parameters, have been evaluated for vulnerability assessment, building density have been derived using Normalised Difference Building Index (NDBI), Actual plan of city infrastructure, Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) have been used and modeled to assess the growth of Itanagar City and assess areas of recent expansions. Ward nos. 11, 6, 16, 4, 14 and 10 are those which have more than 10 percent its area is used for buildings only, with 19.70, 18.68, 16.43, 12.89, 12.39 and 10.77 percent respectively. Besides these other impervious areas are responsible for interfering with surface drainage of rainwater. Sewage systems are also inadequate and overflow during high intensity rainfall period. The Land surface temperature is higher at the local ridges used for settlements. An assessment of vulnerability has been worked out. The recent experiences during monsoon are alarming and there is a need to implement the bylaws for safe housing and buildings, develop a robust futuristic urban land use plan in tandem with the smart-city framework.

As per survey results of Itanagar, the buildings are clustered and unplanned in their layout. Wards Nos. like 7 and

14 have the highest number of buildings, i.e. above 700. Ward No. 2 has the least number of buildings, i.e. 34. This excludes huts as dwelling units. Ward-wise building concentration is high in 11 and 16, where per hectare there are more than 20 buildings. These two are part of the area of early settling of the township. When the buildings are clustered around some favourable patches, building density goes up thereby putting a lot of constraints on urban amenities and facilities. It also adds to vulnerability and reduced safety standards. Thus, there is a strong need to regulate unplanned growth and expansion of Itanagar Town. Five and above storied buildings have become recent phenomenon. Unless proactive action and regulations are put in place serious repercussions may follow.

Keywords: Smart city framework, Mountain terrain, Vulnerability assessment, Urban land use plan

Urban Built-Up Expansion, Land Fragmentation and Sustainability Paradox: Analysing the Sprawl of Siliguri City, West Bengal with Geospatial Techniques

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As urbanisation continues to grow worldwide, the exploration, understanding, and management of urban built-up land tend to become progressively crucial matters of concern in the realms of research, policy development, practice as well as activism. Urban sprawl has been a keyword in the history of studies on how the spatial pattern of urban built-up growth has been conceived and addressed, and thus, is firmly associated with the concerns on sustainability and resilience. Furthermore, studies grounded on the analysis of urban sprawl has been significantly transformed in the last few decades with the wide availability of remotely sensed data in public domain and the emergence of Geographic Information Science (GIS). Despite the emergence of decision-support tools like remote sensing and GIS, addressing urban sprawl in order to inform the task of spatial policymaking, has been a complex challenge that cannot be effectively tackled using a single method. Therefore, a combination of approaches is necessary to deal with such non-linear phenomenon in any spatial context.

The present study endeavours to understand and detect the territorial transformations encompassing Siliguri, the third largest city of West Bengal, India, over a period of two decades (2001-2021), through an integrated remote sensing-GIS approach. The city of Siliguri, popularly known as the 'gateway to the north-eastern India', is said to be famous for 4 'T's': Tea, Timber, Tourism and Transport. Siliguri, has been recorded as the most rapidly growing urban agglomeration of West Bengal with a decadal population growth rate of 46% between 2001 and 2011. However, due to a lack of statutory planning regulations, the extraordinary population growth of Siliguri has gone along with uncontrolled built-up expansion around the city, which in turn is associated with a host of environmental and social challenges. Siliguri's spatial association with Shiwalik region of Eastern Himalayas and dense forested tracts of Bengal Tarai further contributes to the concerns on the unplanned built-up expansion of the city and its environmental externalities.

From methodological standpoint, the present research draws on the geo-spatially grounded quantitative methods like Urban Expansion Intensity Index (UEII), Shannon's entropy, Landscape Expansion Index (LEI) and Landscape Metrics (LM) to quantify and address the non-linear pattern of urban spatial growth in and around Siliguri city. Accordingly, the research addresses the following questions with respect to the reference period (2001-2021):

- i. To what intensity has the built-up area of Siliguri experienced growth?
- ii. How spatially organised or disorganised is the pattern of built-up growth in and around the city?
- iii. What are the principal modes that characterise the urban growth of the city?
- iv. How has urbanisation contributed to the changing pattern of built-up landscape in the study area?

The findings from the UEII reveal a notable rise in the growth intensity of built-up areas within the Siliguri urban agglomeration over the course of last two decades. This suggests a dynamic trend towards increased urban

development and expansion. Concurrently, when examining the data through the lens of Shannon's entropy, a different facet of the urban growth emerges. The application of Shannon's entropy indicates a remarkable growth in the magnitude of urban sprawl within the study area, as in between 2001 and 2011, the growth rate in relative entropy was 1.35% that has been increased by 6.96% in the subsequent decade between 2011 and 2021. So far as different modes of urban growth is concerned, the LEI depicts an extraordinary dominance of edge-expansion as the principal mode of urban sprawl around Siliguri, as well as a growing number of new urban patches (leapfrog development) coming out over the agricultural tracts without any direct spatial association with pre-existing urban patches. This deduction is also supported by the insights gathered from the dynamics of Landscape Metrics values, which depict an increasing rate of land fragmentation caused by unplanned conversion of agricultural land parcels into built-up tracts.

On the whole, the insights gathered from different geo-spatial indices depict that the existing pattern of urban spatial growth of Siliguri is highly unsustainable in nature that needs an immediate attention of statutory planning authorities. The results of this study, thus, are expected to furnish empirical insights into the spatial pattern of urban growth, encompassing Siliguri, which may assist policymakers in planning for a sustainable pattern of urbanisation in the city and its surrounding region.

Keywords: Urban sprawl, Urban Expansion Intensity Index, Shannon's entropy, Landscape Expansion Index, Siliguri

Sustainable Urban Growth and Environmental Resilience: An Integrated Approach to Land Use Management, Ecological Conservation, and Resilient Development in Thrissur, Kerala, India

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Thrissur, a rapidly urbanising city in southern India, faces complex challenges due to economic development, infrastructure expansion, and changes in land use. This urban dynamism impacts not only the city but also rural areas (rural-urban migration and settlement), affecting agriculture and ecological balance. To address these issues, a comprehensive Land Use Management Framework is proposed, integrating spatial planning, zoning, infrastructure development, community engagement, and environmental assessments. This framework aims to achieve a balance between urban development and ecological conservation, ensuring a sustainable future for both urban and rural communities.

The Land Use Management Framework for Thrissur is supported by a systematic approach that utilises advanced tools like geospatial analysis, land use modeling, ecosystem assessments, and the measurement of urban dispersion patterns. Various policy initiatives are also integrated to address interventions at regional, city, and local levels.

The framework is primarily based on a comprehensive understanding of land use changes during the years 2013, 2017, and 2023. Satellite imagery, particularly from Landsat 8, is utilised to classify different land cover categories such as built-up areas, wetlands, agricultural land, dense vegetation, water bodies, and barren land. Analysis of this data reveals significant trends, including the expansion of developed areas, a decline in agricultural land and dense vegetation, a reduction in wetlands, and slight decreases in other land classes over the past decade. As an innovative measure, the framework uses an artificial neural network approach to predict future land use changes up to 2039. This forward-looking analysis provides valuable projections and serves as a useful tool for strategic planning and navigating Thrissur's ever-changing urban landscape.

The research findings highlight the significant increase in urbanisation trends in Thrissur, with the built-up footprint expanding from 8,080 hectares in 2013 to 14,845 hectares in 2023. This rapid growth demonstrates the transformative impact of urban development on the city's landscape. Additionally, there has been a notable decrease in agricultural land by 836 hectares, raising concerns about potential changes in agricultural practices

and their impact on food security and rural livelihoods. Furthermore, there has been a concerning reduction in dense vegetation by 566 hectares and wetlands by 916 hectares, which raises ecological concerns about forest health and changes in hydrological patterns.

To better understand the broad effects of these land use changes, the study uses ecosystem service valuation to evaluate the consequences on essential services for human and environmental well-being. The findings show declines in services such as food, water, and raw material availability, as well as impacts on climate and water regulation, nutrient cycles, and habitat provisions. This highlights the complex relationship between urban development and ecological health, emphasising the need for sustainable land use practices.

In addition to this, Shannon's entropy method plays a key role in accurately representing the urban structure of Thrissur. It provides a quantitative approach to analysing spatio-temporal distribution patterns and fragmentation trends. This method is particularly useful for understanding urbanisation characterised by uncontrolled and haphazard development. The results obtained demonstrate an increase in built-up areas and a lack of uniformity in urban development throughout the study area. The calculated entropy values, which range from 0.938 to 1.056, highlight the level of disorder and unevenness in the urban landscape. These values exceed the threshold, confirming the presence of urban sprawl and indicating that urbanisation is occurring without a cohesive and planned framework. This confirmation provides valuable insights into the challenges posed by uncontrolled urbanisation and emphasises the need for strategic interventions in urban planning processes.

The proposed comprehensive plan for Thrissur is a multifaceted strategy designed to curb urban sprawl and address the challenges of dispersion in the region. Informed by spatio-temporal mapping and Shannon's entropy analysis, the plan advocates for localised area planning to manage urban growth, prevent uncontrolled sprawl, and mitigate environmental impacts. It emphasises the establishment of a statutory metropolitan planning body to coordinate actions across sectors and jurisdictions effectively. Additionally, the proposal suggests using surplus government lots for affordable housing and meeting critical housing needs. In conjunction with these land use and transportation policies, the study proposes a Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) model. This model offers various incentives to promote environmental stewardship and conservation practices in different sectors. Examples include providing payments to farmers who adopt sustainable farming practices, establishing a sustainable fisheries fund to encourage conservation among fisherfolk, empowering communities to undertake environmental activities, and encouraging eco-friendly practices in the tourism industry through certification programs and price premiums. Corporate contributions and government-imposed eco-taxes are also suggested to support environmental conservation efforts.

An integral aspect of the proposal involves the development of a Biodiversity Index, serving as a monitoring and evaluation framework with relevant indicators. This index acts as a quantitative scoring tool, enabling cities to assess their progress in biodiversity conservation against individual baselines. The self-assessment nature of the Index on Cities' Biodiversity provides a means for cities to benchmark and monitor their efforts systematically, fostering a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of conservation initiatives. Clear urban-rural boundaries are set to protect valuable agricultural and ecological areas, accompanied by greenbelt integration to conserve natural landscapes. The peri-urban transept concept ensures controlled development overflow from the core city. The plan utilises regulations, incentives, and investments to safeguard Thrissur's cultural identity, environment, and promote inclusive economic growth. With a focus on the urban-rural interface, the plan strives for a balanced approach, preventing undue pressure on rural spaces while fostering sustainable urban development. By integrating these elements, the comprehensive framework aims to achieve well-balanced and informed development, considering the interconnectedness of ecological, cultural, and economic factors and preserving Thrissur's unique character and resilience.

Keywords: Land Use Land Cover Change, Ecosystem Service Valuation, Shannon's Entropy, Rural-urban migration and settlement, Sustainable Land Use

Examining the Role of Informal Processes in Shaping the Built and Natural Environment in Peri-urban Vadodara, India

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Since economic liberalization, the growth of urban activities has been swiftly changing the peri-urban regions in India. It is observed that the changes in land use and the built environment of the urban peripheral region are not a natural process (Shaw, 2005; Sridharan, 2011).

The peri-urban developments in an Indian city have been an intrigued area for issues of land uses. Conventionally, the peri-urban region has been peripheral to the key processes of urban development and planning was absent or negligible efforts were made. However, today it is considered to be a product of new dynamics of capitalism which is happening under the predominant impact of global and local political economy of the world. Now these peri-urban regions in South Asian countries represent the profound political and economic shifts and social transformations. These peripheral changes are considered to be central to the process of universal economic integration (Banerjee-Guha, 2002; Harvey, 1978; Roy, 2009, 2015).

It is believed that the socio-economic conditions, political economic forces, formal and informal processes of urban planning and governance influence the contemporary urban expansions and surrounding region (Harvey, 1978; Roy, 2009, 2015). During post-independence period in India, the industrial and real-estate development reciprocally strengthened each other. At present, the power of state and private sector is evident which impact the political rationality of speculative world of real estate by provoking new forms of informal planning and governance processes which intervene in other stakeholders' rights and livelihood practices in ways that add to their vulnerabilities, risks, and conflicts. This paper explains the paradox of urban and regional planning and governance by analysing the structure of informal processes in Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

This paper is based on the fundamental study conducted in the peripheral region which explore formal and informal urban governance processes, underlying socio-economic or political forces and changing socio-spatial characteristics of urban growth by focusing on the case of Vadodara. The city is best known for progressive urban planning and industrial development along with socio-economic reforms that were practiced under Maratha rule (Rajgyor & Tripathy, 1979). The research is a thorough case study of the fast and recent development of residential complexes, farmhouses and weekend homes, which have been taking place in the peripheral region of Vadodara. The mixed methods of research employed to collect primary data from three main groups of stakeholders. The data gathered from secondary sources provides knowledge about temporal peri-urban development pattern in erstwhile Vadodara.

The analysis reflects upon linkages between the socio-economic condition of stakeholders, challenges, and prospects with regards to the role and instruments of stakeholders associated with physical planning and governance of peri-urban development and changes in built environment. It can be concluded from this research that continued history of the strong mercantile economy in Gujarat, socio-economic and urban reforms by Marathas, commercial agriculture practices, and pro-industrialisation policies largely determined the characteristics of peri-urban built environment during the colonial period in Vadodara which is quite different from other princely states of India (Vasudeva, 2018). However, the post-liberalization peri-urban regions mainly belong to the emerging middle and upper-middle income group of people. The well-designed residential complexes are one of the important driving forces. Restricted entry and intentional social and spatial segregation are clearly visible in recently developed peri-urban regions. As the nature of capital is changing and it is re-modifying the peri-urban built and natural environment. New international school, colleges, farmhouses, clubs and weekend homes are getting developed in peri-urban areas. However, this development is not in tandem with the village lifestyle and eventually leads to conflicts between villagers, developers, development authority and new peri-urban residents. The major conflict issues deteriorate the existing condition of villages as well as lead to bumpy and biased overall development of town planning schemes and residential development. Many informal processes between developers, development authority and village panchayat officials result into main conflict areas such as quality and quantity of the provision of facilities and amenities, change in infrastructure and traffic condition and overall quality of life. That location of peri-urban projects negatively impacted the quality and quantity of agricultural product and farmers are forced to

give up farming activities (McGee,1991; Vasudeva,2018). The urban expansion is encroaching the agricultural areas and farmers are losing the agricultural interest (Singh and Vyas, 2014; Vasudeva, 2018).

The study observed that the new farmhouse and weekend homes make use of village infrastructure, but in turn village receives noise and air pollution which further deteriorates the condition of existing facilities. These types of conflict seem to have occurred due to the absence of micro- zoning tools (EWC, n.d., Vasudeva, 2018). It was observed that the formal process of provision of premium FSI has potential to change the characteristics and typology of a neighbouring building. By using the premium FSI, in the same neighbourhood, the stakeholders from high-rise built spaces encroach on the privacy of stakeholders from low-rise residential campuses. Such situation leads to conflicts between stakeholders. Waste management and garbage disposal are critical issues of regular conflicts and are directly connected with environmental sustainability and quality of life in peri-urban built environment. It can be concluded that the conflicts and informal processes seem to change the direction of development and growth of peri-urban and rural territories (Harvey, 1978; Lefebvre, 2003).

The current system of peri-urban planning and development basically plays a coordinative role to spatial orderliness. However, this research reveals many gaps and it requires intervention, improvement, and revision in current perspective and instruments utilised for peri-urban development. Failure to address these apparently peri-urban development issues not only results in a plethora of missed opportunities to benefit from rural-urban synergies but also fails to address a key flashpoint in undermining the ability to improve environmental integrity and social equity in a growing urban region. Such linkages between informal processes and study of other aspects have the potential to improvise the current system of physical planning and governance of peri-urban regions.

Keywords: Built environment, Conflict, Informal process, Peri-urban development, Physical Planning

TRACK- 5: INCLUSIVE URBAN REGENERATION AND PUBLIC SPACES

The track revolves around creating public spaces considering beauty, quality, accessibility, connectivity, and resilience for sustainable urban regeneration. How does place-making change over identity, culture, and geography? How can we address the challenges of inclusivity in sustainable urban regeneration through place-making? How do we tackle gentrification and the conflict between formal and informal placemaking? The track has the following sub-themes:

- Urban Regeneration: Social Inclusion and Equity
- Age-Friendly and Gender-Sensitive Urban spaces
- Sustainable Placemaking: Policies and Approaches

Urban Green Space and Sustainability: An Approach to Developing Green Spaces in Itanagar-Naharlagun of Northeast India

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Urban settlements transform the natural environment so greatly that people tend to see the city only as an employment site, economic, and cultural center. Thus, a growing number of people prefer to settle in the cities for various purposes such as employment, trade, education, medical purpose, and other conveniences. This trend has resulted in the rapid growth of urban populations across the globe; and the world's cities are becoming increasingly congested and polluted. Increased population density and spatial expansion has exerted huge negative impacts on green areas and transforms urban green spaces to impervious landscapes. Additionally, ongoing rapid urbanisation has resulted in various environmental hazards and climate change-related issues. In recent years, a lot of studies have documented urban growth and consequent loss of urban green spaces. Few examples of such challenges include, urban land use, impact on land surface temperature, urban climate, environmental degradation, loss of natural habitat and species diversity, changing local climate, the Urban Heat Island, and the rising level of pollution.

According to Census of India (2011), 31.16% (37 crore) of the country's population resided in urban areas and the urban component is expected to rise to around 40% by 2026. Similarly, the state of Arunachal Pradesh has been recorded with very high urban growth rate of 37.55% and annual growth rate of 5.44%. In its Urban Mapping and Geo-database (December, 2021), the Department of Town Planning and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs), Government of Arunachal Pradesh, has pointed out that "the number of urban settlements in Arunachal Pradesh is increasing relatively rapid growth and the percentage of state's population living in urban areas is expected to increase to nearly 40% by 2026 and cross 50% by 2051". This trend of unprecedented urbanisation has been fuelled by rapid economic growth and industrialization. This means that a larger number of settlements, as well as a larger percentage of population, has to be planned for urgently to ensure economic growth of the nation and well-being of the people.

Urban green spaces (UGS) provide a wide range of ecosystem services that could help combat many urban related issues and improve life for city dwellers. The ecosystem services provided by green spaces largely depend on the physical qualities and functions of those spaces, and they give benefits and values for people. UGSs have very important part in creating the space of cities because quality of an urban is a result of balanced distribution between buildings, transport infrastructure, and green spaces. Apart from ecosystem services, UGS provides several benefits to the urban dwellers in terms of environmental benefits, public health, psychological benefits, aesthetic value, and overall wellbeing. UGS also provides ecological, physical benefits, and economic benefits. According to the TCPO, GoI, MoUD (2014), urban green spaces are critical for making our cities sustainable, healthy, and energy efficient.

In recent years, a lot of studies have documented urban growth and consequent loss of urban green spaces. Therefore, ensuring sustainability in the urban environment has become a general concern among scientists and policy makers. UGS has been suggested as an essential factor for advancing human wellbeing and sustainable urban development. In other words, UGS is one such undertakings that is considered as an important aspect of urban settlements as well as cities worldwide as its contribution is significant part of sustainable development.

The aim of this study is to identify issues on environmental challenges in Itanagar-Naharlagun complex of Northeast India where urbanisation and industrialization has greatly impacted on the spatial patterns, settlements, land surface temperature, land use, and loss biodiversity as a result of reduced green spaces.

The proposed study area i.e., Itanagar and Naharlagun are the twin-capital cities of Arunachal Pradesh though the former remains the administrative capital of the state. The 'Itanagar-Naharlagun Complex' is often referred so, to indicate the close proximity between the two as well as connectivity which is closely connected in terms of economic, trade and marketing, travel, education, health facilities, etc. Itanagar is adjacent to Naharlagun with a road distance of 13 km. With their close correlates, Itanagar lies between 27.0844°N latitude and 93.6053°E longitude at an average altitude of 320 meters above sea level. Naharlagun on the other hand, lies between 27.1086° N latitude, 93.6984° E longitude at an altitude of 155 meters above sea level. Both cities experience humid

subtropical climate, rich in natural resources and ecological conditions. The total geographical area of Itanagar is 167.09 sq.km. and that of Naharlagun is 153.30 sq.km. Population wise, Itanagar has a higher number of persons (81,000) than Naharlagun (47,000). The population density is 391 per sq.km. and 320 per sq.km. for Itanagar and Naharlagun respectively. Rapid increase in urbanisation and urban migration in recent years has given rise to increased population densities and built-up areas of which both Itanagar and Naharlagun are core cities with high level of urban development. According to the Department of Town Planning, Government of Arunachal Pradesh, the Itanagar-Naharlagun region comprises of 30 urban wards (20 in Itanagar region and 10 in Naharlagun (including Banderdewa) region).

The increasing trend of urbanisation and urban migration in Itanagar-Naharlagun complex seems to be in a similar paste with the rest of the cities in India. There are limited literatures on UGS in Northeast India and specifically in Arunachal Pradesh. This paper proposes an analytical approach for detailed investigations which will help in effective and systematic development of green spaces in these cities. Establishment of research approach, through proper data processing and analysis, will shed insight on our understanding of UGS and sustainability. The results to this call would help researchers and policy makers to develop strategies to deal with the impact and negative consequences of urbanisation, urban migration and industrialization

Keywords: Urban Green Space, Sustainability, Urbanisation, Industrialization, Development

Rail Transit Hubs, Urban Regeneration and Contemporary Urbanism: A Study of Land Use-Transport Feedback Mechanism and Transit-Oriented Development in India

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Urban regeneration, a multifaceted process centered on the reconstruction of spaces, encompasses initiatives aimed at elevating the quality of both physical and social environments. This transformative endeavour also seeks to enhance the economic viability of spaces and foster environmental sustainability. Notably, railway stations stand out as pivotal elements in contemporary urban regeneration strategies, playing dual roles as significant social hubs and crucial focal points of material interest. As we navigate the complexities of the twentieth century, railway stations have gained increasing prominence due to several pressing issues. The exponential growth of the global population, coupled with relentless urbanisation trends, has posed significant challenges to the sustainable functioning urban centers. Moreover, the alarming rise in vehicle emissions and the consequent pollution further underscore the critical importance of railway stations and systems as essential components in urban infrastructure. Recognising these challenges, urban policymakers have increasingly turned to railway stations as strategic sites for intervention and development.

The latter part of the previous century witnessed a paradigm shift in urban policies, acknowledging the immense value inherent in railway stations and their adjacent lands. Beyond their traditional role as transportation nodes, these locations have come to be viewed as potential catalysts for comprehensive urban development. The strategic positioning of railway stations allows for not only efficient transportation but also serves as a catalyst for socio-economic growth. This realisation has prompted urban planners to incorporate railway stations into broader urban policies, leveraging their potential to shape and optimize the functionality of urban centers. Moreover, the revitalisation of railway stations aligns with the broader goals of sustainable urban development. As cities grapple with the need for environmental responsibility, the adaptive reuse and redevelopment of railway stations provide opportunities to create eco-friendly, transit-oriented urban spaces. This holistic approach to urban regeneration emphasises not only the economic and social aspects but also the imperative of mitigating the environmental impact of urbanisation.

This paper seeks to undertake an in-depth analysis of the inherent significance of railway stations and their immediate surroundings within the intricate urban fabric of a city. To accomplish this, a pertinent theoretical

framework, namely the ‘Node-Place Model,’ (Bertolini, 1996, 1999; Bertolini and Spit, 1998) will be employed to shed light on the dynamic interplay between these transportation hubs and their urban context. In tandem with this theoretical exploration, the paper also aims to bring into focus the concept of (re)development of functional spaces in and around railway stations. This facet represents a key dimension of contemporary urban regeneration strategies. The paper will elucidate this dimension by drawing upon specific examples from India, thereby providing real-world illustrations of how station-oriented (re)development initiatives contribute to the overall urban landscape. India is a country that has experienced a significant surge in urban population since the last three decades, thus, grappling with a myriad of urban challenges. These factors together places the country at the forefront of adopting innovative approaches to address the imperatives of sustainable urban development. Among these strategies, Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) has emerged as a powerful tool with the potential to enhance the liveability, sustainability, and inclusivity of Indian cities. The envisioned outcome of this transformative process is the emergence of what is colloquially termed as “Railopolis” – a miniature smart city embedded within the existing urban landscape. Therefore, the principal objectives of this study is to:

- i. Understand the ‘place value’ of railway stations, as a part of overall urban landscape.
- ii. Argue for the realisation of such (place) values in contemporary urban development strategies that seek to promote the goals of sustainability and resilience;
- iii. Contextualize the need for transit-oriented urban planning in Indian cities and throw lights on contemporary Indian initiatives that aim to address such planning needs.

On the grounds of methodology, the present research draws on the published literature available in the public domain as well as the analysis of the representations of transit-oriented urban development endeavours in popular mass media (especially newspaper articles).

The findings of this research, thereby, reveals that the pressing urban issues faced by India, including rapid urbanisation, congestion, and environmental concerns, necessitate novel solutions that go beyond conventional urban planning paradigms. Transit-oriented development (TOD) stands out as a holistic approach, integrating transportation infrastructure, land use, and urban design to create vibrant, interconnected urban spaces. By strategically locating high-density, mixed-use developments around transit nodes, such as railway stations, TOD aims to optimize accessibility, reduce dependency on private vehicles, and promote sustainable modes of transportation. Moreover, the concept of “Railopolis” encapsulates the essence of TOD on a microcosmic scale. By envisioning mini smart cities evolving around existing railway stations, this approach seeks to leverage the transit infrastructure as a catalyst for comprehensive urban development. The integration of smart technologies, sustainable practices, and inclusive design principles within these “Railopolis” entities aligns with the overarching goals of sustainable urban development in India.

Keywords: Railway stations, Transit-Oriented Development (TOD), Node-Place model, Urban regeneration, Contemporary urbanism

Identifying Vernacular Architectural Styles Evolution and Its Integration into Resort Design of Kerala

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Kerala, renowned as “God’s Own Country,” stands out for its unparalleled natural allure, diverse cultural heritage, and distinctive tourist attractions. This research delves into the growing trend of incorporating indigenous architectural styles into resort projects across the Kerala region. Resorts, strategically positioned in landscapes ranging from serene beaches to picturesque lagoons, lush hillsides, and tranquil lakes, function as havens for relaxation and enjoyment. The surge in adopting indigenous architectural styles in Kerala’s resort projects marks a compelling evolution, seamlessly blending modern hospitality with the state’s rich cultural legacy and breathtaking natural surroundings. These resorts, designed to provide guests with unparalleled experiences, artfully integrate

Kerala's distinctive features—backwaters, pristine beaches, rolling hills, and a tapestry of cultural and traditional history. The infusion of local architectural elements not only adds a unique charm to the resorts but also fosters a deeper connection with the region's roots. This trend signifies a conscious effort to offer visitors a holistic experience, where the architecture itself becomes a storyteller, narrating the tale of Kerala's past while embracing the comforts of contemporary luxury. In essence, the convergence of indigenous architectural styles in Kerala's resort projects exemplifies a harmonious fusion of tradition, nature, and hospitality, creating an unforgettable retreat for discerning travellers.

Kerala's traditional architecture intricately weaves together historical, geographical, and climatic influences, resulting in unique features that marry practical functionality with artistic expression. Characterised by slanted roofs, intricate woodwork, and the use of indigenous materials like timber and laterite stones, along with spacious inner courtyards, these architectural elements have evolved as a response to the tropical climate and a reflection of local values. The architecture, deeply rooted in the region's ethos, seamlessly integrates with the abundant natural surroundings.

Resorts in Kerala, embracing these native architectural styles, consciously act as custodians of the region's cultural heritage while providing tourists with an immersive experience. The deliberate fusion of traditional forms with the natural landscape establishes a symbiotic relationship between the built environment and the terrain, promoting sustainable tourism practices. This not only fosters a sense of pride and connection to Kerala's heritage among both locals and visitors but also prioritises the preservation of traditional craftsmanship and architectural skills, often involving skilled artisans who have inherited ancient traditions. Beyond mere aesthetic appeal, the integration of traditional architecture reflects a profound commitment to honouring and perpetuating Kerala's rich legacy, making these resorts not just places of stay but living embodiments of the state's cultural and architectural narrative.

This paper delves into the captivating confluence of traditional architectural customs and contemporary resort design principles prevalent in the scenic landscapes of Kerala. Examining critical factors crucial in resort design, the research focuses on site planning intricacies, exterior and interior design paradigms, the synergy of passive and active design elements, and the meticulous crafting of facilities, juxtaposed against pricing strategies. Augmented by in-depth case studies of resorts, with a particular focus on those situated along the beaches and backwaters, this seminar culminates in a comparative analysis, synthesizing diverse design approaches and strategies.

The study places a spotlight on the escalating allure of vernacular architectural styles in resort hotels, emphasising their seamless integration with Kerala's nature and cultural heritage. It endeavours to explore the fundamental concepts underpinning the fusion of different design elements, analysing how this integration enhances the experiences of visitors while concurrently safeguarding and conserving the traditional aesthetics of the region. Significantly, the research underscores the importance of this design approach in not only providing a unique and immersive experience for guests but also in contributing to the preservation and celebration of Kerala's architectural and cultural legacy.

This comprehensive study delves into the intricate relationship between the environment, traditional values, and the contemporary paradigm of resort architecture in Kerala. Utilising a combination of case studies and an extensive review of pertinent literature, the objective is to unveil the nuanced interplay between design philosophies, cultural heritage, and the natural surroundings. The primary aim is to deepen our understanding of how these elements harmonize, not only shedding light on the current state of resort architecture but also providing insights into the potential trajectory of future projects that prioritise sustainability while immersing visitors in Kerala's diverse cultural tapestry.

This research aspires to serve as a roadmap for the evolution of resorts that go beyond mere aesthetics, aiming to respect and preserve tradition while embracing modernity. The ultimate goal is to pave the way for culturally immersive, environmentally conscious, and sustainable architectural endeavours within Kerala. Through a synthesis of case studies and literature, this study aims to provide crucial guidance for architects, developers, and stakeholders. It advocates for the creation of resorts that not only captivate through innovative design but also actively contribute to the positive preservation of Kerala's environment and rich cultural heritage. By offering insights and recommendations, the research seeks to inspire a sustainable and culturally sensitive approach in future resort projects, aligning them with the ethos of the region while enhancing the overall visitor experience.

Keywords: Resorts, Native architectural styles, Cultural heritage, Beach and backwaters resorts

Improving Inclusive Mobility in Urban Environments: A Case Study of Jamshedpur's Straight Mile Road

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This paper presents a set of tactical suggestions for revitalising Jamshedpur's transportation network based on Secondary and Primary data. Jamshedpur is one of the oldest and is considered as the largest existing industrial town in India. Straight mile road is one of the major connector of the city's commercial establishment with the western part of the Jamshedpur city. The study identified the road's present mobility issues and recommended solutions to mitigate traffic, environmental issues, and other concerns. The primary recommendation for improving the mobility is to invest in infrastructure. The framework recognises the importance of public transportation and promotes the creation of effective, networked transit networks. This includes designating specific lanes for non-motorized transportation, such as walking and bicycling routes. Integrating smart technology is also essential for improved user experience, real-time monitoring, and traffic optimization. The aim is to create a resilient mobility network that can adapt to future changes in technology and population while also satisfying present needs.

The strategic framework calls for minimal changes that can alter the regulatory environment and promote environmentally friendly transportation methods in addition to infrastructure expenditures. Infrastructural improvements must work in concert to establish an environment where sustainable transportation is not only an option but also a desirable and realistic alternative for the citizens of Jamshedpur. The research promotes the creation and application of environmental friendly changes that give preference to ecologically sustainable forms of transportation. Adding to it the consideration of the old buildings (heritage building) – Which will increase the value of the road while giving an identity. Heritage sites are arguably the physical component of a city's identity. The lived-in architecture, the strategic locations and the uses of these buildings reveal unique stories telling of how our city came to be and can offer predictions of where it might be going. These features add character and beauty to our city, fostering a sense of home and community, and serving as a reminder to each of us that our city's history belongs to all of us together. Just as these magnificent buildings have been passed down to us, we must preserve them for future generations. Another instance is for vendors many vendors try to keep the streets clean and safe for their customers and provide them with friendly personal service. Street vendors create jobs, not only for themselves but for porters, security guards, transport operators, storage providers, and others. Street vending thus provides employment to a large section of the population. The poorer sections in the city are able to procure their basic necessities mainly through street vendors, as the goods sold are cheap. The suggested changes include encouraging the use of electric cars, providing rewards for carpooling, and enacting congestion pricing to deter the use of private vehicles during rush hours. A regulation review is also recommended to promote mixed-use development and lessen the demand for mass transit.

The research highlights community engagement as a crucial component of revitalising Jamshedpur's transportation network. Incorporating locals in the decision-making process, exchanging ideas, and offering feedback on mobility efforts is vital. To allow citizens to actively participate in conversations, the research recommends using community forums. Educational initiatives are also advised to encourage a sense of shared accountability for the city's transportation ecology and to highlight the advantages of sustainable mobility practices.

The strategic framework also acknowledges the necessity of ongoing assessment and monitoring systems to gauge the success of suggested initiatives. This call for setting up data gathering procedures, performance measures, and ongoing assessments to gauge the effectiveness of tactics that have been put into practice. The urban mobility scene is continuously evolving, and the study emphasises how crucial it is to apply recommendations with flexibility, allowing for iterative modifications based on feedback from the actual world and evolving trends.

The study findings are carefully considered for larger implications on urban planning and development worldwide, especially in industrial centers. The research explores the complex network of urban mobility, essentially taking the reader on an intellectual voyage. The research provides a concrete action plan rather than just diagnosing urban problems, offering policymakers and urban planners a wealth of useful assistance as they tackle similar difficulties in their various regions. The proposed blueprint serves as evidence of the research's goal of acting as a catalyst for constructive change by imploring stakeholders to reconsider and rework their plans for urban growth.

In conclusion, this research encapsulates a holistic exploration of Jamshedpur's journey towards revitalising its backbone—urban mobility. The findings of this research extend beyond the specific context of Jamshedpur, offering a valuable contribution to the global conversation on reshaping urban mobility in the face of evolving industrial landscapes and growing urban populations. The research aspires to inspire positive change, to serve as a guiding light for cities worldwide seeking sustainable and transformative solutions.

Keywords: Inclusive mobility, Infrastructure planning, Non-motorized Transport, Walking, Bicycling, Mixed use development

Revitalising Urban Public Open Spaces: A Gender Specific Exploration of the Impact and Strategic Significance of Regeneration of Open Spaces in Contemporary Urban Planning for Vibrant and Inclusive Communities

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In contemporary urban planning, urban regeneration of public open spaces is a strategic strategy that aims to revitalise and reconfigure urban landscapes in order to meet the ever-changing requirements of a wide variety of communities. The comprehensive study digs into the numerous ways in which urban redevelopment affects public open spaces, highlighting the vital role that it plays in facilitating the transformation of communities. In order to better understand the significant social, economic, and environmental components of urban regeneration programs, the analysis includes a review of a variety of case studies and scholarly literature. The primary focus of the research is on the potential of these initiatives to build community spaces that are dynamic and welcoming to all members of the community. The recognition that public open spaces are not only important social centers but also have a substantial impact on the overall quality of urban life is the impetus behind the idea of reviving these spaces. The economic benefits that are linked with urban regeneration emerge as key contributors to the sustainability of these projects. This is in addition to the social benefits. The revival of public open spaces has been shown to have the potential to result in increased property prices, the creation of new jobs, and the development of the local economy, according to numerous studies.

An important feature of urban regeneration is its capacity to address and alleviate gender-specific issues that women confront in urban areas. This is in addition to the larger influence that urban regeneration has on communities. Women frequently face a variety of distinct challenges in public areas, including those pertaining to personal safety, accessibility, and inclusiveness. These issues can be mitigated to a significant degree by the implementation of urban regeneration programs, which aim to create surroundings that are safer, more accessible, and more inclusive for all individuals, regardless of gender.

The emphasis placed on green spaces and sustainable design methods is in line with the worldwide urgency to combat climate change and to develop urban environments that are resilient. Not only can the incorporation of environmentally friendly elements, such as green roofs, rain gardens, and lighting that is effective in terms of energy consumption, improve the aesthetic appeal of public areas, but it also makes a contribution to the overall well-being of the community. These environmentally responsible behaviours not only reduce the negative effects on the environment, but they also make the urban environment healthier and more livable for the people who live there. It is becoming increasingly clear that the involvement and participation of the community are essential components for the success of urban redevelopment programs. Residents should be included in the planning and decision-making processes in order to guarantee that the regenerated areas are in accordance with the desired outcomes and requirements of the community. The participatory aspect of urban regeneration initiatives is especially advantageous when it comes to addressing the particular requirements that women have within the community. Women's participation in the planning and decision-making processes ensures that their perspectives and concerns are taken into account, which ultimately results in the creation of spaces that are responsive to the varied requirements of the entire community for whom they are intended. This strategy goes beyond merely

addressing urgent safety problems; rather, it delves into the creation of conditions that empower women in the context of economies, social relationships, and cultural practices. In addition, the restoration of public open spaces frequently involves taking into consideration a wide variety of cultural and recreational activities. Not only does this inclusiveness make it possible for women to participate in more leisure activities and social interactions, but it also helps to break down barriers that exist between different groups of people. Women are provided with opportunities to actively participate in cultural and recreational activities through the organisation of community programs and events that take place in regenerated spaces. This helps to promote a sense of belonging and empowerment among women. Not only does this participatory method make the project more sustainable, but it also gives communities the ability to take ownership of their public places, which in turn helps to cultivate a sense of pride and responsibility. By acting as a dynamic catalyst for community transformation, urban regeneration of public open spaces has the potential to influence the social, economic, and environmental aspects of urban life. The study discussed in this review sheds light on the linked nature of these characteristics, highlighting the necessity of adopting holistic approaches that prioritise community engagement, sustainability, and inclusivity. As cities continue to develop, urban regeneration is becoming an increasingly important and dynamic instrument for the creation of urban environments that are resilient, lively, and community-centered. These settings are designed to meet the changing requirements of a wide range of populations. Through the creation of landscapes that are not only aesthetically beautiful but also socially and economically beneficial for women, the urban regeneration of public open spaces emerges as a transformative force in the process of resolving gender inequities. This study emphasises the potential of urban regeneration to serve as a catalyst for eliminating gender-specific obstacles and building a more equitable and inclusive urban landscape. It does so by examining the restrictions, challenges, and interconnected nature of urban regeneration.

Keywords: Urban regeneration, Public open spaces, Gender bias, Community engagement

Decoding the Role of Art as a Tool for Social Inclusion in Urban Regeneration- A Case of Malleswaram Neighbourhood, Bengaluru, India

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Art is getting infused in our everyday spaces and demonstrated itself as social commentary to various narratives and diverse experiences. Street art and graffiti is considered synonymous to vandalism or crime in public opinion earlier but recently un-commissioned urban art in Malleswaram, Bengaluru considered as a radical and alternative way of contributing to the urban inheritance and revitalising urban spaces. It is not only an appropriation of urban space through an artistic approach but is the true form of access and democratization of public space to express the city dynamics and bridging the gap between its people and spaces. This similar spirit is reverberated now as a domino effect in many streets of Bengaluru, transforming the city's landscape into an eclectic canvas to express social, political and economic concerns along with the provision of safer access to the plurality of the city. Participatory art projects have provided a platform for dialogues and enabling the communities to voice their opinion on shaping and regenerating their neighbourhoods.

This paper investigates role of Art in the neighbourhoods of Bangalore and projects like "Art in Transit" aiming at facilitating a discourse between art and urban regeneration. It will also understand the role of art in bringing social inclusion which could be a major tool for urban regeneration. The works of Street artist like "Guess who" "who is staying anonymous and making Bengaluru waking up to some scathing humour that adorns street side walls of Church Street, Halasuru and St Mark's Road, the "Kalakarah effect" which explores the art in commissioned spaces will also be studied to understand the impact in other neighbourhoods of Bengaluru. The paper employs qualitative research methods and reflexive thematic analysis involving detailed in depth interviews, visual recordings, and ethnographies. It explores embodied research methods to generate tools to evaluate the impact of Art in these neighbourhoods of Bengaluru, India. The study aims at finding the contribution of Art as a tool to social

inclusion and a permanent discourse in urban regeneration. Malleswaram a northwestern older neighbourhood established after the infamous Bengaluru Plague of 1898 and an upper middle class Hindu communities had its share of glory in the historical timeline. With the uncontrolled urban development and real estate dominance in the neighbourhood, the marginalized communities had been neglected for years, the existing community also had expressed its lack of place identity, sense of belonging and blurred cultural identity. Development in transit corridors and unsustainable real estate development have been considered to the urban degradation. The infrastructural development and urban growth have led to cultural degradation and social exclusion which have generated to unsustainable urban development.

The research resulted in understanding how Art can contribute to express diversity and builds empathy among communities. It also creates safer accessibility to marginalized communities by empowering them to express opinions on various socioeconomic concerns and political discourses of the city. It contributed to the understanding of social inclusion a sustainable method for urban regeneration Art projects in Malleswaram have created a sense of place and fostering community participation in the neighbourhood. It also had created a way forward of other Bengaluru's neighbourhoods to relook at the inclusion of Art projects as tool for urban regeneration. Social equity, Inclusive communities plays a major role in urban growth especially in city like Bengaluru where cultural identity is blurred after colonial invasion. The ever-changing identity of this metropolis can have a sustainable growth with Art projects. The research also found out Art works in Malleswaram is contributing to the urban inheritance which is an underexplored area in urban research. Further investigations can help us to understand this development too.

Concluding Art projects serves as a powerful tool for social inclusion by fostering empathy, understanding among communities. It also brings diverse communities to work towards a common goal of urban regeneration of their neighbourhood. This as a medium can be explored further as an inclusionary/exclusionary work for a larger urban regeneration project but policy level interventions is the current need for future projects. Art research and interdisciplinary approaches to measure economic value beyond the sociocultural benefits of Art projects is required which in future will contribute to the feasibility of various Art project proposals to local authorities.

Keywords: Social inclusion, Street art, Graffiti, Public spaces, Urban inheritance

A Literature Review on Quality of Public Streets

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Public streets are dynamic centres of identity, empowerment, recreation, awareness, celebration, and revenue generation that reflect the true spirit of a city. They have a huge role in shaping a city and hence need adequate attention from all its stakeholders for their upkeep. As one of the primary categories of public space, the streets have been narrowed down as a subject to be studied here.

Streets are a crucial category of public space due to their versatility and intensity of use in the daily lives of every urban resident. These can be streets, avenues, and boulevards; squares and plazas; pavements; passages and galleries; and bicycle paths (UN Habitat, 2015). In Indian context we might refer to them as roads, pathways, streets, pedestrian walkways, and cycle tracks. Streets are the most widely used public spaces in all forms of hierarchy, be it arterials roads of the city, inner lanes of the neighbourhood or busy commercial bazaars. "These are public spaces in the fullest sense of the word because they are publicly owned and maintained, accessible and enjoyable by all without charge and at all hours, day and night. They are the most versatile in terms of public enjoyment: they can host open-air markets, performances, events, political rallies, demonstrations, and informal sector activities." (UN Habitat, 2015). Carr (1992) rightly mentions them as the most "public", responsive, accessible, diverse, democratic, and multipurpose utilities.

Due to the highly restricted structure of the streets in the inner parts of cities, the conflict on which function should be prioritized becomes a difficult choice. There are cities such as Copenhagen, Vienna, Paris, Berlin, and London where car share models have been reduced to provide spaces for other activities. However, most of the developing cities still work towards provision of higher car modal share. (Anciaes, 2020). It is essential to balance place-based functions and movement (Carmona,2018). Successful streetscapes are inclusive and provide for the competing requirements of their users (Transport of London, 2016a, 2016b:1). Hence the streets need to be viewed as spaces that welcome all users' point of views. The policymakers today look at streets beyond their single purpose of passing vehicular and user traffic. They are considered complex places with economic and social exchanges along with the purpose of movement (Carmona,2018). The intention is to plan for streets that are capable of integration for multi functionality. In short, managing streets as “places” where social, cultural activities have a space.

The role of Indian streets is culturally unique and highly diverse in function. Indian streets are dynamic hub of cultural melting pot, commerce and trade, social gatherings, celebrations and festivities, streets art and expression, historic significance, culinary delight, economic activities, political rallies, protests, religious processions, street games and most importantly transportation and movement. These characteristics make Indian streets not just a mode for thoroughfares for commute, but multidimensional spaces that capture the essence of Indian spirit. These streets are highly adaptable and constantly evolving with societal changes, new trends and technology. And yet they maintain their inherent charm and character.

There is a lack of discussion of maintenance of street facilities and infrastructure. The focus remains on placemaking of streets rather than “place keeping” them. Secondly the recent discussion on placemaking focuses on the need to consider impermanency of structure for lighter quicker cheaper arrangements making streets more accommodating to the changing needs of the people. However, most street guidelines are devoid of this concept and purely more on permanency of infrastructure. Indian streets host *pandals*, *nukkad-natak*, or weekly bazaars and many more frequently. Hence the space of temporality of functions is a need. Thirdly, a very crucial aspect of the financial sustainability of the streets has been completely ignored. It is assumed that the streets are a liability, and the concerned agencies would fund their development and maintenance, bringing us back to the discussion of streets being considered as a liability rather than an asset. Revenue generation, or self-maintenance mechanisms, paid license businesses on streets are rarely discussed.

A quick literature review helps conclude that substantial work has been done around quality of streets and its assessment in developed nations. However, research in an Indian setting focuses more on universal accessibility, safety, and security concerns and street vending activities. There is limited work on what is a quality street and how the quality of Indian (or developing nation) streets could be understood. There is a need to accept and study Indian streets differently from those in developed countries. This research responds to the question - What is a quality street in an urban Indian setting? This question has been further broken down into the parameters for the quality of streets and perception of the quality of streets of its street users.

This study would address the understanding of how Indian streets could be treated differently and how they could be more sensitive to what the actual users want. In practice, it is very frequently observed that what is designed and planned for the streets is often not how it is used by the users. Academically this research responds to the evident gap in literature where there is limited discussion of how the quality of Indian streets could be studied. This study also throws light on the difference in perception of quality streets from different groups of users, professionals, and practitioners. This research would lay a setting stone for further studies that aim to link the impact of quality streets on various other urban attributes.

Keywords: Public Streets, Quality of Streets, Street user perception

TRACK- 6: GOVERNANCE, CAPACITY BUILDING AND EDUCATION

This track focuses on capacity building of the urban planner, managers, and decision-makers. It examines innovative planning and development approaches adopted for sustainability in the global south. It raises questions related to how the governance structure and policies in cities address sustainability? Why is it crucial to address the issue of capacity building among urban professionals and create awareness among the young generation for a sustainable future of cities? It will discuss institutional and human capacity-building practices, impacts, approaches, and policies, the existing scenarios of planning education in the global south, its issues, and the way forward. It will also focus on case studies, sustainable city framework, and best practices. This track is divided into the following sub-themes:

- SDGs and urban policy alignment in the global south
- Future sustainable cities- prospects and challenges
- Innovative governance strategies for urban sustainability
- Capacity building of urban professionals in the global south
- Planning education for sustainable urban development
- Future of cities, planning education and urban professionals: approaches and strategies for way forward

What is Smart in a Smart City: A Genealogy of Techno-centrism

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The debate on the idea of the ‘developmental state’ has widened to include questions of the kind of intervention that such a state invariably undertakes. Located within a techno-bureaucratic neoliberal framework, the modern nation state has come to embody the familiar trappings of a much-debated ‘problem-solving’ policy orientation. The gap between the ideals and the realities of implementation makes it pertinent for the state to relook its policy orientation. The failure of the developmental states occurs when they are sought to be transplanted across contexts and irrespective of local specificities. With the state supposedly receding to a traditional role of a functionary that works from above, more so within a neoliberal market framework, there exists the need to have a relook at the motives and consequences of an overriding economic lens of development.

In the Indian context, a large body of literature has already captured the numerous categorizations of the state’s developmental interventions. As concerns the newer policy framework of being a facilitator of governance, the Indian state’s Smart Cities mission is again a manifestation of the state seeking to bring about synergy from above. Rather than limit itself to a co-actor, the Indian state has, by contrast, actively framed the rules of engagement by seeking to harness the supposed idea of ‘fairness’ embedded in open, competitive markets. In its bare output, the focus has merely been on improvement through infrastructural growth, thereby conflating, yet again, the twin ideas of growth and development. Urban planning is an inherently political process, making it all the more desirable as an instrument of control by the bureaucratic apparatus. Questions of inclusiveness and coproduction have been seemingly sacrificed for instrumentalist gains. As a result of the ‘policy paradox’, the logic of development used by the state seems to have been one governed only through economic motives rather than societal inputs. While infrastructure is of utmost importance, it is not the sole metric of development, which needs to portray a more humane face.

This paper begins with an exploration of the idea of development that the Indian State has come to embody over time. In contrast to its western counterparts, the Indian state has emerged as a result of contestations and fragmentations in ideas. The political arm of the state has always sought to represent the convergence of ideas in its outlook. In a move away from multipolar interests, the contemporary state is instead characterised by an emphasis on uniformity of vision; the vision of a market-driven polity and society. This is in line with the notion of a ‘demiurge’ regime identified by Peter Evans, where the state and the market exist in mutually beneficial relationships. The particularities of such an outlook have led to the reproduction of an earlier version of a ‘problem-solving’ state, in the sense of contested ideas being repeatedly recaptured in contemporary bureaucratic language. The advent of new institutionalism has therefore seen its inevitable outcome in the widening gap between the aspirations of the state and its own ability to meet them. The recourse towards an earlier vision of development prevalent in western countries, while seeking to actively chart its own trajectory, forms the body of the paper, encapsulated through the idea of a smart city. In seeking to map out an indigenous strategy of development, the Indian state has seemingly gone back in policy making, by ordering society along economic lines. What is of particular note is that the current policy making is acknowledging of the need for inclusive development without a particular notion of how to achieve it. In such a scenario, despite good intentions, the idea of smart cities is a transplanting of earlier contested forms of planning. While the idea of creating a community-led model culminating in the manifestation of a ‘smart citizen’ is laudable, the avenues towards that goal is solely one of technological development. This version, it is argued, is an incomplete and partial representation.

Finally, a few avenues of alternative visions of inclusive development are explored, to enable the Indian Smart Cities Mission to better reflect the goals of ‘people-centric development’ that it envisages. While in line with the principles of sustainable development put forth by the United Nations, the actual workings reveal a murkier experience on the ground. A leaf can be taken out of the Yokohama Urban Design Sketchbook, a pioneering effort in civic planning that has the community at its heart. Instead of pursuing the idea of making a city smart over time, the direction of policy-making has tended to jump on to the next buzzword, encapsulated in declining mentions of the scheme from the mouth of the bureaucrats themselves. It is in such a landscape that the government’s Smart Cities Mission stands at a crossroad, with no clear pathways to its realisation. The idea of participative democracy and open and inclusive governance are sought to be intertwined through an increasingly forceful unifying rhetoric.

Keywords: Smart City, Policy-paradox, Problem-solving, Developmental State

Ragging in Educational Institutions in South Asia and Global South - A Possible Solution

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The pervasiveness of ragging in educational settings and its subsequent socio-psychological implications has been a topic of significant concern in contemporary academia.

Ragging is a long-standing tradition of maltreatment within the educational sphere, often seen in schools and universities worldwide. This practice, while called different names like fagging, hazing, bullying, and pledging in various regions, generally involves unwelcoming and harsh treatment of newcomers. In French, it's known as 'baptême', in Dutch as 'doop', and in Finnish as 'mopokaste'. Essentially, ragging refers to any act where a student is ridiculed or offended in a way that disrupts their mental well-being. New students often endure both physical and psychological torment, often inflicted by senior students, which infringes upon their basic human rights. Every year, many students suffer due to this forced humiliation. Victims of ragging can face a range of issues from physical harm to emotional distress. Tragic outcomes such as self-inflicted harm, violent incidents, mental disorders, and even suicides often arise from these episodes of ragging. As per the Indian Supreme Court's definition, ragging involves any form of misconduct—be it verbal, written, or physical—that instills fear or shame in a younger student, severely impacting their mental health. It essentially represents an abusive initiation rite for newcomers to educational institutions. Ragging is any action, practice or conduct by which the dominating power of senior students, ex-students or outsiders from other universities, is brought to bear on freshly enrolled students or any students who are in some way considered junior by senior students and includes individualistic or collective practices. (1) Involving physiological or psychological bullying or threatening or use of force or wrongful restraint or confinement; (2) violating the dignity, honor, and status of those students; (3) exposing students to contempt and ridicule and affecting their self-confidence and self-esteem; (4) engaging in act of verbal abuse and aggression, inappropriate gesture and nudity and obscenity in behaviour.

Informed by a combination of sociological and psychological theories, the review examines ragging through two main frameworks. First, the Social Learning Theory, which posits that individuals learn, and replicate behaviours observed in their social environment, helps us understand the cyclical nature of ragging wherein seniors, once victims themselves, perpetrate the same acts upon their juniors. Second, the Social Identity Theory offers insights into group dynamics, illuminating how students may resort to ragging as a mechanism to reinforce group cohesion and establish hierarchical structures.

The “what” of this review revolves around a detailed exploration of ragging's origins, manifestations, impacts, and prevalent measures to counteract it. We dissect ragging's multifaceted nature – ranging from seemingly ‘harmless’ pranks to severe physical and emotional trauma. The “why” delves into root causes, focusing on factors like peer pressure, the desire for dominance, institutional culture, and the absence of adequate preventive mechanisms.

A significant gap identified in the current body of literature pertains to the long-term psychological implications of ragging on its victims. While several studies highlight immediate after-effects, such as trauma, depression, and academic setbacks, there is a paucity of research on enduring psychological scars or potential post-traumatic growth. Additionally, many studies predominantly center on male-dominated institutions, thereby leaving a vacuum in understanding the nuances of ragging in co-educational and female-dominated settings.

This review is pivotal for multiple reasons. Firstly, by amalgamating diverse findings, it offers a holistic view of ragging, which can guide institutional policies and preventive measures more effectively. Secondly, by identifying gaps, it underscores areas requiring further exploration, facilitating a more comprehensive understanding of ragging's long-term effects and gender-specific dynamics. Lastly, in spotlighting the severity and ubiquity of the issue, it underscores the urgent need for stakeholders - from policymakers to educators - to prioritise the creation of ragging-free educational environments, promoting a culture of mutual respect and safety.

Ragging is a deeply rooted issue in South Asian educational institutions. Often framed as a rite of passage or harmless tradition, it has serious negative implications for the well-being and mental health of its victims. In countries like India, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh, incidents of ragging have sometimes escalated to grave physical

harm, or even led to student suicides. Despite legislative measures in these countries to curb this menace, its continuation underscores deeper societal challenges, including power dynamics and the normalisation of aggressive behaviours. The socio-cultural dimensions of ragging, as well as its psychological impacts, remain areas requiring further exploration and intervention in the South Asian context.

Keywords: Ragging, Bullying, Harassment, Educational institutions

Role of e- Governance in Reducing Corruption in Urban Governance in the Global South

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The omnipresence of corruption remains a pervasive issue in many governments worldwide. This literature review delves into the transformative potential of e-governance in curtailing such malfeasance. The study seeks to elucidate how technological interventions in governance can enhance transparency, accountability, and efficiency, subsequently leading to a decrease in corrupt practices. Several theories are explored, from the Information Asymmetry Theory, which suggests that improved information flow reduces opportunities for corruption, to the Public Choice Theory, indicating how digital tools can deter rent-seeking behaviours. Various frameworks, such as the Technology Acceptance Model, Process Re-Engineering Approach, Complex Systems Approach and the Institutional Analysis and Development framework, serve to contextualize e-governance adoption and its impact on reducing corruption. A predominant theme noted is the positive correlation between e-governance maturity and a decline in corruption indices. However, significant gaps persist, particularly in understanding the role of cultural, socio-economic, and political factors in mediating the efficacy of e-Governance initiatives. This review is crucial as it aggregates fragmented knowledge, providing policymakers with a holistic understanding of e-Governance's potential. It further contributes novelty by emphasising previously understudied interplays between e-governance and socio-political determinants of corruption.

Corruption has persistently plagued societies around the world, obstructing economic growth, compromising justice, and eroding public trust. Contemporary societies have been ardently seeking mechanisms to reduce and possibly eliminate the menace of corruption. In this quest, e-governance has emerged as a potential catalyst in promoting transparency, efficiency, and accountability in public administration. The advent of information technology and digital tools in governance has presented a paradigm shift in the way government's function and interact with their citizens. This literature review endeavours to critically analyse and synthesize existing scholarly work concerning the role of e-governance in mitigating corruption. The purpose of this literature review is to delve deeply into the multifaceted relationship between e-governance and its implications for reducing corruption and to comprehensively understand the breadth and depth of e-governance interventions, identify the key success factors, challenges faced, and gauge its real-world impact in curbing corruption. As nations around the world increasingly integrate technological advancements into their administrative frameworks, there is a burgeoning need to evaluate the effectiveness and potential of these digital systems in combating corrupt practices. e-governance, characterised by its transparent, efficient, and accountable operations, promises to revolutionize the way governments function by making them more accessible and responsive to their citizens. This review seeks to collate and synthesize diverse scholarly perspectives on the topic, exploring how various e-governance models have been implemented across different cultural and socio-political contexts and the impact they have had on transparency and corruption levels. Furthermore, it aims to identify gaps in current knowledge, highlight successful strategies, and provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced in leveraging e-governance as a tool against corruption. Through this exploration, this review hopes to contribute to the discourse on innovative governance strategies and their role in fostering a more transparent and accountable administrative ecosystem.

In the digital era, the pressing question of how technology can aid in the alleviation of societal challenges has gained prominence. Among these challenges, corruption stands out as a pervasive issue that hampers the growth and equitable distribution of resources in many nations. e-Governance, characterised by the digital transformation

of government operations, service deliveries, and citizen participation, emerges as a potential tool to counteract corrupt practices. The decision to focus my literature review on the role of e-governance in reducing corruption is driven by the need to understand the scope and depth of its impact. Specifically, as governments globally accelerate their digital agendas, it's imperative to determine if and how these technological shifts correlate with transparency and integrity in administrative processes. This review will delve into empirical studies, theoretical discourses, and case analyses, aiming to draw a comprehensive picture of e-governance's potential in creating transparent systems that leave limited room for corrupt activities. Through this, I aspire to contribute a consolidated perspective to policymakers and stakeholders, aiding in the informed design and implementation of e-governance initiatives targeted at corruption reduction.

The transformative potential of e-Governance in shaping modern administrative processes and fostering a transparent, accountable governance framework has been consistently elucidated throughout this review. By minimising the traditional bureaucratic bottlenecks, reducing human interference, and promoting transparency through open data initiatives, e-Governance inherently combats the malaise of corruption that has plagued governmental systems for ages. However, this potential is not without its challenges. Future research must delve deeper into understanding how e-Governance can be tailored to resonate with diverse cultural and regional sensibilities. A more granular exploration of case studies from different geographic areas, each with its unique corruption challenges, can provide a rich tapestry of insights. Moreover, there's a pressing need to research how e-Governance can be fortified against evolving digital threats, as the merger of cybercrime with corruption could be the next frontier of challenges.

In synthesizing the vast array of literature on e-Governance's role in counteracting corruption, it becomes abundantly clear that this digital paradigm promises a transformative shift in governance structures. e-Governance, rooted in the principles of transparency, efficiency, and citizen engagement, inherently challenges traditional corruption avenues. By reducing bureaucratic layers and championing open data initiatives, e-Governance diminishes the opportunities for corrupt practices to thrive, rendering illicit transactions more visible and traceable. However, the journey from traditional governance to e-Governance isn't devoid of challenges. The complexities of transitioning, coupled with issues like digital literacy, accessibility, and cybersecurity threats, require meticulous attention. Furthermore, the socio-cultural dynamics, often underpinning corruption, demand a tailored approach to e-Governance across different regions. While the potential of e-Governance in eradicating corruption is vast, its real-world impact hinges on continuous adaptation, stakeholder engagement, and sustained political will (Khan, 2005). In essence, e-Governance, when effectively implemented, can act as a formidable deterrent to corruption, heralding a new era of transparent, accountable, and citizen-centric governance. Future endeavours should focus on bridging identified research gaps, enhancing implementation strategies, and fortifying the e-Governance infrastructure against evolving threats, ensuring its unwavering commitment to reducing corruption remains robust.

Keywords: e-Governance, Corruption, Information Asymmetry Theory, Public Choice Theory, Technology Acceptance Model

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